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T4.2: Assessing how policies enable or constrain the resilience of the intensive arable farming system in De Veenkoloniën – Oldambt (The Netherlands).

An application of the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT)

Work Performed by P1, Wageningen University & Research (WUR)

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1 Introduction: Main challenges for intensive arable farming in Veenkoloniën – Oldambt

The *Veenkoloniën* and *Oldambt* are two regions located in the North of the Netherlands; in the Province of Groningen. The region of the Oude Veenkoloniën² consist of a total land area of 55,682 hectares and had a total population of 134,598 in 2017 (Allecijfers.nl, 2018). Oldambt consist of a total land area of 22,673 hectares and has a population of 38,075 in 2018 (Allecijfers.nl, 2018). The agriculture in the Veenkoloniën and Oldambt is characterised by the growing of cereals, starch potatoes, sugar beets and rapeseeds due to heavy clay soil (Smit et al., 2005; Prins et al., 2011; Gemeente Oldambt, 2015). Different challenges related to the economy and changing markets, social-, political- and environmental changes can be identified in the case study region (Provincie Groningen, 2017).

The rural areas in the east of the province of Groningen, and thus also of the case study region, are (historically) characterised by turbulent political developments. During the end of the 19th and the 20th century, the welfare between rich farmers and poor labourers grew. As a result, communism gained ground in the region, became a big political movement in the area and influenced (local) politics (Februari, 2009; Karel, 2012). During the 1960s and 1970s, the agro-industry gradually disappeared; the period was characterised by reorganisation and corporate mergers. Only the company AVEBE remained after the decline of the large potato starch industry of the region (Karel, 2012) (AVEBE was able to grow out to a major player in the regional agricultural sector as one of the only purchasers). Other companies, such as straw cardboard manufactures or sugar beet manufacturers, also disappeared. The economic consequences due to the loss of a large share of the agro-industry were huge (Karel, 2012). Currently, the economic situation of the regions is still lacking compared to other parts of the Netherlands (Februari, 2009; Karel, 2012).

The population in the Province of Groningen, especially in the Veenkoloniën & Oldambt, is both 'degreening' and 'greying'; the proportion of younger people is decreasing, while the proportion of elderly people is increasing (Gemeente Oldambt, 2015; SPG, 2018). The farmer population is also aging, while the labour is demanding. The demand for successors for farms is increasing, but there are fewer young people who can (and want) to take up farming (Provincie Groningen, 2012; Rook, 2014). The problems related to finding successors, in combination with the upscaling of farms, may lead to a further loss of individual farms (consolidation of farm sector), and can decrease employment opportunities in the region (Provincie Groningen, 2012; Rook, 2014).

The introduction of the reform of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in 2013/14 brought challenges for the agricultural sector of the Veenkoloniën & Oldambt. The financial resources for Dutch direct payments were reduced (Provincie Groningen, 2012; Henke et al., 2015). Moreover, historical references used to allocate direct payments are being gradually removed in the Netherlands by 2019 along coupled support for products (Immenga et al., 2012; Dijkma, 2013; Dijkma 2014A; Kuhlman et al., 2014). The reduction in direct payments will be significant for some Dutch agricultural sectors that traditionally received high direct payments, especially the starch potato sector, which is largely concentrated in the Veenkoloniën. The farmers will thus gradually lose a share of stable income (Provincie Groningen, 2012; Dijkma, 2013; Dijkma, 2014A; InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014). Consequently, the farmers need to earn a larger share of their income on the market (Gemeente Oldambt, 2015). At the same time, the selling prices are mostly set by the world market; this means that price fluctuations are more likely and income be less predictable (Immenga et al., 2012).

Farming in the Veenkoloniën & Oldambt is vulnerable to climate change and more extreme weather conditions. The soil in the region is sensitive (in terms of water retention and drainage) and susceptible to drought and extremely wet conditions with flooding as a result (Prins et al. 2011). Profitable crops, foremost potato, are very vulnerable to these extreme weather events, in particular large changes in temperature, periods of drought and wet conditions have a negative effect on yields and the quality of

² The region of the Oude Veenkoloniën is located in multiple municipalities, namely: *Veendam*, *Pekela*, *Stadskanaal*, and the areas of the former municipalities of *Hoogezand-Sappemeer*, *Menterwolde* (both part of *Midden-Groningen*) and *Vlagtwedde* (now part of *Westerwolde*)

the crops (Prins et al., 2011; Diogo et al. 2017). Warm winters can become fatal for the quality of sugar beets, while winter wheat is sensitive to cold temperatures (Prins et al. 2011; Diogo et al, 2017). Farmers are thus facing challenges related to changing weather patterns (climate change) against which the crops need to be protected, or need to adapt the crops they grow.

There is also the challenge of crops that are vulnerable to plant diseases due to bad weather conditions or as a result of intensification. There is a high risk for potatoes to be infected by diseases during very wet periods, such as *Erwinia* spp. The potatoes will then experience second growth or potatoes' tubers might rot (Prins et al., 2011). The intensive farming of potatoes in the area led to the occurrence of nematodes in the soil, resulting in the disease known as '*Aardappelmoetheid*' (tr. potato fatigue) (NVWA, 2018). The disease affects the growth and health of the crops and restricts the cultivation of potatoes that are very profitable. The challenge for the agricultural sector of the Veenkoloniën & Oldambt is therefore how to deal with these types of diseases? There is a demand for the development of crop varieties that are more resistant against diseases and new pesticides.

Summary challenges

- Economically lacking behind
- 'Degreening' and 'greying' (farmer) population
- Direct Payment convergence introduced in the 2013/14 CAP reform
- Climate change and extreme weather conditions
- Plant diseases and vulnerable soils

2 Data

The following thirteen documents were collected for the assessment.

2.1 CAP policy documents

1. EC: European Commission (2013A). CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-13-937_en.htm
2. EC: European Commission (2013B). Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief n° 5*. https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf
3. EC: European Commission (2017A). Agriculture: A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP): for our food, for our countryside, for our environment. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f08f5f20-ef62-11e6-8a35-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>
4. EC: European Commission (2017B). CAP Explained: Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/direct-support/direct-payments/docs/direct-payments-schemes_en.pdf

2.2 National CAP implementation plan(s)

5. EC: European Commission (2016). Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/external-studies/2016/mapping-analysis-implementation-cap/fullrep_en.pdf
6. Henke, R. et al. (2015). Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States. <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3ec35f7a-8776-11e5-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
7. Dijkma, S.A.M. (2013). Kamerbrief³ 06-12-2013 Implementatie Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid. Den Haag: Ministerie van Economische Zaken. Available at: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2013/12/06/kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid>
8. Dijkma, S.A.M. (2014A). Kamerbrief 2014 Uitwerking directe betalingen Gemeenschappelijk landbouwbeleid. Den Haag: Ministerie van Economische Zaken. Available at: <http://www.rijksoverheid.nl/bestanden/documenten-en-publicaties/kamerstukken/2014/06/05/kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen->

³ A *Kamerbrief* (tr. letter to parliament) is a written document of the Dutch government to the Dutch parliament. In the analysed letters to parliament, the former Minister of Economic Affairs explains how the Dutch government wants to implement the CAP in the Netherlands.

[gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid/kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid.pdf](#)

9. Dijkma, S.A.M. (2014B). Kamerbrief 02-04-2014 Invulling Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma 2014-2020. Available at: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/binaries/rijksoverheid/documenten/kamerstukken/2014/04/02/kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020/kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020.pdf>
10. Dijkma, S.A.M. (2014C). Kamerbrief 29-07-2014 Wijzigingen in invulling van de vergroening GLB. Den Haag: Ministerie van Economische Zaken. Available at: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2014/07/29/kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb>

2.3 Other relevant national agricultural policy programs

11. InnovatieVeenkoloniën (2014). Innovatieprogramma Landbouw Veenkoloniën 2012-2020. Noorderdiep: InnovatieVeenkoloniën. Available at: <http://drenthe.begroting-2016.nl/media/Innovatieprogramma%20Veenkolonien.pdf>
12. Provincie Groningen (2012). Landbouwagonde 2012-2015. Groningen: Provincie Groningen. Available at: <https://www.provinciegroningen.nl/beleid/werken-en-ondernemen/grootschalige-landbouw/>
13. Provincie Groningen (2017). Programma Duurzame landbouw Provincie Groningen 2017-2020. Groningen: Provincie Groningen. Available at: <https://www.provinciegroningen.nl/beleid/werken-en-ondernemen/duurzame-landbouw/>

3 Analysis

Section 3 presents the interpretation of the data from the policy documents. The interpretation is done by scoring the data. The scoring is complemented with the argumentation for the given scores. The results of the scoring and the arguments are presented in Table 5 of D4.1 – ResAT. The findings presented in Table 5 then form the basis for the coloured ResAT wheel.

3.1 Scoring and argumentation

Question	Scale (0-5)	Arguments
ROBUSTNESS		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	4	<p>The focus on the short-term is enabled (4) by goals that follow a year-to-year approach.</p> <p>For instance, the CAP makes it possible for Member States to revise the percentage of the national ceiling devoted to the payment for young farmers. The budget for this payment scheme can thus be adjusted on a yearly basis; enabling a short-term vision and the possibility to make marginal adjustment to the payment scheme (Henke et al., 2015).</p> <p>Another example is that the former Dutch State Secretary of Economic Affairs (responsible for agriculture) aimed at making it possible for farmers to change how they want to comply with the Ecological Focus Areas (EFAs) requirement. This enables farmers to adapt a short-term vision as farmer are allowed to change their strategy on a yearly basis (Dijksma, 2014C).</p> <p>The policy goals show a short-term focus as a result of the possibility to make (marginal) adjustments on a yearly basis and therefore can come short in providing a longer secure situation.</p>
1a. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	4	<p>The policy instruments are overall enabling (4) the focus on the short-term because the instruments are implemented for a period of a year or less and are then open for marginal adjustments.</p> <p>First of all, the CAP makes it possible for Member States to vary in their percentage share of transferred funds between Pillar I and Pillar II from year to year. The transfer certainly contributes to flexibility, however, the adjustments that can be made on a yearly basis are only up to 15% in order to maintain the functions of both pillars. The instrument is therefore slightly enabling a short-term focus (2).</p> <p>The Direct Payment Scheme of the CAP can be seen as a payment cycle of one year as farmers have to apply each year in order to receive direct payment (EC, 2017B). The Direct Payment scheme is a major mandatory component of the CAP, targets every active farmer and is simply focused on providing financial means to maintain farming businesses. It is therefore that this instrument is very enabling a short-term focus (5). The ceiling for the basic payments may be increased by a maximum of 3% of the national ceiling on a yearly basis to reduce the risk of unspent funds (Henke et al., 2015). This instrument to resist the undesirable effect of unspent funds is fairly enabling a short-term focus (3).</p> <p>Overall, a short-term focus is enabled through financial instruments (shifts in funding; payments) that focus on short time scales and are then adjusted slightly, however, not too much as the financial instruments should still be able to have its original function.</p>
2a. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled	4	<p>The protection of the status quo is enabled (4) by the policy goals.</p> <p>Many goals within the policy documents were identified by the researcher as robustness – protection of the status quo. There are goals that can be seen as very constraining to maintain the status quo. Decoupling was introduced with as goal to</p>

<p>or constrained by the policy goals?</p>		<p>move the agricultural sector towards the free market (EC, 2017B). This can be seen as introducing more market effects, such as sudden price oscillations, into the agricultural sector. These are (extra) shocks that farmers need to deal with. The Netherlands decided to continue with the decoupling to remove the link between direct payments and specific products (Dijksma, 2013). This constrains the protection of the status quo.</p> <p>The goals of <i>internal and external convergence</i> are fairly constraining the protection of the status quo as they aim to adjust direct payments to increase the fairness of the system. The Netherlands – as a Member State with average direct payments above the EU average – will see its allocation progressively reduced as result of external convergence (Henke et al., 2015). At the same time, internal convergence leads to the removal of historical references as basis of the Direct Payments and the ambitions to grow towards an equal direct payment per hectare (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013A; Dijksma, 2014A). These goals influence the agricultural sector in the Dutch Veenkoloniën and Oldambt due to loss in income, however there will still be an adjusted system of Direct Payments in place to support existing practices. As a way to compensate the loss of income, the region set as a goal to increase the production and to realise higher prices for products (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014); a goal very focused on the current production system and very focused on robustness.</p> <p>However, most of the goals were categorised as fairly enabling or higher (score 3, 4 or 5). The overall goals of the CAP are still focused on maintaining a stable, varied and safe food supply (EC, 2013B; EC, 2017A; EC, 2017B) – the same applies for the Dutch implementation (EC, 2016); and to improve the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and to continue the current agricultural system (EC, 2013B; EC, 2016). Moreover, the EU describes farmers as very important strategic and economic players who cannot be afforded to be lost; argues that the agricultural sector is more dependent on natural factors; and that a public policy is necessary for a sector that is responsible for ensuring food security (EC, 2017A; EC, 2017B) – all reasons to legitimise specific state support for the agricultural sector (agricultural exceptionism) and thus very enabling protection of the status quo.</p> <p>Both voluntary coupled support and protection of areas with natural constraints (ANC) have goals that are very enabling the protection of the status quo. Voluntary coupled support aims at maintaining the current level of production in sectors or regions with specific types of farming; and protecting ANC needs to guarantee the presence of farmers and farms in difficult areas so that these rural communities do not disappear (EC, 2013A; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2017B). Despite both being voluntary, these goals encourage the preservation and continuation of existing practices.</p> <p>Finally, there is the European and national Dutch goal of facilitating generational renewal in the agricultural sector. The goal is to make sure the agricultural system can continue; to ensure continuity and sustain the functioning of the existing system. Generational renewal is a goal that is focused on the future, however its main reason is to make sure the agricultural system can continue to function and maintain desired levels of output. It is therefore enabling the protection of status quo.</p> <p>Overall, the goals seem to prioritise to different extent existing practices or are focused on ensuring that the current farming system can continue to function despite conditions that change. Some goals of policy interventions show constraining factors, however these can mostly be seen as (minor) adjustments instead of wanting to introduce radical change existing patterns.</p>
<p>2b. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The policy instruments enable (4) the protection of the status quo. There are instruments in place that especially introduced for this purpose, but there are also instruments that have a constraining effect on this protection.</p> <p>There are some policy instruments that have a constraining effect on the protection of the status quo. For instance, the measure of <i>decoupling</i> (EC, 2017B). There are also policy interventions that have a constraining effect on the opportunities for farmers to upscale their farming business; these are <i>instruments introduced to reduce the amount of phosphate and nitrogen emissions</i> (Provincie Groningen, 2017).</p>

		<p>The <i>changes to the system of Direct Payments</i> constrain the protection of the status quo. The instruments of internal and external convergence have the effect that Member States and agricultural sectors that historically received large payments need to give in a share of these payments (EC, 2013A; EC, 2013B; EC, 2016). At the same time, Member States have the ability to <i>limit the number of entitlements</i> a farm may receive; meaning that a farm may receive less payments in the future.</p> <p>The mandatory instrument <i>degressivity</i> was introduced from 2014. As a result, the basic payments exceeding €150.000 were reduced by 5% in the Netherlands (EC, 2013A; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016); this slightly constrains the protection of the status quo as it is the minimum a Member State has to do.</p> <p>The Dutch government was concerned that some agricultural sectors would not be able to directly cope if full convergence was already implemented in 2015. The Netherlands therefore opted for <i>full convergence in 2019</i> (Henke et al., 2015). This instrument is fairly enabling the protection of the status quo as it was introduced to ensure that existing agricultural sectors would be able to sustain the adjustments, however, despite given more time for preparations, the adjustments to the Direct Payments will be made.</p> <p>The CAP facilitates information events, training courses and advisory sessions; and provides funding for these type of events (EC, 2016; EC, 2017A). These instruments slightly enable the protection of the status quo. The training and advisory sessions are meant improve farmers' their knowledge on current practices and how to adjust existing farming practices; there are no real reflections on the underlying thoughts/paradigms and therefore qualify better as "cognitive learning". The training of farmers is an instrument to introduce new knowledge to the farmers that can be of use to sustain the functioning of the existing farming system.</p> <p>There are also a lot of financial instruments made available to restructure rural areas and farms (e.g. upgrading infrastructure; construction of storages; lot exchange for logistics and homogenisation; clustering); and for young farmers (Dijksma, 2013, 2014A, 2014B; Provincie Groningen, 2017). Investments are also made to create new potato breeds to be more disease resistance and to increase potato and cereal crop yields (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; Provincie Groningen, 2017). These financial means are meant to make sure the current system can continue to function through better agricultural structures, generational renewal and higher yields.</p> <p>Lastly, the CAP offers several instruments that can be used to preserve certain agricultural products or sectors (<i>Crop specific payments for cotton; Voluntary support; voluntary payments for ANC</i>). These instruments are therefore very enabling the protection of the status quo. However, the Netherlands did hardly implement these instruments (only voluntary coupled support of 0.5%) (EC, 2016).</p> <p>Overall, the CAP has instruments that are focused on the interests of the current farming sector and are introduced especially to ensure the functioning of existing agricultural sectors. Adjustments have been introduced through some instruments that to some extent constrain the preservation of characteristics of the current system. This adjustment is, however, minor. The direct payments are still a major instrument that provides farmers with a basic income. This may reduce the pressure on farmers to change their business. The direct payments are critical for enabling the status quo.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The policy goals do enable (4) the development of buffer resources.</p> <p>The main objective of the CAP is to ensure that farmers of a reasonable income. This goal is leading in the policy and therefore identified multiple times. The Direct Payments are a major source of support and provide a guaranteed income for farmers. The goal is to provide a stable income for farmers independent of market fluctuations (EC, 2013B; EC, 2017A; EC, 2017B). The Direct Payments are also justified as remunerating farmers for providing public goods and for managing the countryside (Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2017A). In addition, specific financial assistance and grants are available for multiple reasons (e.g. to support young farmers or to cope with the effects of climate change). These goals strongly enable buffer resources. They stress the importance of these financial compensations and legitimise the Direct Payments.</p>

		<p>The Direct Payments are however being adjusted with the goal to generate a more equitable distribution of direct payment at national and European level (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013A; Henke et al., 2015). This has effect on the national envelope of the Netherlands and thus on the financial means available for the financial compensation. Moreover, the gradual introduction of the internal convergence does has a constraining effect on the income of farmers in the Veenkoloniën, who produce potatoes (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014). But the original and main goal of the direct payments stays intact, namely to provide farmers with a basic income.</p> <p>Overall, the policy goals do enable the development of the buffer resources – mainly financial – as the goals legitimise the reason for the buffer resources to be in place and are there to compensate farmers.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>The policy instruments strongly enable (5) the development of buffer resources.</p> <p>Some constraining instruments for the development of buffer resources were identified. Firstly, the Netherlands suffer pronounced cuts of -18.4% in their allocations for Direct Payments (external convergence) (Henke et al., 2015). For the Netherlands external convergence is strongly constraining the buffer resource instruments. The cuts of the total available budget for the Netherlands results in less available direct income support for, for instance, the potato sector in the case study region (Provincie Groningen, 2012; Dijksma, 2014A). Moreover, the instrument of internal <i>convergence</i> also has a constraining effect on the buffer resources of farmers in sectors that historically received a large sum of direct income support, as their guaranteed income will decline (Dijksma, 2014A). Lastly, the instrument <i>Degressivity</i> implies a mandatory progressive reduction of large direct payments (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013B; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016). This constrains the available buffer resources for large farms.</p> <p>Despite these changes, the Direct Payment Scheme is still a major instrument of the CAP (discussed in all consulted policy documents) and eminently an instrument that should be identified as a buffer resource; they are a major source of support for farmers in the EU (EC, 2013B). A lot of financial resources are available for the direct payments (but is decreasing) (Dijksma, 2013; Dijksma, 2014A). Transfers from Pillar II to Pillar I slightly enable some extra funding for the Direct Payment Scheme is possible for Member States (Henke et al., 2015).</p> <p>The Direct Payment Scheme consists out of multiple topical payment schemes that each function as a buffer resource. Some of these payments schemes are mandatory for the Member States to implement, others are only voluntary. Applying or not applying of these voluntary schemes has thus influences on the available buffer resources for farmers. The core of the Direct Payment Scheme are the <i>Basic Payments</i> that function as income support for farmers; to remunerate farmers for delivering public goods (EC, 2013A, 201B; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016, 2017A; 2017B). The CAP reform, as well as the Dutch government, aim at reaching a flat-rate payment in which all beneficiaries will ultimately receive the same unit value payment (Dijksma, 2013, 2014A; Henke et al., 2015). The ceiling for basic payments is allowed to increase by a maximum of 3% to reduce the risks of unspent funds (Henke et al., 2015); thus increasing the available funds for buffer resources in some occasions.</p> <p>Cross-compliance has introduced a compulsory basic layer of environmental requirements and obligations to be met in order to receive full funding (EC, 2013b, 2017B). A minimum standards should be reached before receiving funding, therefore slightly constraining farmers in simply receiving funding. However, these requirements are not that strict and are also introduced to reduce abuse of the scheme in order to continue with it.</p> <p>Other mandatory payments schemes are the <i>Young Farmers Scheme</i> that is used for additional financial compensation for young farmers (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013A, 2013B; Dijksma, 2014B, Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016, 2017B); and the <i>Green Payment Scheme</i> used to provide farmers with financial compensation for obliging to agricultural practices that are beneficial for the climate and environment (EC, 2013A, 2013B; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016, 2017B). Related are the payments to maintain</p>

		<p>or convert to organic farming practices and methods (EC, 2016). The Green Payments and payments for organic farming are meant as financial compensation, however are regarded as fairly enabling due to the fact that the payments are used to adjust the production strategies of farms – more related to adaptation.</p> <p>There are also voluntary payments schemes available for Member States, such as the <i>Small Farmers Scheme, Redistributive Payments or Payments for ANC</i> (EC, 2013A, 2013B; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016, 2017B). The Netherlands do not apply these schemes.</p> <p>The CAP thus introduces a great set of financial support instruments. The financial resources are used to mostly preserve the functionalities of the current system. The financial support schemes are used to make sure farmers have a decent income and are better able to resist the unpredictability of markets. A standard amount of income is set for farmers, which could perhaps discourage them to change their farming practices.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>The goals identified are very enabling (5) other modes of managing risk</p> <p>The CAP acknowledges that farmers need to cope with special characteristics of the agricultural commodity markets. The CAP therefore wants to make it possible for farmers to better respond to market instability or fast falling prices through mutual funds and insurance schemes. The goal is to provide an effective safety net through market intervention in the context of external uncertainties; the CAP reform aimed at public intervention that is more responsive and efficient and to provide private storage aid (EC 2013A, 2013B; EC, 2017A).</p> <p>In addition, the Dutch government wants to continue the support of extreme weather insurance so that farmers can be compensated for weather induced damage to their crops (Dijkma, 2013).</p> <p>Slightly enabling other modes of risk managements are the goals of the EU to enhance the accessibility, use and quality of information and communication technologies. To make sure that farmers in rural areas can have access to the latest information and connect them to networks (EC, 2016; EC 2017A). Or the goal to improve the negotiation position of farmers in the food chain as this should help them to better anticipate on market disturbances and to enforce, for instance, better prices.</p> <p>These goals all are introduced to help the farming system in case of a shock (e.g. market or weather) to bounce back to the original state – thus very enabling other modes of managing risks – or to improve the position of farmers to better participate to risks and take preventive measures. There are differences in the extent to which the goals enable the other modes of risk managements, however constraining goals are not identified.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>The policy instruments identified are overall strongly enabling (5) other modes of managing risks.</p> <p>The CAP has several instruments installed that should help the farming system in case of (mostly) economic characterised shocks. The instruments are used to make sure the shock does not further escalate and to help the system quickly moving back to its initial and acceptable state. The EC is can activate, through <i>safeguard clauses, emergency market support measures</i> to respond to general market disturbances (sudden price drops as a result of temporarily oversupply or of a health scare) (EC, 2013A, 2013B, 2017A, 2017B). In several cases the EC may even authorise producer organisations to take certain temporarily measures collectively to stabilise a sector in case of a crisis (EC,2013A). Lastly, a large amount of financial funds are made available as a crisis reserve at European and the Dutch national level (Dijkma, 2013; EC, 2013A). These instruments are all examples of public intervention to respond to a shock and keep the shock in control; and very enabling other modes of risk management.</p> <p>Another instrument that strongly enables other modes of risks management is the <i>risk management toolkit</i>. It offers marketing tools and insurance schemes for crops</p>

		<p>and animals (EC, 2013A, EC 2017A). The Dutch government also provides a weather insurance scheme for farmers to restore potential damage due to adverse weather events (Dijkma, 2013, 2014A, 2014B). These instruments are safety nets that can help to bounce back after a shock.</p> <p>The CAP also offers support for investments in preventive measures against natural disasters, climatic events and catastrophic events, and for investments in the restoration of agricultural land and production after a damaging event (EC, 2016). These are instruments that enable farmers to anticipate disturbances, but are seen as less enabling as the previous instrument. The reason is that it offers advice and support, and places responsibility with the farmers instead of direct actions that the market measures offer.</p> <p>Lastly, there are instruments that are categorised as slightly enabling compared to the previous instruments. Collective buying and facilitating producer cooperations make it possible for farmers to reduce costs. A simple mean for farmers to reduce individual risks. Or the installation of ICT infrastructure to provide farmers with better access to information and connection to monitoring systems (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; EC, 2016).</p> <p>Overall, the instruments are all, to different extent, enabling other modes of risk management. The instruments are (mostly) installed to respond to a risk and should help the farming system to quickly return to its initial state after a shock. The instruments need to make sure that shocks do not escalate and prevent the current system to collapse.</p>
ADAPTABILITY		
<p>1a. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The policy goals in the analysed documents enable (4) a focus on the middle-long term.</p> <p>The goal of the Dutch government for their decision for “full convergence in 2019” is clear. They want to offer the most gradual transition towards the equal payments per hectare as possible. The government recognises that this change can have disturbing effects on agricultural sectors, such as the potato sector in the case study. They therefore want to offer the affected farmers a longer time period so that can adjust and adapt accordingly (Dijkma, 2013; Dijkma, 2014A; EC, 2016). This aim was also suggested by the EU (EC, 2017B). This goal is enabling a middle-long term focus. On the one hand, it shows awareness that adjusting the system of Direct Payments – a core aspect of the CAP and fully integrated in the farming systems – requires some time; on the other hand, there is willingness to change this (financial) strategy based on past experience.</p> <p>The question, however, remains if the adjustments to the Direct Payments are rigorous enough to withstand future disturbances. Moreover, the adjustment is also aimed at maintaining the same function of providing farmers with basic income; preserving a current system characteristic.</p> <p>Other middle-to-long term focused goals relate to changing the current agricultural practices towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly forms of producing food the coming years (organic farming or nature inclusive agriculture and reducing CO₂ emissions) (Provincie Groningen, 2012, 2017). Or another goal is to change agricultural activities to the changing climate (Provincie Groningen, 2012). These goals encourage actions to adjust current practices, but are aware that this would require some time. Moreover, the goals are aimed at changing farming strategies without changing the operational logic of the farm or farming system.</p> <p>Lastly, there are middle-to-long term aspects recognisable in other goals, such as aiming for projects or monitoring systems of several years. These goals do ask for a middle-to-long term focus regarding their planning and implementation; but it is unclear if this would lead to adaptation of the system.</p> <p>Overall, the identified goals aim to implement changes to avoid or withstand future disturbances without changing the operational logic of the farming system and aware that this probably takes time.</p>

<p>1b. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The instruments fairly enable (3) the focus on the middle-to-long-term.</p> <p>The Young Farmer Payments can to a certain extent be regarded as a middle-to-long-term instrument as the payments are granted for a maximum of five years. The Young Farmer Payments are the only payments that can be granted for a longer time period. However, the payments are introduced to promote generational renewal and to make sure that young farmers can maintain the current functionalities of the farming system and thus to sustain the existing functioning of the system itself. The instrument is therefore only slightly enabling adaptation as it shows signs of robustness.</p> <p>Most instruments that focus on the middle-to-long-term can be qualified as monitoring instruments. These instruments are brought into place for multiple years to provide insight in experiments, projects or the effects of some policy interventions (Dijksma, 2014A; InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014). The CAP itself also introduced a monitoring system for the whole CAP period 2014-2020 that should provide feedback for the CAP goals and instruments (EC, 2013A). Monitoring should help with learning from experiences and with applying changes that benefit the system. However, the monitoring would only have an effect when results are actually used and monitoring can also be considered as a way of postponing necessary measures.</p> <p>Lastly, the provided option of "Full convergence in 2019" enables a middle-to-long-term focus as it enables the quick action of changing the Direct Payment system, but it also recognised that existing farms and farming culture require some time to adjust to this change.</p>
<p>2a. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The policy goals differ in their extent of enabling flexibility. It was therefore decided that the goals fairly enable (3) flexibility.</p> <p>Some goals of the CAP provide no room for national decision making. For instance, the goal of increasing diversification of crops and market intervention goals (Dijksma, 2013). These are therefore very constraining flexibility as there are binding requirements and decided top-down.</p> <p>The CAP reform had as goal to make it better possible for Member States to decide over how to allocate finances between the two pillars. It is therefore possible to transfer up to 15% between the two pillars (EC, 2013B; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016). The Netherlands decided to transfer fund from pillar I to Pillar II.</p> <p>Within Pillar I – the Direct Payment Scheme – there was also the goal to enable more flexibility. National governments can decide which of the various payment schemes to finance from the national envelope (EC, 2013B; EC, 2017B). There is the possibility for member states to combine different direct payment schemes to ensure efficient support to farmers adapted to national circumstances (EC, 2017B); or to implement a simplified payment scheme that replaces all the other payment schemes (Henke et al., 2015). In addition, it is possible to accentuate different measures to better support young farmers in their local contexts.</p> <p>It was decided at EU level to provide three options of internal convergence to provide the Member States with the possibility to choose for internal convergence suitable for the national context (EC, 2013A). The Member States can also decide if they want to introduce other measures to rebalance payments even more, but this is not mandatory (EC, 2013B).</p> <p>There is a bit flexibility in deciding how payments are granted, but it allows not for major differences between member states; they are allowed to change small thing, but within limits set by the EU. Moreover, the Netherlands decided to apply the basic payment at national level, considering the whole territory as a single region (Henke et al., 2015); the Netherlands aims for a much as possible equal implementation per province. This constraints the idea of regional differences (differences in contexts between regions) and possibilities to adapt payments accordingly.</p>

		<p>Within the Greening Measures, the EU also aimed to introduce some flexibility in how to implement the measures. It was made possible for Member States to introduce equivalent measures as alternative to the proposed Greening Measures (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013A; Dijksma, 2014C; InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014C; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2016, 2017B). The outcome in this case seems to be more important than the means how the green objectives are reached. Moreover, through allowing farmers to collectively arrange EFA, the CAP enables flexibility for farmers to find other ways to oblige to Greening requirements and better possible to reach adjacent EFAs (Dijksma, 2013, 2014A).</p> <p>Lastly, the CAP aims to allow Member States to adjust and compose their own Rural Development Programmes so that the measures are adapted to the specific needs of the country or regions (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2017A). This flexibility is however limited by fact that it is only allowed to choose from a specific list of instruments. In addition, the Netherlands had as goal to reduce the amount of instruments provided in the Rural Development Programmes to reach a clearer focus and a more consistent approach (Dijksma, 2013).</p> <p>Overall, the goals of the CAP was to provide more flexibility for the Member States in how to compose the Pillar I and Pillar II. However, the flexibility is limited due to (legislative) guidelines through providing a limited set of options from which can be chosen - a specific course of actions.</p>
<p>2b. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>Flexibility is fairly enabled (3) by the policy instruments.</p> <p>Most of the instruments that are relevant flexibility were already mentioned during the discussion of the goals (previous section).</p> <p>Firstly, there is the possibility to transfer funds between Pillar I and Pillar II, and it is possible to vary the percentage per year. Also, the Member State can decide out of a set of voluntary payments schemes to implement. In addition, there were three options available for <i>internal convergence</i>. These instruments do to a small extent enable flexibility. These instruments do of course make it possible for member states to make adaptations corresponding to the national context; however, this flexibility is limited due to the limited and ready-made options provided. This shows some form of steering to a specific course of action.</p> <p>Within the Greening Measures flexibility is enabled through the option to introduce equivalent measures. These equivalent measures can replace the prescribed three Greening Measures if it is proven to be equally (or even more) effective in reaching the greening objectives. This allows member states to come up with a different mean that can be used to reach a desired outcome. It is less focus on the mean, but more on reaching the goal. The Netherlands have chosen to introduce a sustainability certification scheme as an equivalent measure as this system was already in place and proven to be effective.</p> <p>Lastly, the possibility of collectively implement EFAs shows that the Greening Measures are not too strict and means-oriented in how objectives should be reached.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The goals indicated in the policy documents are fairly enabling (3) variety. There are not that many constraining-related goals indicated; however, there is a difference in the extent the found goals enable variety. It is decided to give the overall score of 3 as the slightly enabling and the (very) enabling goals weigh against each other.</p> <p>A constraining goal is the result of another goal, namely to simplify administrative procedures through the Small Farmers Scheme. A farmer that enters this small farmers scheme is exempted from greening obligations and cross-compliance conditions (Henke et al., 2015). The Greening and cross-compliance conditions are, however, conditions that ask farmers to adapt their activities mostly out of environmental concerns. The Small Farmers Scheme can have an (unwanted) constraining effect on the variety.</p>

Variety goals aim to create or encourage diversity. It is concerned with possibly changing the homogeneity of farming practices. The Dutch government has stated that their ambition is to let the agricultural sector contribute to (inter)national issues on food security, biodiversity, energy, water, climate and animal welfare – a variety of goals (Dijksma, 2013). A similar ambition was found with the Province of Groningen as they want more attention for broadening agricultural practices. They are aware that the development of agricultural nature conservation is a step in the right way, however, they want to aim for more activities (Provincie Groningen, 2012). The goals are focused on trying to adapt agricultural practices in such a way that it can contribute to multiple (integrative) issues. These are overall statements that enable variety.

The policy goals show that variety should be reached through returning themes which will be discussed below:

Slightly enabling are goals that aim to introduce new crops as way to create variety and slow soil degradation (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; EC, 2017B). It can offer farmers with new outlet market, however it does not primarily diversify the agricultural practices at the farm level if it would just replace another crop.

Another way of reaching variety is by encouraging farmers to contribute in producing and supplying local (renewable) energy. Very enabling is, for instance, the goal to produce a significant part of the total energy of the Veenkoloniën at the local scale and in an environmentally friendly manner; eventually to considerably reduce CO₂ emissions, but also producing additional income (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014). Similar goals are stated by the EU (EC, 2016); and the Province of Groningen (2012, 2017) even sees the possibility of realising 'village energy collaborations', in which farmers take up the role of supplier.

Goals are identified that are specifically aimed at greening and environmental issues. The Dutch government stated that they want to realise the greening of the Direct Payments with ambition as they argue that agro-biodiversity, quality of the environment and protecting the climate are very valuable for the quality of the living environment and agricultural production (Dijksma, 2013). This is an ambitious goal that is enabling variety. The EU also aims to restore and preserve the biodiversity and scenic value of the landscape in rural areas; and to promote agricultural practices with a lower environmental impact (EC, 2013B, 2017A). The Greening Measures were introduced with the aim to mitigate the environmental impact of current farming practices and to introduce more diversity to these practices (EC, 2017B); but the measures are bare effective and can hardly be seen as adding green elements to the farming practices. Finally, similar goals are also formulated at the regional scale. The overall aim is to further develop the agricultural sector in a sustainable manner. Here, the focus is however more on adopting the greening measures in such a way that it fits the case study area and other objectives (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; Provincie Groningen, 2017). The stated goals can mostly be considered as generalities, however the goals differ due to the fact the aim is to adapt the measures to the regional context.

A separate goal of the Direct Payments is mentioned by the EU, namely that it is also a way of enhancing other roles of the farmer (e.g. nature and landscape manager), promote environmentally friendly farming practices and to set rules related to the environment and animal welfare rules. This is indeed true, but this is not the main goal of the direct payments; moreover, this goal is later added to 'green' the direct payments.

Lastly, the goal of **Rural Development** is to contribute to multiple issues that are present in rural areas (EC, 2013B; Dijksma, 2013, 2014A). It aims for an integrative approach as the goal is to combine multiple measures to focus on a specific region or sector (Dijksma, 2013). The Dutch government aims to contribute to European and international environmental and water goals through the national Rural Development Programme. Moreover, the Rural Development Programme also needs to help with creating a competitive, innovative, sustainable and future-proof agricultural sector; this should be reached through a set of different themes (climate, energy, environment, animal welfare, quality and safety of food, animal- and plant health and

		<p>planning (Dijksma, 2013). The LEADER approach is part of the Rural Development Programme. The goal of the LEADER approach is to contribute to social-economic development and employment rates in rural areas, innovation of agricultural businesses, the living environment in rural areas. It is aware of that there are multiple problems in the area and that rural areas are more than places where food is being produced. It wants to realise integrative projects that help to realise multiple objectives, such as innovation, energy reduction and production, water quality, the environment and employment. (Dijksma, 2013).</p> <p>Overall, the goals relevant to variety mostly aim for the same themes. The most reoccurring theme relates to that farming practices should become more environmentally friendly, but specific steps to reach are mostly amiss. This holds also true for the other goals; they stay at a quite general level and do not state any concrete objectives. This makes it harder to assess to what extent the goals actually contribute to allowing variety.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The instruments identified are fairly enabling (3) variety.</p> <p>The EU provides a whole set of support measures, each meant to reach a different goal, but all focused on adapting and diversifying (farming) practices and strategies that should benefit the environment and rural communities (EC, 2016). These measures are however, seen as slightly or fairly enabling as they are described as sub-measures; and the use of the word 'support' makes it quite abstract and less strong.</p> <p>Fairly enabling variety are the grants made available by the EU to create greater visibility for organic farming, to maintain organic farming and to promote farmers to convert to organic farming (EC, 2013A). This diversifies farming practices within the system and allows farmers to adapt their strategies without changing too much of the operational logic of the farm. Different financial means are also made available for management and restoration of nature and landscapes, and improving the quality of the water at the regional scale (Dijksma, 2013, 2014A, 2014B; InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014). Interesting is that these financial means are mostly co-financed (mostly almost for 50%) by other (regional) actors (provinces or water boards). Moreover, the Netherlands have chosen to transfer funds from Pillar I to Pillar II; and thus increasing the funds available for Rural Developments (Henke et al., 2015). These financial instruments enable (to different extent) the implementation of a variety of goals related to developing the environmental aspects of the farming system.</p> <p>The focus on sustainability is clear in Pillar II since at least 30% of the budget for the Rural Development Programme must be reserved for voluntary measures beneficial for the environment and climate change which are adapted to local needs (EC, 2013B). It can fairly enable variety as it provides a set percentage of financial means for instruments focused on adapting farming practices, however the fact that the means are voluntary means that implementation is not guaranteed.</p> <p>Slightly enabling variety are the three Greening Measures introduced by the CAP: (1) <i>Crop diversification</i>; (2) <i>Maintaining permanent grassland</i>; and (3) <i>Ecological Focus Areas (EFA)</i> (EC, 2013A, 2013B; Dijksma, 2014A, 2014C; Henke et al., 2015; EC, 2017A, 2017B). These three instruments should be implemented to receive green payments. The measures are aimed at adapting farming activities to take into account environmental concerns. The instruments introduce some heterogeneity to the traditional farming practices, however the instruments are not that ground breaking and more a formality for receiving green payments; moreover as penalties are given to farmers that do not satisfy these requirements for green payments (Henke et al., 2015).</p> <p>Different environmental management and environmentally friendly agricultural practices are introduced as to increase the variety in biodiversity in rural areas (Provincie Groningen, 2012). Building on this idea, Nature Inclusive Agriculture is being explored as a mean to further increase the environmental sustainability of the agricultural sector by decreasing environmental impact, strengthening ecosystems and perhaps contributing to a circular economy (Provincie Groningen, 2017). It is a</p>

		<p>way of changing the production of food, but the core of the farm stays the same. However, this instrument is only coded as slightly enabling. It is introduced as a new way of reaching environmental goals, but it is not yet clear how it needs to be implemented and in practice can contribute.</p> <p>Lastly, the Dutch Rural Development Programme – the POP3 (<i>Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma 3</i>) - is an instruments that could strongly enable variety. The programme broadens it approach by focusing on rural areas rather than only on farming businesses; it is therefore a programme focused on multiple issues, especially on sustainable development and renewal, that ask for an integrative approach. It also became clear in the variety-goals section that the Rural Development Programme has set goals to address specific needs and challenges that face rural areas (EC, 2017A; Provincie Groningen, 2017). The POP3 is also used to co-finance different means, such as agricultural nature management or the LEADER Approach (Dijksma, 2013).</p> <p>Overall, the instruments are meant to address more social and environmental aspects related to the farming systems. Measures are introduced that ask for adapting regular practices, however the measures seem not to require major change in farming practices. This is partly the result of that the policy documents mostly stay with suggesting the instruments instead of actually announcing that the implementation would definitely take place.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The goals enable (4) social learning.</p> <p>A critical aspect of social learning is that the learning happens during social processes in which different actors develop, share and preserve knowledge. The ambition of sharing knowledge through social interaction is widely present in the policy documents. The policy goals aim to strengthen the links between different fields of research (agriculture and forestry) (EC, 2013B; EC, 2016); bridging the gap between science and practice through training sessions, information events and workshops with stakeholders; increasing the relationships between stakeholders and knowledge institutes (Dijksma, 2013; EC, 2013B; InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; EC, 2016). The CAP also has the LEADER Approach which was developed with as goal to bring local actors together and to encourage them to address local issues (EC, 2017A). The LEADER Approach aims to form partnerships at a regional or local level between different stakeholders and sectors to contribute to rural development. This goal is a good example of social learning.</p> <p>Overall, the goals stay quite abstract. It therefore remains the question to what extent these ambitions indeed lead to new insights that could result in adjustments of practices better suited to manage disturbances. However, the fact that ideas and ambitions regarding sharing knowledge through social settings is mentioned regularly in most policy documents contributed to the score of 4.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>Social learning is fairly enabled (3) by the policy instruments.</p> <p>The majority of the instruments that are focused on social learning can be categorised as financial resources; or as organising events, projects, developing example cases, training sessions and dialogues with stakeholders. Typically for these instruments is that they are described in an abstract manner.</p> <p>The Dutch government did engage stakeholders already early on during the development and implementation of the CAP. It informed the stakeholders through different communication instruments and stakeholder organisations were invited to provide input for the process (EC, 2016). At the regional scale, dialogues about the future of the agricultural sector were held in the province of Groningen. Different stakeholders were invited to these dialogues. The conversations between stakeholders led to discussions about different themes. The results were documents that presents the potential building blocks for the vision with an action perspective in favour of the sustainable development of the agricultural sector (Provincie Groningen, 2012).</p>

		These examples of how social learning is implemented are limited in the policy documents.
TRANSFORMABILITY		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	<p>The goals that are mentioned in the policy documents can only be identified as slightly enabling (2) a focus on the long-term.</p> <p>The policy documents do mention some goals in which a long term focus can be recognised. These goals ask for a transformative change and are extended over a longer time span, mostly over the time span of the current CAP (until 2020). All of these goals are aimed at sustainability themes; to reduce the environmental impact of the agricultural sector, such as 'closing the mineral loop within agricultural practices at a local scale', 'making the agricultural sector leader in sustainability' or 'to make the agricultural sector CO₂ neutral' (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014; Provincie Groningen, 2012). The goals can be described as ambitious because their achievement would require transformative change. The downside is, however, that the goals remain quite abstract and general while it is unclear how these goals should be reached and which smaller in-depth changes are aimed for as intermediate steps. Strategies to reach the more transformative goals are missing.</p> <p>Overall, the goals do hardly enable a long-term focus. There are goals that aim for transformative change that would require a longer period of time to take place. However, the goals remain abstract and it is unclear how these goals will be reached.</p>
1b. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	1	No distinctive instruments that focus on the long term were recognised in the consulted policy documents.
2a. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	<p>The policy goals in the policy documents overall slightly enable (2) the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo.</p> <p>The CAP had as goal to iron out some legal loopholes in who can receive direct payments; they therefore introduced the term 'active farmer' (EC, 2013A). They want to make the criteria more selective and strict to reduce abuse. This is slightly dismantling incentives that support the status quo as it is a slight adjustment of the existing pattern that can be recognised as perverse. However, one can question if this really transforming the system. Therefore a low score is given.</p> <p>The CAP also wants to ensure improved competitiveness for produces on the domestic world markets. It wants to provide famers with better opportunities to respond to market developments. Farmers should not be blocked in their practices due to block-ins, such as quota's. This is their main reason for abolishing production constraints (EC, 2013A).</p> <p>Finally, the Dutch government stated that it was no longer justifiable that certain sectors received large sums of direct payments per product or animal and that this did not suit the new CAP. (Dijksma, 2014A). The Dutch government thus seems to be aware of the possible negative effects of the direct payments on certain sectors. The goal is then to change these "knelsectoren" (difficult sectors) by transforming their business as usual, however the aim is also to make sure that these sectors survive the reduction in direct payments. The aim is two-fold (transformative-robustness) and therefore scored as slightly enabling the dismantling of status quo.</p> <p>Overall, the policy documents analysed do have a small amount of goals that have the ambition to change aspects that result in path dependency; the goals express the intention to change the existing patterns. However, these goals are scarce in the policy documents or mentioned carefully.</p>

<p>2b. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>The dismantling of incentives that support the status quo is, except for one instruments, not enabled (1) by the policy instruments.</p> <p>The CAP introduced that <i>production constrains</i> will be removed, such as <i>the sugar quota</i> (EC, 2013A, 2013B). The goal of the removal was already discussed in the previous section. The removal of the production constrains is an intervention that addresses a path dependency. This is an instrument that serves to change the way the current system is functioning. Despite this being a big change, no other instruments that could have a dismantling effect on the status quo were recognised in the policy documents. CAP instruments are hardly introduced to fundamentally change existing patterns of behaviour.</p> <p>At the same time, the area-based direct payments, which provide a significant incentive to maintain the status quo (at least in terms of land ownership), are maintained.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>In-depth learning aspects can hardly be recognised within the goals of the policy goals. The goals are therefore not enabling (1).</p> <p>In-depth learning means that actors in the farming system need to reflect and challenge dominant mind-sets to then fundamentally change them; these goals should enable the actors to question the paradigm of the farming system they are part of. This type of learning was not evident within the policy goals found in the material. If a goal could qualify as in-depth learning, it remained still vaguely unclear if knowledge was gained from different sectors or working fields; therefore making them hard to identify. It is also this reason why the limited number of in-depth learning goals is scored low.</p> <p>There are research funds made available by the EU that are devoted to develop new farming systems so that farmers can respond to the variety of challenges that lie ahead. This aim shows that there is a form of awareness with the EU of that the current system is not fully capable to function properly within the current ecological, social economic structures. Or there are a minimum amount of goals that state to use experiences or projects as input for policies and decision making; it uses insights to reflect on current practices and to discuss the future of (new) policies. However, more of these type of statements or goals are hardly present in the policy documents. Moreover, you can question if this would lead to intensive reconsideration of underlying thoughts.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>No distinctive instruments that focus on in-depth learning were recognised in the consulted policy documents. Therefore, a score of (1) was given.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>The goals within the policy documents are slightly enabling (2) the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations.</p> <p>Interesting is that the goals that enable the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations are almost all formulated at the national or (case) region scale. The Dutch government aims to support farmers – with physical investments – in the development of new prototypes that need testing and for the introduction of new innovations on the market for the use in the agricultural sector (Dijksma, 2013). Within the Veenkoloniën, there is the ambition to develop as an “area of experimentation”; new innovations or agricultural techniques will be developed and tested in the Veenkoloniën. One of the goals is to develop and test new fertilization systems, monitoring systems and techniques to detect diseases early on (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014).</p> <p>The underlying aim of the innovations can all be traced back to wanting to improve agricultural production within the current farming system. You can therefore question</p>

		<p>if these goals have as aim to transform the farming system; there is attention for innovation and support to accelerate innovation, however not every innovation can be qualified as transforming the system. This is also the case for the scarce set of goals within the policy documents. They are therefore overall scored as slightly enabling.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The policy instruments fairly enable (3) the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations.</p> <p>Firstly, in the Netherlands, the organisation "InnovatieVeenkoloniën" was started to specifically focus on innovative projects and experiments in the case study region. The organisation is a collaboration between different actors that come together to develop projects that should lead to improvements in agricultural practices in the context of the region. The organisation has set up its own agenda that describes multiple means in how they want to accelerate innovations for the regional agricultural sector and its own budget. Furthermore, the organisation is supported by the national government as the government provides financial resources for this innovation programme (Dijksma, 2014A). This specific organisation therefore very enables the acceleration of niche innovations.</p> <p>Secondly, the Dutch government also has access to a specific instruments that should help new (niche) innovations to be introduced to the markets. The instrument is used to reduce the risks and barriers that come with entering the markets – the so-called "<i>Garantstelling Marktintroductie voor risicovolle Innovaties</i>" (GMI) (Dijksma, 2013). Financial resources are made available for this instrument (Dijksma, 2014A); however these are relatively small compared to the other instruments the Dutch government announced as reaction to the 2013/14 CAP reform.</p> <p>Lastly, other mentioned instruments stay quite inexplicit in that they only mention that investments and (financial) support for the development of innovations or innovative projects should be made possible (EC, 2016; Provincie Groningen, 2017). They are seen as slightly enabling as there is support for new ideas or products, but is unclear what they mean with 'innovation'.</p> <p>The CAP provides business start-up aid for different topics (for the development of small farms; for non-agricultural practices; for young farmers) (EC, 2016). Business start-up aid is particularly focused new comers to the farming sector. Start-ups are mostly entrepreneurial and create new ideas and business strategies. This enables the acceleration of niche innovations, but because the instruments are only directed at a marginal group of farmers it is fairly enabling (3).</p>

3.2 ResAT Wheels

Figure 3.2A: ResAT policy goals

Figure 3.2B: ResAT policy instruments

3.2.1 Explanatory text for the ResAT Wheels

Each of the resilience characteristics received a score based on the argumentations provided in section 3.1. A colour was assigned to each score based on a traffic light concept (see table 6 of the ResAT protocol). This resulted in two ResAT wheels: one for the goals, and one for the instruments. The next section provides an explanation for the wheels.

Table 6: Assigned colours per Likert score

<i>Question: To what extent do the policy's goals and instruments enable or constrain the</i>		
Answers enabling	Answers constraining	Scores
Not clear		0
Not enabling	Very constraining	1
Slightly enabling	Constraining	2
Fairly enabling	Fairly constraining	3
Enabling	Slightly constraining	4
Very enabling	Not constraining	5

A mix of colours

Overall, robustness scored not lower than a score of 4, both for the goals and instruments. This means that currently the CAP and the implementation in the Netherlands is enabling the robustness well. This finding is interesting when you compare it to the scores given to the two other resilience types. In general, adaptability scored lower than robustness and received mostly mediocre scores, especially for the instruments (scores of mostly 3). However, transformability almost only received scores of 2 or lower, except for “niche innovation instruments” (score 3). These findings show that there seems to be an unbalance between the three types of resilience; goals and instruments that enhance the robustness of the farming system seems to be more present than adaptability and even more than transformability. This unbalance can be considered as a weakness as it is argued that overall resilience of a farming system is dependent on a right balance between robustness, adaptability and transformability.

Also, it is interesting to see that there are differences in scores between the policy goals and the policy instruments of the same characteristics. In almost all the cases, except for ‘buffer resources’ and ‘niche innovations’, the instruments score the same score or a lower score. This shows that there is a discrepancy between the influence of policy goals and policy instruments

4 Stakeholder check

4.1 How selected and approached

The stakeholder check was organised at the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (LNV). The Ministry is responsible for agricultural policies and the CAP in the Netherlands.

The Ministry of LNV was approached via one of the policy officers working at the department involved with the future of the CAP. The policy officer was our contact person and was contacted by email and telephone. The contact person spread the invitation at the department. Four policy officers of LNV were present during the stakeholder check. Each of the participants were involved in and had experience with the CAP.

4.2 Method

The stakeholder check was organised to discuss the analysis and the results; it functioned as a way to validate the results, but also to strengthen the results via practical insights of the participants. The meeting had the following structure:

- (1) General introduction of the SURE-Farm project and the objectives of Work Package 4
- (2) Explanation of the concept of Resilience (Robustness, Adaptability and Transformability), the ResAT and the aim of the analysis
- (3) Explanation of the objectives of the stakeholder check; and informing the participants on how their contributions will be used in the research.
- (4) Short introduction of the case region, in which was emphasised that the case provided a context to the analysis.
- (5) Presentation of the coloured ResAT wheels
- (6) Discussion round: a set of topics (based on the arguments in section 3.2) were selected and discussed with the participants. These topics were selected as they were argued to be noticeable and to be able to facilitate a discussion. The topics were:
 - a. *Short-, middle and long-term vision in the CAP*
 - b. *Generational renewal*
 - c. *Direct payments*
 - d. *Dismantling the status quo*
 - e. *Learning*
 - f. *(Niche) innovations*

The focus of the stakeholder check was on the opinions of the stakeholders and, therefore, it was arranged that they could express their opinion during the whole meeting, especially during the discussion-part of the meeting.

The stakeholder meeting took place at a location chosen by the contact person on 7 September 2018. The participants are kept anonymous on request.

Notes were taken during the stakeholder check. These notes and formed the base for the summary of the stakeholders perspectives (Section 4.3).

4.3 Perspectives stakeholders

Outcome 1: *The interpretation of the concept of resilience is dependent on the political and cultural context of a Member State.*

The stakeholders mentioned multiple times that the idea of resilience is also dependent on the national-, political-, and cultural context of the Member State. It was discussed that you may notice two different ways of approaching the concept of resilience in Europe: (1) Resilience is mostly only robustness, meaning that the system (e.g. the Direct payment scheme) needs to be kept in place as it is now; and (2) The state should not interfere too much in the system; farmers have also their own responsibility in making themselves resilient, for instance via insurances (the more Dutch approach).

The meaning of resilience also depends on the goal you set. Do you want to maintain every farming business, and every sector? Or is your aim to support only viable farming businesses? Or even whole rural areas? For instance, several Member States have regions that are confronted with depopulation. In addition, a large share of the electorate can be found in these regions. Maintaining rural areas is, therefore, an important (political) goal. This is not so much the case for the Netherlands.

Member states differ in their approach and the meaning they give to resilience. This was an argument which returned multiple times during the discussion. It was interesting to hear that (European) historical developments, cultural differences and national political dynamics of a Member State determines how the concept of resilience is understood and how policies is adapted to this understanding.

Outcome 2: *The Direct Payments can be seen as slowing down change.*

From an economic- and transition perspective, you can argue that the Direct Payments should be seen mostly as constraining change. This perspective is also quite in line with the Dutch vision on the CAP, while in most other EU Member States the Direct Payments are seen as necessary and essential in supporting the system. It thus depends on the context of the country if Direct Payments constrain or enhance the resilience.

The opinion was shared that simple payments for legal requirements will lead to that people will do the minimum of work; this does not work in achieving collective goals. The Direct Payments can be seen as conditionality, and this does not necessarily work. Despite that the Dutch agricultural sector is quite able to function on its own, it still needs the Direct Payments of the CAP. This applies even more to other Member States

It was mentioned that the Commission mentions resilience constantly; however, direct payments stay untouched and are protected instruments. At the same time, there is almost no attention for risk management. Member States now have the obligation to implement at least one risk management instrument, but this is even challenged by some Member States as this will be at the expense of the direct payments.

This is in line with the argumentation of section 3.1 in which was argued that the Direct Payments are a very decisive buffer resource and could discourage farmers to change their farming practices. There seems to be a form of fear with farmers and even some Member States to lose the Direct Payments.

Risks

An interesting point related to risks was brought up by the stakeholders. Farmers make trade-offs between risks and resilience, or perhaps profits. Some farmers decided to produce products with a lot of risks, but want high profits. Or decided to export to Russia for high profits, but with the risks of a possible boycott; or decided to not take weather insurance. However, when things go wrong, there is a strong voice for that the government should help to overcome this problem; they want to take risks, but do not want to bear the consequences. Risk behaviour plays an interesting role in the agricultural sector.

Outcome 3: *The CAP as a policy is quite resilient.*

The participants agreed upon that the CAP is almost entirely focused on the short term. Changes that are associated with a long term vision can only happen very slowly in small steps. However, it was also argued that changes only happen when the situation asks for it (e.g. changes made due to WTO agreements). It was even mentioned that Mansholt – at the end of his career - was surprised of how hard it became to change the CAP.

Something that already exists is always hard to change. Instead of changing the policy, new goals or elements are added to the current policy (layering). This contributes to the fact that the CAP keeps on existing (in its traditional form). In that sense, the CAP can be considered as very resilient. It depends on your personal (political) views and goals if you could say that the CAP fails. You can perhaps argue that the CAP fails as it does not allow change?

Outcome 4: *The status quo of a system gradually changes when it becomes clear it is not that profitable anymore.*

The status quo changes gradually; however, this happens very slowly and only when it becomes clear that the current situation is not interesting anymore. This process will be fastened when the budget is so small (without correction inflation) and that rationality will win from political considerations. There are actors (e.g. environmental organisations) that want to fasten the dismantling, but if this is desirable depends on your political choices.

Outcome 4 is in line with the results of the analysis. Dismantling of the status quo was scored very low in section 3.1 and the ResAT wheels, because relevant goals or instruments were (hardly) recognised.

Outcome 5: *The younger generation of farmers help to introduce new ideas and can contribute to the resilience of the system.*

More and more (Dutch) farmers have followed higher education; and are less isolated from the 'world' than in the past. Perhaps it is beneficial that a lot of young farmers cannot directly takeover the farm, because now they can see more of the world or study; thus, gaining new ideas.

It was also mentioned that 'greying' is not only a problem in the agricultural sector, but it is a broader problem that is occurring in the whole of society. 'Greying of the agricultural sector' is more of frame. Generational renewal is a pet area of policies and politics; everyone thinks that it is important. However, it is not always handled in the right way.

Difficulties regarding generational renewal are that a lot of the of new farmers come from the agricultural sector, rarely from outside the sector. In addition, young farmers are vulnerable the first 15 years after they take over a farm due to high investments, loans etc.

Outcome 6: *The CAP introduces many instruments for 'learning', however, learning takes almost only place at a sectoral level.*

The stakeholders were in the beginning mostly of opinion that there are a lot of instruments in the CAP that could enhance learning. They mentioned knowledge sharing instruments, networking instruments, training sessions events.

However, the stakeholders began to realise that the learning was very sectoral. Gaining knowledge from other sectors (ICT, marketing, transportation, logistics etc.) did hardly take place. The CAP, for example, facilitates meetings for potato farmers that talk with each other, instead of

that experts from different sectors exchange ideas; looking beyond personal/sectoral borders. There were perhaps some small sign that it this was changing a bit.

This outcome shows similarities with the results presented in section 3. During the analysis, it became clear that there are indeed instruments within the CAP that aim to enhance learning. However, these instruments could almost only be regarded as social learning, while in-depth learning goals or instruments were hardly or even not present.

The CAP, however, is traditional / strict in who should receive Direct Payments – the CAP is then not that welcoming for new comers with new ideas or production strategies. But it was also possible that these new comers decided themselves not to ‘join the CAP’. You may question if it would be desirable for their resilience to become part of the CAP system.

Innovations

It was typical for the Veenkoloniën that there are a lot of innovations happening in the area, however, these innovations were not able take off. The innovations were not able to drive out the traditional crops. The reason being that the traditional farming business already have a decent income and are not waiting to start something new, especially if the region does not provide the right infrastructure etc. You cannot impose innovation on a region; innovation needs to come from the people themselves.

5 Conclusion: overall analysis of strengths and weaknesses

Policies are able to influence the robustness, adaptability and transformability of farming systems; and thus the overall resilience of the system. However, it is still insufficiently researched how to assess if a policy is even capable of enhancing the resilience of a system. The aim of this research was, therefore, to develop an analytical framework and use it to assess to what extent policies affect the different types of resilience (robustness, adaptability and transformability) of the intensive arable farming system of the Veenkoloniën and Oldambt.

Different policy documents – European, national and regional – were analysed by using the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT). Policy goals and instruments were identified and scored on how much they enhance or constrain the robustness, adaptability or transformability of the farming system. These results were further validated through a stakeholder check with five participants. Finally, the scores were visually represented in two ResAT wheels (policy goals and policy instruments) by using colours based on a traffic light system. The results showed that there is an unbalance between the extent policies enhance the three types of resilience of the intensive arable farming system in the Veenkoloniën and Oldambt.

The policy goals and instruments are very focused on enhancing the robustness of the farming system. The direct payments play an essential part in enhancing the robustness. Despite some changes implemented to the direct payments by the Reform of 2013/14, the direct payment scheme is still the major instrument in the CAP. It has been able to develop in a major buffer resource by stabilising the income of farmers and is implemented with the desire to protect the status quo of the farming systems. Moreover, the current CAP is also clearly focused on making sure that the farming system is able to quickly return to its initial state after a shock. Different goals and (financial) instruments are mentioned that need to make sure that shocks do not escalate and prevent the collapse of the current system, but also to reduce the negative consequences for farmers when the system is confronted with a shock. Currently, the CAP is focused on enhancing the robustness of the farming system on the short run.

The other two resilience capacities are, however, to a lesser extent enhanced by the policy goals and instruments of the CAP and the implementation in the Netherlands. The findings show that adaptability is for the most part only slightly enhanced and that transformability is insufficiently addressed in the policy goals and instruments. There are, thus, elements within the CAP that introduce possibilities for farmers and the farming system to slightly adapt their activities to changing circumstances (flexibility, variety, social learning), however, the CAP does hardly provide possibilities for farmers and the farming system to fundamentally change their operational logic on the long term in case of internal and external pressures that challenge the current system. For

instance, the CAP did introduce goals and instruments to enhance learning within the farming system, however, it was very questionable if learning goals and instruments would lead to intensive reconsiderations of the underlying thoughts of the farming system and would enhance knowledge exchange between sectors. Only instruments that enhance the promotion of niche innovations were slightly present in the CAP. This shows that there are possibilities to introduce transformability enhancing instruments in the policy.

The on-going challenge for actors within the farming system is thus to find a proper balance between robustness, adaptability and transformability. The strong focus of the CAP on robustness shows that it is necessary to address resilience in the CAP in a more extensive way; as overall resilience is also dependent on the capacity to adapt and transform.

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Annex

i. Analysis of the policy documents

Codes (24)

- A. *Robust_short term_goals*
 - B. *Robust_short term_instruments*
 - C. *Robust_protect_status_quo_goals*
 - D. *Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments*
 - E. *Robust_buffer_resources_goals*
 - F. *Robust_buffer_resources_instruments*
 - G. *Robust_other_risk_management_goals*
 - H. *Robust_other_risk_management_instruments*
 - I. *Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals*
 - J. *Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments*
 - K. *Adapt_Flexibility_goals*
 - L. *Adapt_Flexibility_instruments*
 - M. *Adapt_variety_tailored_goals*
 - N. *Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments*
 - O. *Adapt_social_learning_goals*
 - P. *Adapt_social_learning_instruments*
 - Q. *Transform_long-term_goals*
 - R. *Transform_long-term_instruments*
 - S. *Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals*
 - T. *Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments*
 - U. *Transform_In-depth_learning_goals*
 - V. *Transform_In-depth_learning_instruments*
 - W. *Transform_niche_innovations_goals*
 - X. *Transform_niche_innovations_instruments*
-

Code Co-occurrence table - The amount of quotations per score categorised per resilience type (goals and instruments)

GOALS							
	A. Robustness_0	B. Robustness_1	C. Robustness_2	D. Robustness_3	E. Robustness_4	F. Robustness_5	OVERALL
A. Robust_short term_goals	0	0	0	0	2	0	4
C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals	2	2	16	26	41	20	4
E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals	1	2	7	6	11	12	4
G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals	0	0	4	3	2	4	5
	G. Adaptability_0	H. Adaptability_1	I. Adaptability_2	J. Adaptability_3	K. Adaptability_4	L. Adaptability_5	OVERALL
I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals	1	0	1	1	7	5	4
K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals	3	2	17	15	16	0	3
M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals	2	1	28	25	27	4	3
O. Adapt_social_learning_goals	1	0	7	7	13	1	4
	M. Transformability_0	N. Transformability_1	O. Transformability_2	P. Transformability_3	Q. Transformability_4	R. Transformability_5	OVERALL
Q. Transform_long-term_goals	0	0	6	2	5	0	2
S. Transform_dismantle_status_quo_incentives_goals	0	0	2	2	3	0	2
U. Transform_in-depth_learning_goals	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals	0	0	0	1	3	0	1
INSTRUMENTS							
	A. Robustness_0	B. Robustness_1	C. Robustness_2	D. Robustness_3	E. Robustness_4	F. Robustness_5	OVERALL
B. Robust_short term_instruments	0	0	1	4	0	2	3
D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments	1	6	16	12	14	14	3
F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments	4	4	4	13	35	44	5
H. Robust_other_risk_management_instruments	0	0	6	2	2	15	5
	G. Adaptability_0	H. Adaptability_1	I. Adaptability_2	J. Adaptability_3	K. Adaptability_4	L. Adaptability_5	OVERALL
J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments	0	0	3	3	7	1	3
L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments	1	0	22	19	8	2	3
N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments	2	0	33	12	7	1	3
P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments	1	0	7	19	18	1	3
	M. Transformability_0	N. Transformability_1	O. Transformability_2	P. Transformability_3	Q. Transformability_4	R. Transformability_5	OVERALL
R. Transform_long-term_instruments	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T. Transform_dismantle_status_quo_incentives_instrument	2	0	1	2	1	0	1
V. Transform_in-depth_learning_instruments	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments	1	0	5	3	2	2	3

Relevant texts for policy goals & instruments (The Netherlands)

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Robust_short term _goals

2 Quotations:

5:7 4. Boeren moeten jaarlijks kunnen kiezen hoe ze de EFA willen invullen..... (2:1159 [2:1232]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

4. Boeren moeten jaarlijks kunnen kiezen hoe ze de EFA willen invullen.

Comment: by buite049

Farmers able to change their decisions every year

2 Codes:

A. Robust_short term _goals / E. Robustness_4

15:49 By August 1 of each year, with effect from the following year, Member..... (53:2904 [53:3072]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

By August 1 of each year, with effect from the following year, Member States may revise the percentage of the national ceiling devoted to the payment for young farmers.

Comment: by buite049

Each year the national ceiling devoted to the payment for young farmers may be revised. The payment scheme can thus be changed every year

2 Codes:

A. Robust_short term _goals / E. Robustness_4

Robust_short term _instruments

7 Quotations:

6:66 M 6.2 business start up aid for nonagricultural activities in rural a..... (18:1548 [18:1621]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.2 business start up aid for nonagricultural activities in rural areas

Comment: by buite049

*Start up aid is focused on the beginning of setting up the non-agricultural activities = short term instrument.
But the activities are introduced to create variety on the farms = variety*

4 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / D. Robustness_3 / J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:67 M 6.3 business start up aid for the development of small farms (18:1712 [18:1775]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.3 business start up aid for the development of small farms

Comment: by buite049

Start up aid is focused on the beginning of setting up a farming business = short term instrument

2 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / D. Robustness_3

6:87 M6.1 business start up aid for young farmers (18:1363 [18:1406]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M6.1 business start up aid for young farmers

Comment: by buite049

Start up aid is focused on the beginning of setting up a farming business = short term instrument

2 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / D. Robustness_3

9:30 Farmers may apply for direct payments every year. In order to be eligi..... (5:293 [5:436]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Farmers may apply for direct payments every year. In order to be eligible, all of the following conditions need to be complied with each year:

Comment: by buite049

*famers may apply for direct payments each year. Direct payments are payment cycles of one year --short term instrument.
very enabling robustness short-term*

2 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:32 Farmers have to apply for aid every year in order to receive direct pa..... (5:2012 [5:2137]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Farmers have to apply for aid every year in order to receive direct payments, declaring every parcel of their farm holding.

Comment: by buite049

*each year farmers have to apply for direct payments --> Direct payments are payment cycles of one year --short term instrument.
very enabling robustness short-term*

2 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:29 they may review their decision each year, making any changes known to..... (49:3432 [49:3566]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

they may review their decision each year, making any changes known to the Commission by 1 August preceding the year of application.

Comment: by buite049

*Short term as there is no long term vision for this payment. Decision can be changed yearly.
The yearly revision of the decision may also indicate a form of flexibility for the member states. They can change their decision based on if it reduces the risk of unspent funds.*

2 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / D. Robustness_3

15:116 The percentage share of transferred funds may vary from year to year..... (46:1265 [46:1571]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The percentage share of transferred funds may vary from year to year. Member States may revise their decisions by 1 August 2017, with effect from calendar year 2018 in the case of transfers from Pillar I to Pillar II, and with effect in 2019 and 2020 in the case of transfers from Pillar II to Pillar I.

Comment: by buite049

*Slightly enabling flexibility as it is possible to revise the transfer of funding from one pillar to the other pillar.
Also a short term instrument as it means that the payment cycle has a period of only one year and can partially be changed the next year.*

4 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

108 Quotations:

2:1 The reform therefore focused on the operational objectives of delive..... (2:3351 [2:3587]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The reform therefore focused on the operational objectives of delivering more effective policy instruments, designed to improve the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and its sustainability over the long term (Chart 1).

Comment: by buite049

*The goal is to make sure that the agricultural sector is able to keep existing - sustainability in this sentence does not reference to the environment, but about the continuation of the sector itself
This is the overall objective of the reform --> very enabling*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

2:2 In short, EU agriculture needs to attain higher levels of production..... (3:270 [3:460]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

In short, EU agriculture needs to attain higher levels of production of safe and quality food, while preserving the natural resources that agricultural productivity depends upon.

Comment: by buite049

goal of keeping the current system and making sure it can be maintained

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

2:9 Farmers should be rewarded for the services they deliver to the wide..... (5:407 [5:595]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Farmers should be rewarded for the services they deliver to the wider public, such as landscapes, farmland biodiversity, climate stability even though they have no market value.

Comment: by buite049

This is to legitimise the provision of the direct payments for greening (buffer resources). It is however based on other factors than food production (variety..)

It is thus a subsidy for the existing system to introduce some greening, no major changes. But because it is focused on greening (public goods services) the score for enabling protection of status quo is lowered to score 3

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

2:14 The objective of past reforms to enhance the market orientation of E..... (5:2373 [5:2594]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The objective of past reforms to enhance the market orientation of EU agriculture is continued by adapting the policy instruments to further encourage farmers to base their production decisions on market signals.

Comment: by buite049

Constrains the protection of the status quo as market signals will get a higher influence in the farming system and markets may introduce more economic fluctuations.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

2:33 support for ANCs (7:2427 [7:2442]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

support for ANCs

Comment: by buite049

protection of areas facing natural constraints. This measure want to support farms in difficult areas to make sure that they can continue to operate. via financial support

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

2:37 to provide more targeted support to small and medium-sized farms. (7:3014 [7:3081]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

to provide more targeted support to small and medium-sized farms.

Comment: by buite049

*Constraints the protecting of large farms;
However the goal is to make sure that small and medium farm are able to keep existing and maintaint their desired levels of outputs.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

2:39 The reduction in disparities of the level of direct payments between..... (8:987 [8:1194]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The reduction in disparities of the level of direct payments between Member States, known as external convergence, will reinforce the credibility and legitimacy of the support system at EU level.

Comment: by buite049

The reason for the internal convergence is to make the system more credible and legitimate - thus to make sure that the direct payments can stay in place for the farmers. Making the system more robust --> protection the situation as it is. But it is also a bit constraining the protection of the status quo as the goal is to solve disparities of direct payments between countries and farmers; thus to not prioritising the current situation -> changing it. However the system of direct payments keeps existing --> no real transformation: dismantling the status quo. It is thus enabling the protection status quo, but fairly

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

2:46 The key characteristics of the architecture of the EU Rural development..... (9:207 [9:322]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The key characteristics of the architecture of the EU Rural development policy remain untouched by the reform.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

3:3 Rendement: In 2020 is de gemiddelde opbrengst van de hoofdgewassen a..... (6:444 [6:653]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Rendement: In 2020 is de gemiddelde opbrengst van de hoofdgewassen aanzienlijk gestegen. Hierbij is een 15-15-10 doelstelling richtinggevend: 15 ton zetmeel, 15 ton suiker en 10 ton graan per hectare.

Comment: by buite049

increasing production / desired level of outcomes without really changing the production strategy

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

**3:5 De industrie keert aan de telers een concurrerende prijs voor zetmee..... (6:846 [6:1014])
- D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien**

De industrie keert aan de telers een concurrerende prijs voor zetmeelaardappelen en suikerbieten uit, zodat deze teelten een solide basis vormen voor het gebied.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to provide the farmers with enough income through their products. These products that are historically produced here will continue to form a solid base for the region.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

**3:12 Om dit verschil te compenseren is het van cruciaal belang dat opbr..... (8:275 [8:473]) - D
3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien**

Om dit verschil te compenseren is het van cruciaal belang dat opbrengsten per hectare worden verhoogd en dat er tegelijkertijd hogere prijzen worden gerealiseerd voor de geteelde producten.

Comment: by buite049

To deal with the lost of income (buffer resources) the strategy will be to increase the production and to realise higher prices for the products. This goal is mainly focused on the same production and to increase it. This needs to protect the status quo in this area.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

3:13 Verder moeten akkerbouwers 5 procent van hun areaal inzetten voor de..... (8:475 [8:639]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Verder moeten akkerbouwers 5 procent van hun areaal inzetten voor de vergroeningseisen van het GLB. Dit betekent ook een afname van het totale productieareaal.

Comment: by buite049

the production is challenged by the inclusion of greening measures --> 5% of the land needs to be used for greening, meaning that Ha is handed in and not being used for production --> less income --> constraints the status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

3:23 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (11:43:320-11:203:396) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

Stijging opbrengst
/ hoofd gewassen 15-15-10doel
= zetmeel 15 ton/ha
= suiker 15 ton/ha
= graan 10 ton/ha

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

3:50 Ambitie Dit project geeft concreet invulling aan het optimaliseren..... (18:5 [18:180]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Ambitie Dit project geeft concreet invulling aan het optimaliseren van het productieproces op het boerenbedrijf. Doel is om schoner en efficiënter te kunnen produceren.

Comment: by buite049

The ambition is to optimise the current production processes within the regional farming companies. The goal is make it more 'clean and efficient. However the production process does not get drastically altered. The aim is to make sure the current production processes are able to keep desired levels of output despite some perturbations.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

3:72 De introductie van uien en de areaalgroei van cichorei laat zien dat..... (25:14 [25:533]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

De introductie van uien en de areaalgroei van cichorei laat zien dat er mogelijkheden zijn voor nieuwe gewassen in de Veenkoloniën. De teelt van eiwithoudende gewassen op regionale schaal biedt kansen. In enkele projecten wordt gewerkt aan de verbetering van de teelt van soja en lupine. Door opbrengstverbetering worden deze gewassen in bouwplanverband economisch interessant. Door een regionale afzetketen te vormen (bijv. in samenwerking met Agrifirm) wordt een gesloten kringloopgedachte bevorderd.

Comment: by buite049

Introducing new crops (protein rich crops) is seen as a chance to increase yields and income. It is a goal that does not prioritise the current crops - constrains the protection of the status quo.

*But the goal is aimed at changing the production strategy without really changing the operational logic of the farms.
It can bring heterogeneity in the area*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:74 Ambitie Versnelde ontwikkeling van (zetmeel) aardappelrassen met hog..... (19:5 [19:1247]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Ambitie Versnelde ontwikkeling van (zetmeel) aardappelrassen met hoge zetmeel- en eiwitopbrengsten. Averis Seeds (100 procent dochter van AVEBE) en HZPC richten zich op de ontwikkeling van duurzame rassen die hoge veldopbrengst combineren met ziekteresistenties. Duurzaamheid op het veld wordt in belangrijke mate bepaald door opbrengst.

Meeropbrengst bij dezelfde of minder inputs, levert relatief snel een verbetering in milieuprestaties op. Er is een jaarlijkse geleidelijke stijging in veldopbrengst, maar er is zeker een versnelling nodig. Deze versnelling zal naast de verbetering van de landbouwpraktijk bereikt moeten worden door nieuwe aardappelrassen. De moderne DNA-technologie maakt dit mogelijk. Het is de bedoeling versneld tot een doorbraak met de zogenaamde hybride veredeling te komen. Naast opbrengstverbetering die het resultaat is van een complexe samenwerking van vele eigenschappen, lijkt het op kortere termijn mogelijk dat vooral ziekteresistentie versneld ingebracht kan worden in nieuwe aardappelrassen. Het gebruik van gewasbeschermingsmiddelen tegen de aardappelziekte (Phytophthora) kan met een goede resistentiestrategie met circa 80 procent worden teruggedrongen

Comment: by buite049

The main goal is to come to a new breed of potatoes that is more resistance against diseases (innovation), but also has as goal to improve the production rate / the yield per potato. The main goal is thus to improve the level of output and be better able to cope with disturbances like diseases --> robustness protecting the status quo - the potato farming.

They do mention that the new potatoes or increased yield quicker production can help with other relevant goals (increasing the sustainability of the farm). But the main goal is to increase the production and yield for the farmers in the current production system

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

3:95 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën (10:136:402-10:319:426) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Content

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

4:4 Met deze invulling stimuleert het kabinet samen met de provincies jong..... (2:140 [2:281]) - D 4: (Dijkma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Met deze invulling stimuleert het kabinet samen met de provincies jonge gemotiveerde boeren om hun bedrijf voor de toekomst gezond te houden

Comment: by buite049

The goal is focused on the long term - the future; however it seems that it is more about creating robustness - to make sure that the farms are kept healthy to maintain desired levels of outputs

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

6:1 For most Member States/regions in this group the implementation of co..... (46:651 [46:898]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

For most Member States/regions in this group the implementation of coupled support payments does not fit in their national political orientation, according to which government intervention in markets should be as much as possible non-distortive.

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands do not have coupled support as this is seen as government intervention in markets --> constraints the protection of the status quo.

1 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

6:6 The priorities set under its agricultural policy are to have a competitive..... (51:1078 [51:1189]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

The priorities set under its agricultural policy are to have a competitive and innovative agricultural sector

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

6:8 The Netherlands mainly put its efforts under the CAP general objective..... (51:925 [51:1076]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

The Netherlands mainly put its efforts under the CAP general objectives of 'viable food production' and 'sustainable management of natural resources'.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

6:25 Those Member States that were previously operating the Single Area P..... (14:2219 [14:2342]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Those Member States that were previously operating the Single Area Payment Scheme (SAPS) can continue to do so until 2020.

Comment: by buite049

Can keep on using this system of direct payments

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

6:41 facilitating generational renewal in the agricultural sector; (16:4019 [16:4079]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

facilitating generational renewal in the agricultural sector;

Comment: by buite049

It is a long term goal. However it is not focused on transformation, but on making sure the system is able to continue

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

6:42 facilitating restructuring of farms facing major structural problems,..... (16:3789 [16:4013]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

facilitating restructuring of farms facing major structural problems, notably farms with a low degree of market participation, market-oriented farms in particular sectors and farms in need of agricultural diversification;

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to support farms that are not fully functional anymore in the current system. These farms have a special treatment instead of leaving them to the market

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

6:44 improving water management; (17:681 [17:708]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

improving water management;

Comment: by buite049

improving the water management can be considered as adapting the current way of dealing with water - adaptability

But it is also about making sure that it can still supply water for the agricultural tasks and to continue farming - robustness

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:45 improving soil management; (17:713 [17:739]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

improving soil management;

Comment: by buite049

Improving the soilmanagement can be considered as adapting the current way of dealing with water - adaptability

But it is also about making sure that it can still supply water for the agricultural tasks and to continue farming - robustness

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:46 increasing efficiency in water use by agriculture; (17:937 [17:986]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

increasing efficiency in water use by agriculture;

Comment: by buite049

increasing the efficiency is a goal that is beneficial for the environment. It is adapting your your own system to respond to changing external drivers. But it is also about continuing the current system in such a way that you can still maintain desired levels of outputs. --> adaptability (2) --> robustness (3)

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:47 increasing efficiency in energy use in agriculture and food processing..... (17:992 [17:1062]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

increasing efficiency in energy use in agriculture and food processing;

Comment: by buite049

increasing the efficiency is a goal that is beneficial for the environment. It is adapting your your own system to respond to changing external drivers. But it is also about continuing the current system in such a way that you can still maintain desired levels of outputs. --> adaptability (2) --> robustness (3)

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:63 M7.2 Support for investments in the creation, improvement or expansi..... (18:2657 [18:2838]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.2 Support for investments in the creation, improvement or expansion of all types of small scale infrastructure, including investments in renewable energy and energy saving

Comment: by buite049

*The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.
Investments in small infrastructure are meant to maintain the area and to allow the farms to continue their practices (protection of status quo).
However investments in renewable energy and energy saving are more adaptation - investing in other functions. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:70 Support for investments in the settingup, improvement or expansion of..... (19:130 [19:314]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Support for investments in the settingup, improvement or expansion of local basic services for the rural population including leisure and culture, and the related infrastructure

Comment: by buite049

It is an instrument that is focused on a different theme than the regular agricultural activities --> enabling variety instrument

But the goal is to improve the rural area for the inhabitants. To make sure that the areas are livable --> to make sure they can continue on existing and that farmers can continue on with their jobs --> protection of status quo - slightly enabling

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:72 M7.6 Support for studies/investments associated with the maintenanc..... (19:459 [19:745]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.6 Support for studies/investments associated with the maintenance, restoration and upgrading of the cultural and natural heritage of villages, rural landscapes and high nature value sites including related socioeconomic aspects, as well as environmental awareness actions

Comment: by buite049

the aim of this support is to make sure the rural area can continue on existing and that the landscape do not get lost.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

7:6 Ik zoek daarom naar een EFA-invulling die niet leidt tot onnodig prod..... (3:1992 [3:2239]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Ik zoek daarom naar een EFA-invulling die niet leidt tot onnodig productieverlies, en tegelijkertijd wil ik niet dat de EFA volledig kan worden ingevuld met reeds bestaande meer of minder 'groene' elementen - het zogenaamde 'green washing' .

Comment: by buite049

*Both enabling and constraining the protection of the status quo
Therefore Score 3 (neutral) Fairly enabling / fairly constraining*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

7:14 Dubbele betaling Wat in de eerste pijler meetelt voor de verplichte v..... (5:1912 [5:2331]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Dubbele betaling Wat in de eerste pijler meetelt voor de verplichte vergroening, en daarmee tot de 'baseline' behoort, bijvoorbeeld als ecologische aandachtsgebied (EFA),

mag vanwege het verbod op dubbele betaling in de tweede pijler niet nog eens vergoed worden via Agrarisch Natuurbeheer (ANB).

De ANB-vergoedingen moeten daarom gekort worden voor zo ver er fysieke en inhoudelijke overlap is tussen ANB en EFA.

Comment: by buite049

This is to make sure that the dubble payments get restricted --> to make the current system of direct payments more robust

To ensure that money is well spent for the right reason slightly enables the robustness (score 2)

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / I. Adaptability_2

7:15 Wanneer het aandeel blijvend grasland meer dan 5% daalt ten opzichte..... (7:2227 [7:2557]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Wanneer het aandeel blijvend grasland meer dan 5% daalt ten opzichte van 2012, ben ik verplicht om een individuele herinzaaiplicht op te leggen aan aanvragers die blijvend grasland hebben omgezet. De kans hierop is aanwezig, aangezien RVO.nl heeft geconstateerd dat het areaal blijvend grasland de afgelopen jaren is gedaald.

Comment: by buite049

It is a measure that increases the variety on the farms - less homogeneity. However, the measure of permanent grassland was not yet fully implemented and will only be done when the total amount of permanent grassland is lower than 5%. This meant that the situation was kept as it was. But if the measure will be used it will constrain the protection of the status quo.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:16 Uitgangspunt bij de GLB-hervorming is dat betalingen op basis van hist..... (8:65 [8:329]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Uitgangspunt bij de GLB-hervorming is dat betalingen op basis van historische referenties maatschappelijk niet langer verdedigbaar zijn. Daarom houd ik vast aan de convergentie naar een gelijke hectarepremie in 2019 en blijvende ontkoppeling (zie TK 28625-168).

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the protection of the status quo, however is is not a drastic change that it transforms the system. It changes how direct payments (buffer resources) are grantend and changes the situation for certain sector. It therefore constraints the buffer resources, however the system is only adapted not removed. I would therefore not argue that it is transforming the system by dismantling the status quo.

Robustness 4 - slightly constraining - Buffer resources

Robustness 3 - fairly constraining - protection status quo - as the argument is that the old situation is not favourable.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

7:20 Tegelijkertijd heeft de sector een aantal belangrijke maatschappelijke..... (8:2205 [8:2512]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Tegelijkertijd heeft de sector een aantal belangrijke maatschappelijke opgaven.

Hoewel de Nederlandse intensieve kalverhouderij belangrijke stappen heeft gezet op terreinen als dierenwelzijn, diergezondheid, vermindering antibioticagebruik en kwaliteitscontrole, acht ik verdere verbetering noodzakelijk.

Comment: by buite049

Goal is to improve the animal welfare, animal health, lessen the use of antibiotics and more quality checks in the meat sector. --> to improve other factors that come with producing meat. However it is an adjustment of the system to continue the current trajectory of producing meat.

Is about livestock farming. Thus not relevant for the Dutch case study of crop farming

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:21 Omdat ik zie dat de afname van de directe betalingen de vereiste innov..... (8:2696 [9:254]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Omdat ik zie dat de afname van de directe betalingen de vereiste innovatie onder druk zet, wil ik de verduurzaming van de sector ondersteunen door het bevorderen en stimuleren van systeeminnovaties in de kalfsvleesketen, niet alleen gericht op verbetering en doorontwikkeling van de huidige houderijsystemen, Directoraat-generaal Agro Directie Europees Landbouwbeleid en Voedselzekerheid DGA-ELV / 14051593 Pagina 8 van 19

maar ook op een transitie naar nieuwe houderijconcepten. Ik ben dan ook bereid om de sector via het GLB te steunen met een regeling gericht op de verduurzamingsopgaven van de sector, in lijn met de aangehouden motie DikFaber en Geurts (TK 28625-182).

Comment: by buite049

The sector needs to be supported because the decline in direct payments would lead to a decrease in innovations.

The support is for both improving the current production strategy as to create new ones.

The support is thus focused on the making sure the sector can keep on going despite small perturbations of losing direct payments. It is provided with support because the (perverse) buffer resource is decreasing

Score 4 protecting status quo not 5 - because the support is focused on innovations for making it more sustainable.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

7:29 in combinatie met ondersteuning van sectoren die daarbij het sterkst..... (12:2013 [12:2267]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

in combinatie met ondersteuning van sectoren die daarbij het sterkst achteruitgaan, zal de Nederlandse agrosector de transitie naar de gelijke hectarepremie in de concurrentie met de ons omringende landen naar mijn overtuiging succesvol kunnen maken.

Comment: by buite049

This must ensure that the Dutch agricultural sector (mostly the sectors that will be hit hard by the changes) are able to maintain their levels of output and are still able to compete with other countries. The reform is actually seen a shock (sudden change in direct payments received) which the sector tries to overcome and the Dutch government want to support (robustness)

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

7:30 Ik heb ervoor gekozen om dergelijke gebieden niet met 'top-ups' te st..... (12:2847 [13:36]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Ik heb ervoor gekozen om dergelijke gebieden niet met 'top-ups' te steunen, omdat daarbij geen sprake is van betalingen gericht Directoraat-generaal Agro Directie Europees Landbouwbeleid en Voedselzekerheid DGA-ELV / 14051593 Pagina 12 van 19 op specifieke doelen of prestaties.

Comment: by buite049

*Decision that constraints more use of buffer resources for specific regions.
It constraints extra subsidies for specific regions and their production systems. No exceptions*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

8:4 In order to move towards a fairer distribution of support, the CAP sys..... (1:1381 [1:1741]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to move towards a fairer distribution of support, the CAP system for Direct Payments will move away from one where allocations per Member State - and per farmer within the Member State - are based on historical references. This will mean a clear and genuine convergence of payments not only between Member States, but also within Member States

Comment: by buite049

*Constraints the protection of the status quo - the old way of direct payments based on historical references. However, the system is still based on direct payements
Constraints the protection of the status quo. Als the systems needs to be changed. But the goal of this change is to gain legitimacy for the Direct Payments to keep the system going.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

8:15 In order to maintain current levels of production in sectors or regi..... (3:1287 [3:1500]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to maintain current levels of production in sectors or regions where specific types of farming or sectors undergo difficulties and are important for economic and/or social and/or environmental reasons,

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

8:54 Those Member States that currently maintain allocations based on his..... (2:716 [2:877]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Those Member States that currently maintain allocations based on historical references must move towards more similar levels of the basic payment per hectare.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints protecting the status quo as the old historical references will be removed. --> fairly constraining 3 However, the measure is still focussed on a basic payment and the goal is to provide the farmers with a basic income as a buffer --> robust buffer resource goals --> enables robust buffer resource 4

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:2 a stable, varied and safe food supply for citizens. (1:426 [1:479]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

a stable, varied and safe food supply for citizens.

Comment: by buite049

It focuses on the interest of the agricultural sector. But also: the food supply needs to be "stable" --> withstanding shocks --> the situation as it is now needs to be continued. Focus on the traditional task of agriculture

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

9:9 The overall effect of decoupling has been to move the agricultural s..... (2:3027 [2:3210]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

The overall effect of decoupling has been to move the agricultural sector more towards the free market and to give farmers greater freedom to produce according to market demand,

Comment: by buite049

The effect (goal) of the decoupling was to introduce more market effects into the agricultural sector. The market effects and price oscillations are risks / shocks which farmers need to deal with --> very constraining robustness

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

9:11 But farming is a risky – and often costly – business. Weather conditio..... (3:120 [3:388]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

But farming is a risky – and often costly – business. Weather conditions are unpredictable: crops can be ruined and farm output and income badly affected. This is obviously bad for farmers but also for consumers, as food supply chains can be adversely impacted.

Comment: by buite049

Not really a goal, but more the reason why the CAP is implemented. However, one could argue that the CAP had as goal to reduce these problems.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:13 And although farmers are at the heart of the food supply chain in..... (3:1857 [3:2329]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

And although farmers are at the heart of the food supply chain in terms of supplying the actual food, the fragmented nature of the farming sector puts it in a relatively weaker bargaining position compared to other parts of the supply chain, such as the bigger and better-integrated providers of animal feed and fertiliser or the food processors and retailers. This relative weakness puts farmers at a disadvantage when it comes to bargaining power.

Comment: by buite049

*Not really a goal, but more the reason why the CAP is implemented. However, one could argue that the CAP had as goal to reduce these problems.
the goal is to protect farmers from the heavy influence of other actors in the supply change. To make them more robust / better capable to cope with these actoprs and their power. --> enabling protection of status quo. The farmers has a special position which should be kept and protected from other actors in bargaining rounds etc.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:14 EU farmers are also under pressure from the increasing global trade..... (3:1009 [3:1856]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

EU farmers are also under pressure from the increasing global trade in food products and market liberalisation in many countries, which has increased competition at the same time as creating new opportunities for European farmers.

Globalisation and fluctuations in supply and demand have also made agricultural market prices more volatile in recent years, adding to farmers' concerns. Traditionally, prices for many agricultural commodities were relatively predictable, giving farmers a degree of certainty over their projected incomes and allowing them to invest confidently in their business. Price volatility removes this degree of certainty over incomes and makes farmers less likely to invest. This in turn threatens productivity and efficiency, again with potential knockon effects on the supply of food to consumers.

Comment: by buite049

Not really a goal, but more the reason why the CAP is implemented. However, one could argue that the CAP had as goal to reduce these problems.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:16 By helping to keep farms working, direct payments can contribute to..... (3:3524 [3:3722]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

By helping to keep farms working, direct payments can contribute to maintaining or creating jobs in many other sectors that rely heavily on agriculture, from the food industry to rural tourism.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:29 As part of the 2013 CAP reform, it was agreed that the national budget..... (4:1733 [4:2069]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

As part of the 2013 CAP reform, it was agreed that the national budget allocations should be gradually adjusted to obtain a more balanced and fairer distribution of direct payments. That way, the differences in the average support per hectare between each EU country would be reduced via a process known as 'external convergence'

Comment: by buite049

external convergence constraints the old situation of direct payments between member states. This means that member states that traditionally received more national budget for direct payments (such as the netherlands) will loss some of their budget. --> constraints the protection of status quo --> however there will still be a system of direct payments in place --> fairly constraints the protection of status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

9:31 Active farmers Only farmers with a holding located in the EU and exer..... (5:776 [5:1199]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Active farmers Only farmers with a holding located in the EU and exercising an agricultural activity can receive direct payments.

The requirement of being an 'active' farmer means that individuals and companies such as airports, real estate services and sport grounds who may have agricultural land at their disposal but who have no or only a very marginal agricultural activity cannot receive support from the CAP.

Comment: by buite049

The term active farmer and the criteria were brought into the policy to be better able to direct who will and who will not receive direct payments. It is used to make sure that

farmers will profit from direct payments, while other individuals or companies that are not specifically agricultural active will be excluded. The term active farmer is therefore used to protect the interests of farmers and to better control the expenditures of the Direct Payments. Better control over the flow of money makes it also easier to defence direct payments.

It is a term that should help to keep the direct payments into control and to continu the payment system --> robustness protecting status quo --> enabling

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:45 All entitlements allocated to a farmer have the same value, but diff..... (7:801 [7:1540]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

All entitlements allocated to a farmer have the same value, but differences in the value of entitlements may exist between farmers, if a member state opted for such an approach. In that case, the past level of direct payments to individual farmers was taken into account (or the value of the entitlements they possessed under the previous direct payments regime) in order to avoid too abrupt disruptions in their level of support. However, since one of the objectives of the new system is to move away from these historical references, the member states that take this approach have agreed to progressively reduce the differences in the values of entitlements and bring these values to (or closer to) the average by 2019

Comment: by buite049

protection of the status quo = the disruption of the level of support needs to be done progressively + past level of direct payments were taken into account.

Also a bit constraining the protection of status quo = the direct payments are moving away from historical references.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

9:57 The aim of this type of support is to maintain the level of production..... (9:2363 [9:2568]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

The aim of this type of support is to maintain the level of production in regions or in sectors undergoing difficulties and that are particularly important for economic, social or environmental reasons.

Comment: by buite049

Enables the protection of the status quo --> have not give it a scoe of 5, because it is voluntary. However, it is a clear example of protecting the status quo.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

9:61 Encouraging new entrants to take up farming is vital for the future of..... (9:28 [9:186]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Encouraging new entrants to take up farming is vital for the future of agriculture and rural communities, especially as the EU farming population is ageing.

Comment: by buite049

More robustness than Transformation: The goal is of course focused on the future, however the overall goal is to maintain and continue the farming system for the next generation.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

10:11 Daarbij zal ik mij inzetten om de regeldruk en administratieve lasten..... (3:1161 [3:1345]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Daarbij zal ik mij inzetten om de regeldruk en administratieve lasten terug te dringen, de uitvoeringslast van de overheid te verminderen en het ondernemerschap de ruimte te bieden.

Comment: by buite049

*It depends how you look at it (which political perspective you will use):
You can see it as that the government is displacing her responsibilities and places it with the farming sector; the farming sector is self-responsible for change. But why would you change, if the current situation is fine for your farm and economic situation and there are less consequences or a government that is nudging you in the right way?
On the other hand: reducing meddling of the government and providing entrepreneurial freedom may lead to that farmers dare to take initiatives to change or are able to better react to markets or problems*

4 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / G. Adaptability_0 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:14 Op Europees niveau is vastgelegd dat landbouwbedrijven die gebruik wil..... (4:611 [4:791]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Op Europees niveau is vastgelegd dat landbouwbedrijven die gebruik willen maken van de directe betalingen in het nieuwe GLB verplicht zijn vergroeningsmaatregelen toe te passen.

Comment: by buite049

slightly constraints the protection of the status quo due to the fact that there are more (green) demands before you can receive a direct payment. However the system is still based on direct payments and the greening is a way to try to better legitimise the direct payments.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:15 Voor het grasland buiten de Natura 2000- gebieden streef ik naar een..... (4:2050 [4:2535]) - D 10: (Dijkma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Voor het grasland buiten de Natura 2000- gebieden streef ik naar een nationale monitoring van het areaal blijvend grasland, in beginsel zonder verplichtingen aan individuele agrariërs op te leggen om een onnodige beperking in de bedrijfsvoering en extra uitvoeringslasten te voorkomen.

Mocht het areaal blijvend grasland in Nederland met meer dan 5% dalen ten opzichte van het referentiejaar 2012, dan zal ik conform het Europese kader maatregelen treffen op bedrijfsniveau.

Comment: by buite049

The amount of non natura 2000 grassland wil first be monitored before the decision is taken to introduce a measure that reduces the production of farmers. Thus protection the current farming and production system

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

10:26 Sloten die grenzen aan akkerranden en dergelijke kunnen als aangrenzen..... (5:2655 [5:2869]) - D 10: (Dijkma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Sloten die grenzen aan akkerranden en dergelijke kunnen als aangrenzend landschapselement worden meegeteld in de vergroeningsoppervlakte, omdat ze een extra bijdrage aan biodiversiteit of waterkwaliteit leveren.

Comment: by buite049

Flexibility: as the already existing ditches can also be counted as a green surface. Protection of status quo: The ditches are already there and will be counted as green surfaces. The change that occurs is thus minimal, because the ditches are already present without introducing new green surfaces. The increase in green surface will be only on paper, while the real amount of green surfaces stay the same. This may also mean that farmers feel less obliged to introduce new green surfaces.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:34 Ik ben blij dat in het nieuwe GLB inkomenstoelagen niet langer gebase..... (6:2756 [7:403]) - D 10: (Dijkma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik ben blij dat in het nieuwe GLB inkomenstoelagen niet langer gebaseerd zijn op historische referenties.

Pagina 7 van 16 Directoraat-generaal Agro Directie Europees Landbouwbeleid en Voedselzekerheid DGA-ELV / 13196008 Dit is maatschappelijk niet langer verdedigbaar. Daarnaast komt door de dynamiek in de sector het steeds vaker voor dat vergelijkbare bedrijven ongelijke directe betalingen ontvangen, louter gebaseerd op in het verleden geleverde agrarische productie en ontvangen premies

Comment: by buite049

Constraining robust protect status quo

This statement is very clear in that the minister does not agree with the old system and that it was necessary to change it. --> constraining robust -buffer resources.

But no transformation, because the new system will still be based on direct payment and not really transformed

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

10:39 Ik kies ervoor om ook bedrijven die momenteel hoge betalingen per hect..... (7:1753 [7:2354]) - D 10: (Dijkma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik kies ervoor om ook bedrijven die momenteel hoge betalingen per hectare ontvangen of speciale toeslagrechten hebben te laten toegroeien naar een gelijke hectarepremie in 2019. Een hogere betaling zou ten koste gaan van de overige bedrijven, met name extensieve veehouderij- en akkerbouwbedrijven. Deze zouden dan in 2019 minder dan de gemiddelde hectarepremie ontvangen en er zouden (zeer) aanzienlijke verschillen in de hectarebetalingen in 2019 blijven bestaan. Dit betekent dat de hectarebetalingen voor sectoren als de vleeskalversector en de zetmeelaardappelsector zullen afnemen.

Comment: by buite049

Constrains protection of status quo. The system is not really changed by this change.

However the Dutch government explicitly states that the potato sector (which is present in the Dutch case study) will lose a great amount of direct payments.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

10:41 Ik kies in Nederland voor blijvende ontkoppeling, vanwege het streven..... (7:2841 [7:3055]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik kies in Nederland voor blijvende ontkoppeling, vanwege het streven naar een gelijke hectarebetaling en het afstappen van historische referenties. Ik heb dit tijdens de onderhandelingen ook steeds aangegeven.

Comment: by buite049

explicitly states the minister's intention to get rid of the older system of direct payments -->constraining protection of status quo.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

10:53 Versterken van de innovatie en concurrentiekracht van de landbouw l..... (11:843 [11:1244]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Versterken van de innovatie en concurrentiekracht van de landbouw Innovatie van de landbouw is samen met de verduurzaming de belangrijkste opgave voor de agrarische sector om een krachtige concurrentiepositie te behouden. Ik wil innovatie van de landbouw en het versterken van de concurrentiepositie daarom stimuleren met een samenhangend pakket van generieke en gebiedsgerichte maatregelen.

Comment: by buite049

The goals is to strongly invest in innovation. However it is then stated that the innovations are used to protect and maintain the current (economical international) position that the Dutch agricultural sector has. It did also not state in what kind of innovations there will be invested (niche?). --> the goals can therefore be more understood as robust protection of status quo instead of transforming niche innovations.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

10:54 Het aantal boeren neemt in Nederland al jaren af. Jonge gemotiveerde a..... (12:2214 [12:2599]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het aantal boeren neemt in Nederland al jaren af. Jonge gemotiveerde agrarische ondernemers hebben ruimte nodig om een bedrijf over te nemen en voor de toekomst gezond te houden. Jonge boeren zijn immers de boeren van de toekomst. Het kabinet

vindt daarom dat jonge boeren ondersteund moeten worden bij het doen van duurzame en innovatieve investeringen in hun boerenbedrijf.

Comment: by buite049

Goal is to invest in the future through provide extra support for young farmers. However, the investment is also about to continue the farming system for the future. Thus to protect the status quo, to make sure that farms are still able to provide the desired levels of output.

It is aimed at the future, but with in mind to overcome the greying of the agricultural sector. It is not about adapting or transforming the system but about keeping the system working --> enabling robustness protecting status quo (4)

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

10:65 Voor een optimale internationale concurrentiepositie voor de Nederland..... (12:128 [12:369]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Voor een optimale internationale concurrentiepositie voor de Nederlandse landbouw is ook een blijvende investering in de landbouwstructuurversterking essentieel. Efficiëntieverhoging is mogelijk door de juiste aanpassingen van percelen.

Comment: by buite049

Investing in the current agriculture structure is seen as essential. And increasing efficiency will then become better possible. This goal aims therefore on the current system --> enabling (4) protection of status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

10:86 In Nederland is 5% van de agrarische ondernemers onder de 35 jaar. Agr..... (6:1562 [6:1997]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

In Nederland is 5% van de agrarische ondernemers onder de 35 jaar. Agrarische ondernemers, en dus ook continuïteit van agrarisch ondernemen, zijn essentieel voor het creëren van voedselzekerheid, maar ook voor het behoud van het mooie Nederlandse landschap. Ik vind het belangrijk om jonge agrariërs te stimuleren vanwege het belang voor de toekomst, de ontwikkeling en de maatschappelijke positie van de agrarische sector.

Comment: by buite049

It is important to stimulate young farmers. This can be seen as a goal for the future (which it is in a sense) however the young farmers are stimulated to continue the current farming system. To make sure the agricultural sector is able to keep on producing food. --> enables the protection of status quo (4)

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

10:90 Dit overwegende wil ik in het nieuwe GLB inzetten op een eerlijke he..... (2:1473 [2:1555]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Dit overwegende wil ik in het nieuwe GLB inzetten op een eerlijke hectarepremie,

Comment: by buite049

However changing the direct payments away from historical references has its effects on the status quo, therefore constraining it slightly --> constraining status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

12:15 Wij willen geen ruimte bieden aan agrarische ondernemers die zich ni..... (2:3397 [2:3514]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen geen ruimte bieden aan agrarische ondernemers die zich niet op een duurzame manier willen ontwikkelen.

Comment: by buite049

*Constrains protecting status quo
It constrains continuation of existing farming and production systems as it aims to make it impossible for unsustainable farms to continue if they do not want to change --> very constraining*

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

12:48 Meer jonge boeren en boerinnen: in de trends van de laatste jaren word..... (11:1291 [11:2138]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Meer jonge boeren en boerinnen: in de trends van de laatste jaren wordt duidelijk dat ook in de agrarische sector vergrijzing van de beroepsbevolking aan de orde is. In Groningen heeft bijna 72% van de oudere boeren geen opvolger. Tegelijk is het voor

jongeren zonder agrarische achtergrond lastig om een bedrijf te beginnen of over te nemen.

Het ontbreken van een opvolger kan ertoe leiden dat ondernemers terughoudend zijn bij het investeren in de duurzaamheid van hun bedrijf. Om de innovatiekracht van de sector te behouden is het van belang om de instroom van jonge ondernemers op peil te houden. Wij willen daarom in samenwerking met anderen, waaronder de agrarische jongerenorganisaties en onderwijsinstellingen, kijken hoe wij daaraan bij kunnen dragen, maar ook wat er nodig is om een familiebedrijf gezond te houden.

Comment: by buite049

*The goal is to make sure that there will be enough young farmers willing and capable to continue the work in the future.
to make sure that the farming system will be able to continue as the farming population is greying and less young people are available as successor (stressor)*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

12:67 Een deel van de inspanningen op het gebied van de landbouw in Groninge..... (14:2331 [14:2528]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Een deel van de inspanningen op het gebied van de landbouw in Groningen zal erop gericht zijn om deze gevolgen te beperken. Wij willen boeren helpen om goed op in te spelen op de veranderingen.

Comment: by buite049

*voorkomen dat boeren te hard geraakt worden = beschermen hoe de situatie nu is (status quo)
To prevent that the farmers will be hit hard by the changes in the direct payments. To protect the current situation. It is a reaction on the loss of large direct payments (shock).
It is aimed at making sure to that they can withstand the shock*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

12:75 Net als voor andere ondernemers in het MKB is ook voor boeren de groei..... (12:1245 [12:1517]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Net als voor andere ondernemers in het MKB is ook voor boeren de groei van hun bedrijf noodzakelijk. Duurzame ontwikkeling van de sector vraagt van ondernemers een keuze voor het creëren van meerwaarde op hun producten; niet primair meer, maar vooral beter produceren.

Comment: by buite049

Growth of farms is necessary. This can be done through creating more value on their products instead of producing more. This is done to make sure that farms can continue to exist --> robustness, but also a bit focused on changing the idea that growth is dependent on producing a lot. --> fairly enabling protection of status quo.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

15:2 External convergence of direct payments: Member States with average di..... (32:3371 [33:789]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

External convergence of direct payments: Member States with average direct payments per hectare above the EU average will see their allocation progressively reduced in order to finance the increase in those Member States with an average direct 11 Data on financial resources allocated to rural development policies are from European Parliament (2013, Table 10, p. 39).

12 Regulation (EU) 1309/2013.

Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014 – 2020 in the EU Member States

_____ 29 payments below 90 % of the EU average; in the latter, the 90% of the EU average is to be reduced by a third within six years. In those Member States with an average direct payment per hectare above the EU average, the reduction of the financial envelope will be proportional to the distance from the EU average. In 2020, in those Member States where the envelope has been reduced, the average direct payment per hectare cannot be lower than the EU average, and in no Member State can it be lower than EUR 196 per hectare in nominal prices (corresponding to about EUR 164 per hectare in 2011 prices).

Comment: by buite049

The idea is that the Direct payments will be more fairly distributed over the EU Member States. = constraining the status quo. This is definitely the case for the Netherlands. However, the direct payments are still there to support the current desired levels of outputs of the farming systems. --> constraining

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

15:9 the 2013 reform brought about a significant – and unprecedented – red..... (42:831 [42:1155]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

the 2013 reform brought about a significant – and unprecedented – redistribution of the financial resources of the CAP, mainly involving a shift in beneficiaries from those countries that had traditionally received a relatively larger share of resources for direct payments to those that had been penalised in the past.

Comment: by buite049

constraining protecting status quo:

a big change in redistribution of financial resources from the countries that traditionally received a relatively large share for resources for direct payments (the status quo) (The Netherlands) to the countries that were penalised in the past.

There is a change in the situation that effects the status quo, but the direct payments are still a big part of the overall CAP.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

15:13 This flexibility, while perhaps the least expected result of the new C..... (46:1719 [46:1846]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

This flexibility, while perhaps the least expected result of the new CAP, shows well the redistributive purpose of the reform.

Comment: by buite049

The goal of the flexibility is to introduce more of a redistribution.

The goal itself is not to enable flexibility, but more on tackling the status quo --> constraining the status quo. --> slightly constraining --> score 4

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:15 One of the stated objectives of the reform was to remove the historical..... (46:2819 [46:3087]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

One of the stated objectives of the reform was to remove the historical rents created by the progressive decoupling of CAP support, and to concentrate aid on persons, natural or legal, for whom agricultural activity is not marginal (the so-called 'active farmers').

Comment: by buite049

the minimum requirements for receiving direct payments makes it better possible for the CAP to ensure that the right people will receive funding. It is a way of making the system of direct payments more robust. This change was necessary to decrease the stress put on direct payments and have a fairer distribution of this funding for farmers --> robustness protecting status quo --> slightly enables robustness.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

15:25 ‘Internal convergence’ provisions are meant to eliminate or reduce by..... (48:2143 [48:2390]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

‘Internal convergence’ provisions are meant to eliminate or reduce by 2019 any differences in the per-hectare basic payment received by farmers in those Member States in which the SPS was used (and only in this component of direct payments 22).

Comment: by buite049

*constraints protecting status quo as internal convergence is used to eliminate or reduce the current difference - to change the status quo.
However, farms still will receive a basic payment as a buffer.*

1 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

15:30 “Old” payment entitlements obtained within the SPS expired on 31 Decem..... (49:3567 [49:3877]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

“Old” payment entitlements obtained within the SPS expired on 31 December 2014.

However, to take into account the steps taken, Member States applying a regionalised or hybrid model of SPS may keep the existing payment entitlements even after 2014, provided that they are reviewed on the basis of new rules.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to continue using the old existing payment entitlements after 2014. --> enables robustness protection of status quo.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:33 The payment entitlements obtained within the SAPS expired on 31 Decemb..... (50:1165 [50:1504]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The payment entitlements obtained within the SAPS expired on 31 December 2014.

However, the CAP 2014-2020 sets an extension of the scheme, in the same way as the Health Check reform extended the SAPS until the end of 2014. Member States applying the SAPS are allowed to continue to apply this scheme until the end of 2020 at the latest.

Comment: by buite049

possibility to continue SAPS after the reform of 2014. --> protection of the status quo enables.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:55 The redistributive payment is a voluntary component of direct payments..... (54:1949 [54:2120]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The redistributive payment is a voluntary component of direct payments. It aims at redistributing financial support within a Member State from large farms to smaller ones.

Comment: by buite049

redistribution of financial support from large farm to smaller farms --> constraints the protecting of the status quo, because financial support is falling away for the large already established farms to the smaller farms.

But also helps maintaining the outputs of smaller farms and help them to keep on existing despite (~unfair~) competition = robustness

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

15:58 Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints ar..... (55:1068 [55:1363]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints are a voluntary component of the direct payments, justified by the goal of guaranteeing the presence of farmers and farming in these areas by providing support that is additional to that foreseen in rural development policies.

Comment: by buite049

The direct payments for areas with natural constraints is just financial support / compensation for the farmers. The goal is to guarantee the presence of farmers and farming in those areas; thus to keep things as they are --> protecting status quo.

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:61 Coupled support may only be granted to those sectors and regions of t..... (55:2778 [55:3128]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Coupled support may only be granted to those sectors and regions of the Member State in which specific types of farming, or specific agricultural sectors, play a particularly important economic, social or environmental role; it may only be granted to create an incentive to maintain current levels of production in the sectors or regions concerned

Comment: by buite049

agricultural exceptionalism for particular products

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

15:62 The payment takes the form of an annual payment per hectare – or per h..... (56:305 [56:607]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The payment takes the form of an annual payment per hectare – or per head, in the case of livestock; because the aim is to maintain the current level of production (i.e. the support provided should not result in increased production), payments are limited to a maximum number of hectares and heads.

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:73 At the same time, none of these countries (with the exception of Germ..... (59:1136 [59:1249]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

At the same time, none of these countries (with the exception of Germany) will apply the redistributive payment

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands will not apply the redistributive payments = protection of the situation as it is now

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

15:75 while all of them commit a limited share to the coupled support, (59:1469 [59:1534]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

while all of them commit a limited share to the coupled support,

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands commit a limited share to the coupled support --> protection of status quo, as coupled support is used to maintain specific agricultural practices in specific areas., however the protection is limited

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

15:86 In some cases (Italy, Netherlands, Bulgaria and Malta), governmental..... (70:1656 [70:1846]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In some cases (Italy, Netherlands, Bulgaria and Malta), governmental organisations at various territorial levels have been excluded from the list of potential recipients of direct payments.

Comment: by buite049

The system is a bit changed to exclude non-agricultural actors to receive direct payments. A recognition of that this financial support was unnecessary and not beneficial for the farming system. It was done to protect the system of direct payments and to make sure that payments reach farmers instead of governmental actors. --> robustness protection of status quo slightly enabling

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

15:89 Another eight countries (Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Austria,..... (73:912 [73:1092]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Another eight countries (Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Austria, Finland, Sweden, Scotland and Wales) have decided to postpone the realisation of a flat-rate payment to 2019 (

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands has opted for a gradual introduction of the flat-rate payments. However from this sentence it becomes not clear that the Netherlands is indeed gradually introducing this system. --> fairly protecting the status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

15:99 The aim of the small farmer scheme is to simplify procedures for farme..... (94:1662 [94:1877]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The aim of the small farmer scheme is to simplify procedures for farmers and national administrations, and to reduce the related administrative costs, supporting the existing agricultural structure of small farms.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:102 the aim of supporting specific sectors and products listed in Article..... (92:1001 [92:1103]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

the aim of supporting specific sectors and products listed in Article 52 of Regulation (EU) 1307/2013

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:1 to improve agricultural productivity, so that consumers have a stabl..... (3:247 [3:346]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

to improve agricultural productivity, so that consumers have a stable supply of affordable food;

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:5 ensuring viable food production that will contribute to feeding the..... (3:485 [3:631]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

ensuring viable food production that will contribute to feeding the world's population, which is expected to rise considerably in the future;

Comment: by buite049

Fairly enabling protection of status quo

- It is a goal that legitimises the support of the agricultural sector. This is done by mentioning that the agriculture is getting increasingly important to feed world population. In some sense it is a noble goal, but on the other hand it is a way of justifying the support --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

17:9 Farmers are the first to realise the need to care for our natural re..... (4:2842 [4:3150]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Farmers are the first to realise the need to care for our natural resources — after all farmers rely upon them for their day-to-day living. To avoid negative side effects of some farming practices, the EU provides incentives to farmers to work in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner.

Comment: by buite049

*The goal is to make sure that the agricultural production has not too much negative effects on the environment. The Cap provides farmers with incentives (financial compensation) for working in an environmental friendly way
However, to work environmental friendly / sustainable als has the goal to make sure that hte farmers can still produce products in the (near) future and that they, for instance, did not damage the soil too much for production.*

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:10 Agriculture is a sector that is supported almost exclusively at the..... (6:288 [6:695]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Agriculture is a sector that is supported almost exclusively at the European level, unlike most other sectors of the economy for which the responsibility lies with national governments. It is important to have a public policy for a sector that is responsible for ensuring our food security and that plays a key role in the use of natural resources and the economic development of rural areas.

Comment: by buite049

agricultural exceptionism

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:11 The main aims of the CAP are to improve agricultural productivity, s..... (6:696 [6:887]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

The main aims of the CAP are to improve agricultural productivity, so that consumers have a stable supply of affordable food, and to ensure that EU farmers can make a reasonable living.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:12 There is one big European market for agricultural products, in which..... (6:1164 [6:1382]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

There is one big European market for agricultural products, in which a common approach towards supporting agriculture ensures fair conditions for farmers competing in the internal European market and globally.

Comment: by buite049

focus on the interest of the agricultural sector. Support is given to the existing production systems to make sure that there are fair conditions for competition.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

17:14 Agriculture is more dependent on the weather and the climate than ma..... (7:27 [7:588]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Agriculture is more dependent on the weather and the climate than many other sectors. Furthermore, in agriculture there is an inevitable time gap between consumer demand and farmers being able to supply: growing more wheat or producing more milk inevitably takes time. Our consumption of food is largely constant compared with other products, so small changes in the amounts produced can have big effects on prices.

These business uncertainties justify the important role that the public sector plays in ensuring income stability for farmers

Comment: by buite049

agricultural exceptionism

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:22 There are about 11 million farms in the European Union and 44 millio..... (8:131 [8:423]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

There are about 11 million farms in the European Union and 44 million people are employed in the entire EU food supply chain. Farmers are the first link in this food production chain. They are thus very important strategic and economic players and the EU cannot afford to lose them.

Comment: by buite049

*making sure that the system can continue working in the future.
Legitimises the support for the farmers (agricultural exceptionism)*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:23 In some parts of Europe, farming is particularly difficult — as in h..... (8:1173 [8:1489]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

In some parts of Europe, farming is particularly difficult — as in hilly, mountainous and/or remote areas. It is important to keep communities alive in these regions.

The CAP provides funds to ensure that rural communities in vulnerable areas remain in good economic health and do not gradually disappear.

Comment: by buite049

to keep these communities alive = making sure that the current situation can continue. It is meant as extra support for these regions to maintain a desired level of outputs --> protecting status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:24 The EU supports these trends by offering protection for over 3 400 p..... (9:722 [9:1053]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

The EU supports these trends by offering protection for over 3 400 products by registering them as 'geographical indications'. These identify a product as originating in the territory of a particular country, region or locality where its quality, reputation or other characteristic is linked to its geographical origin.

Comment: by buite049

Protecting products in interest of farmers and regions

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

17:30 This is why the CAP gives farmers financial assistance to ensure tha..... (10:1206 [10:1823]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

This is why the CAP gives farmers financial assistance to ensure that they continue working the land and to create additional jobs through the renovation of their villages,

landscape preservation or cultural heritage projects and many other tasks directly or indirectly associated with farming and the rural economy.

This helps prevent rural depopulation in the face of few job opportunities and high unemployment. Public services — such as schools and healthcare amenities — are preserved and improved, giving people a good reason to remain in the countryside and bring up their children there.

Comment: by buite049

This is a set of varying goals to protect the country side and to make sure that farmers can have a decent life in these areas. But the overall reason is to make sure that the agricultural areas / sector can continue on working - to make sure that the existing system can continue. --> robustness - protection of status quo -enabling

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

17:31 Helping young farmers get started is a policy ‘must’ if Europe’s r..... (11:122 [11:266]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU’s common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Helping young farmers get started is a policy ‘must’ if Europe’s rural areas are successfully to meet the many challenges that face them.

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

17:37 make more productive use of forests and woodland; (11:1228 [11:1277]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU’s common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

make more productive use of forests and woodland;

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

17:38 produce and market the food specialities of their region; (11:1165 [11:1224]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU’s common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

produce and market the food specialities of their region;

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2

17:39 Farm modernisation has always been, and still is, an important CAP objective (11:2410 [11:2711]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

Farm modernisation has always been, and still is, an important CAP objective. Many EU farmers have benefited from grants to modernise their farm buildings and machinery. Others have made use of grants to improve the quality of their livestock and the conditions under which they are reared.

Comment: by buite049

focus is on (traditional) agricultural interest. modernisation was and still is a key focus of CAP --> continuing this line of thought in new CAP --> protecting the situation as it is and making possible that the system can continue on in the future. --> protecting status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

17:41 About 335 000 farmers can expect to receive investment support to..... (12:275 [12:381]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

About 335 000 farmers can expect to receive investment support to restructure and modernise their farms

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

17:50 Through its overseas development policy, the EU helps developing countries..... (14:211 [14:399]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

Through its overseas development policy, the EU helps developing countries to sell their agricultural products in the EU. It does this by granting preferential access to its market.

Comment: by buite049

*Constraints the protection of the status quo:
It allows other market players to participate in the EU market. Increasing competition for the own EU Farmers.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

17:51 looking after the countryside across the EU and keeping the rural economy..... (3:705 [3:785]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

looking after the countryside across the EU and keeping the rural economy alive

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

17:52 Encouraging young farmers and ensuring continuity from one generatio..... (8:1033 [8:1172]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Encouraging young farmers and ensuring continuity from one generation to the next is a real challenge for rural development in the EU.

1 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals

17:55 At the global level, food production will have to increase to feed a..... (15:262 [15:553]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

At the global level, food production will have to increase to feed a global population that is expected to rise considerably in the future. The EU, through the CAP, plays a significant role in meeting this challenge. This is why it needs to continue investing in its farming sector.

Comment: by buite049

legitimises the current CAP: it is good that we support our agricultural sector in this way as food production is majorily necessary.

It varies the CAP as it is focused on the developing countries and the world instead of the EU itself. But this is also a way of legitimising the CAP

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

18:5 Het creëren van meer toegevoegde waarde per hectare door schaalvergr..... (7:569 [7:705]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Het creëren van meer toegevoegde waarde per hectare door schaalvergroting, efficiëntere technieken, producten met een hogere waarde

Comment: by buite049

robustness protection of status quo --> the challenge is to continue growing in the same way as before.

| *By acknowledging this it enables to continue the way how the system is currently working.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4

18:60 We willen dit thema benaderen vanuit een landbouwkundige invalshoek,..... (12:1206 [12:1368]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

We willen dit thema benaderen vanuit een landbouwkundige invalshoek, met als resultaat businessmodellen die zicht bieden op een gunstige bedrijfsexploitatie.

Comment: by buite049

| *the approach is to look at nature inclusive agriculture from an agricultural perspective (which is ofcourse logical) but with the goal to reach beneficial farm exploitation. It uses the traditional perspective to implement the nature inclusive agriculture --> protecting status quo as it will continue the agricultural discourse.*

2 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3

Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

61 Quotations:

2:34 Member States may also grant limited coupled support to secure th..... (7:3250 [7:3367]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Member States may also grant limited coupled support to secure the future of potentially vulnerable sectors.

Comment: by buite049

| *It is limited but the coupled support enables the protection of the status quo*

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

2:40 This is mirrored by internal convergence within the Member States. P..... (8:1744 [8:2009]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

This is mirrored by internal convergence within the Member States. Payments will no longer be based on uneven historical references of more than a decade ago but rather on a fairer and more converging per hectare payment at national or regional level.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the protection of the status quo as the goal is get rid of using historical references as a basis of the direct payments; and to introduce a new more fairer system However the system of direct payments keeps existing --> no real transformation: dismantling the status quo

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

2:56 The level of direct payments per hectare, which is currently based o..... (8:1195 [8:1461]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The level of direct payments per hectare, which is currently based on historic parameters in many countries, will be progressively adjusted with the introduction of a minimum national average direct payment per hectare across all Member States by 2020.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the protection the status quo as the system of direct payments is changed. But would not argue that it is transforming the system because direct payment as a buffer resource will still be in place only a bit adjusted.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

3:51 Opwaardering wegen voor landbouwverkeer (18:981 [18:1019]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Opwaardering wegen voor landbouwverkeer

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

3:52 Fysieke maatregelen zoals aanleg tijdelijke opslagplaatsen voor landbo..... (18:687 [18:861]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Fysieke maatregelen zoals aanleg tijdelijke opslagplaatsen voor landbouwproducten voor reductie van tarra (vrnl.

grond) bij de verdere verwerking van de geteelde producten

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

3:53 Kavelruil voor een efficiëntere logistiek (18:936 [18:976]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Kavelruil voor een efficiëntere logistiek

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

3:55 Kavelverbetering ter verbetering van de homogeniteit van gronden (18:866 [18:931]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Kavelverbetering ter verbetering van de homogeniteit van gronden

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

3:85 10.500.000 (33:519 [33:529]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

10.500.000

Comment: by buite049

finances for the creation of a new potato breed for higher yields in the current production system

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

3:93 5.000.000 (33:453 [33:462]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

5.000.000

Comment: by buite049

Financial means for optimisation of the farming businesses

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

4:2 Conform de wens van uw Kamer komt er, zoals ik in de GLB-brief heb gem..... (1:1500 [1:1754]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Conform de wens van uw Kamer komt er, zoals ik in de GLB-brief heb gemeld, een landsdekkende jongeboerenregeling gericht op innovatieve investeringen, en wel voor 5,2 miljoen euro per jaar, waarvan de provincies 2,6 miljoen euro gaan cofinancieren.

Comment: by buite049

Investments to continue the current production system by making sure that young farmers can uptake farming.

The investments are however focused on innovations. But this can still mean innovations for the current system instead of changing it.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

4:9 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:62:610-3:474:630) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

Jonge boeren	2,6	2,6	5,2
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2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

4:15 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:61:458-3:474:479) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investerings in landbouwstructuur 	7,9	7,9	15,8
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2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:11 Voluntary Coupled Support up to 0.5%; (51:2855 [51:2891]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Voluntary Coupled Support up to 0.5%;

Comment: by buite049

Small part only, so not that high of an influence on protecting the status quo

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

6:13 minimal degressivity of 5% for payments excess of € 150 000; (51:2789 [51:2850]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

minimal degressivity of 5% for payments excess of € 150 000;

Comment: by buite049

constraints the protection of the status quo, however no real hard measures taken

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

6:21 Member States can also choose to introduce some optional measures – e..... (14:2002 [14:2155]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Member States can also choose to introduce some optional measures – e.g. coupled support and payment to farmers in areas of natural constraint (ANC).

Comment: by buite049

*Member states can choose to do it. Member states have some freedom to choose if they want to implement a some extra (predetermined) payments --> fairly enabling
But these extra payments are mostly very robustness-focused - compensation payments and means to protect the status quo --> robustness very enabling score 5*

4 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:26 However those Member States not operating the SAPS must shift direct..... (14:2344 [14:2716]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

However those Member States not operating the SAPS must shift direct payments to farmers away from being calculated on an historic basis towards a uniform per hectare rate across the country (or region – which can be defined according to a number of criteria) and they must reduce payments to those in receipt of over € 150 000 of direct payments by at least 5 %.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints protecting the status quo. There will still be direct payments, however the system will be changed and will affect (dutch) farmers that traditionally received full payments quite hard --> constraining score 2

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

6:31 Art. 48-49 Voluntary payment for farmers in areas with natural con..... (16:1834 [16:2090]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Art. 48-49 Voluntary payment for farmers in areas with natural constraints Decide to grant in the basic payment scheme and in the Single Area Payment Scheme (SAPS) additional per ha payment in less favoured areas/areas with natural constraints.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:33 Art. 52-55 Voluntary coupled support scheme Choose to implement c..... (16:2245 [16:2361]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Art. 52-55 Voluntary coupled support scheme Choose to implement coupled support for different sectors or regions

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:34 Crop-specific payment for cotton Bulgaria, Greece, Spain and Por..... (16:2374 [16:2506]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Crop-specific payment for cotton Bulgaria, Greece, Spain and Portugal can decide to grant a crop specific payment for cotton

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:53 M1.1 Support for vocational training and skills acquisition actions (17:3331 [17:3399]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M1.1 Support for vocational training and skills acquisition actions

Comment: by buite049

*no real social learning, but cognitive learning.
cognitive learning is to keep the farmers up to date on knowledge (within the system) to better maintain their farms.*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

6:54 M1.2 Support for demonstration activities and information actions (17:3624 [17:3690]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M1.2 Support for demonstration activities and information actions

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

6:75 M8.2 Support for establishment and maintenance of agro- forestry sys..... (19:1474 [19:1547]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.2 Support for establishment and maintenance of agro- forestry systems

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

7:22 Voor deze sector speelt ook het belang van een gelijk speelveld, met n..... (9:816 [9:1131]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Voor deze sector speelt ook het belang van een gelijk speelveld, met name ten opzichte van Frankrijk en Vlaanderen. Naar verwachting zullen daar de verliezen voor de huidige hoogontvangers met het zogenaamde Ierse model beperkt worden, en zullen daarnaast in enkele gevallen gekoppelde premies worden ingevoerd.

Comment: by buite049

EU: Irish model makes it possible to reduce the losses for sectors that receive major direct payments + coupled payments for sectors are possible.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

7:27 Zowel Frankrijk als België zal het zogenaamde Ierse convergentiemodel..... (11:2182 [11:2364]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Zowel Frankrijk als België zal het zogenaamde Ierse convergentiemodel toepassen, waarbij de huidige hoogontvangers worden ontzien in de convergentie naar een gelijke hectarepremie.

Comment: by buite049

EU: possibility to use an Irish convergence model during the reform of the direct payments --> this model is in favour of farms / sectors that already receive major direct payments as they are spared from the reform.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

7:47 Ik wil de sector hierbij extra ondersteunen met een geormerkt bedrag..... (9:2126 [9:2224]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Ik wil de sector hierbij extra ondersteunen met een geormerkt bedrag van 0,5 min euro per jaar.

Comment: by buite049

financial support per year for existing production system --> robustness protection of status quo.

But meat sector (not related to case)

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

7:48 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:84:365-19:470:370) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

investeringen in landbouwstructuur 7.7 7.7 15.5

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

8:2 In order to move towards a fairer distribution of support, the CAP sys..... (1:1381 [1:1741]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to move towards a fairer distribution of support, the CAP system for Direct Payments will move away from one where allocations per Member State - and per farmer within the Member State - are based on historical references. This will mean a clear and genuine convergence of payments not only between Member States, but also within Member States

Comment: by buite049

constrains (score 2) the protection of status quo. Farms that receive historically a lot of financial support (potato farmers in Dutch case study) can become confronted with less financial support in the future

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

8:11 Reduction of the payment for large farms : Agreement has been reached..... (2:2034 [2:2478]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Reduction of the payment for large farms : Agreement has been reached on compulsory reduction of the payments for individual farms above 150 000€ ("degressivity"). In practice this mean that the amount of support that an individual farm holding receives as basic payment will be reduced by at least 5% for the amounts above 150 000€. In order to take account of employment, salary costs may be deducted before the calculation is made.

Comment: by buite049

constraints the protection of status quo, but no real major transformation. --> slightly constraining

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

8:16 Member States will have the option of providing limited amounts of "..... (3:1501 [3:1973]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Member States will have the option of providing limited amounts of "coupled" payments, i.e. a payment linked to a specific product. This will be limited to up to 8% of the national envelope, or up to 13% if the current level of coupled support in a Member State is higher than 5%.The Commission has flexibility to approve a higher rate where justified. There is a possibility of providing an additional amount (up to 2%) of "coupled" support for protein crops.

Comment: by buite049

Measure to provide farms with extra buffer payments on top of the already granted direct payments

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

8:46 Other areas facing natural & other specific constraints: New delimitat..... (7:2318 [7:2657]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Other areas facing natural & other specific constraints: New delimitation for Areas with Natural Constraints (ANC) – with effect from 2018 at the latest - based on 8 biophysical criteria; Member States retain flexibility to define up to 10% of their agricultural area for specific constraints to preserve or improve the environment;

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

9:8 Further reforms from 2003 saw the breaking of the link between direc..... (2:2842 [2:3026]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Further reforms from 2003 saw the breaking of the link between direct payments to farmers and the type of products (and the amount) they produced – a process known as ‘decoupling’.

Comment: by buite049

The decoupling is a way of reducing the protection of the status quo. This instrument is therefore very constraining the protection of the status quo as it makes it necessary for farmers to move towards the free market with more economic risks.

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

9:27 and (where applied) voluntary Support coupled to production to help..... (4:799 [4:908]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

and (where applied) voluntary Support coupled to production to help certain sectors undergoing difficulties

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:40 Coupled support (6:680 [6:695]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Coupled support

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:58 However, member states may continue to link (or couple) a limited amou..... (9:2248 [9:2362]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

However, member states may continue to link (or couple) a limited amount of direct payments to certain products.

Comment: by buite049

enables the protection of the status quo --> have not give it a scoe of 5, because it is voluntary. However, it is a clear example of protecting the status quo.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

10:66 Om de landbouwstructuur verder te versterken wil ik binnen POP3 onge..... (12:562 [12:741]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Om de landbouwstructuur verder te versterken wil ik binnen POP3 ongeveer €15 miljoen reserveren, waarvan de helft EU-cofinanciering en de helft cofinanciering van de provincies

Comment: by buite049

money available to support 'the structure of the agricultural sector'

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

10:88 Voor jonge boeren gaan de provincies in nader overleg een landsdekke..... (12:2600 [12:2822]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Voor jonge boeren gaan de provincies in nader overleg een landsdekkende investeringsregeling inrichten ter stimulering hiervan voor een bedrag van €5 miljoen per jaar, waarvan de helft aan EU-cofinanciering uit POP3.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

12:46 Door de vorming van clusters van biologische bedrijven kunnen bedrijve..... (11:822 [11:1185]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Door de vorming van clusters van biologische bedrijven kunnen bedrijven in verschillende sectoren (akkerbouw, veehouderij) en binnen ketens elkaar versterken. Daarnaast kan clustering ervoor zorgen dat biologische grond behouden blijft voor de biologische sector, ook als er op een bedrijf geen opvolger is en de gronden worden verkocht aan buurbedrijven.

Comment: by buite049

Clustering as an mean to make sure that the same kind of farms can strenghten each other --> robustness.

It is also used for organic farms, to protect them from dissapearing. The aim is therefore on making sure that the current agricultural activities can continue on --> enables protection of status quo

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

12:74 De innovatieve ontwikkelingen die daarmee op gang worden gebracht ku..... (12:1517 [12:1651]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

De innovatieve ontwikkelingen die daarmee op gang worden gebracht kunnen vanuit verschillende innovatiefondsen worden ondersteund.

Comment: by buite049

financial funds for innovative developments for a more status quo protecting goal. However de subsidies are not there to discourage innovation, but to achieve it. The funds are therefore more subsidies for the existing production system. --> Not really clear. Because the financial funds can be used only if the previous goal leads to innovative developments. Is thus dependent on if the development is indeed considered as a innovation or if innovations take place.

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:5 Financial discipline: existing rules were confirmed, guaranteeing that..... (33:1924 [33:2163]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Financial discipline: existing rules were confirmed, guaranteeing that commitments with regard to financial allocations under the sub-heading 'Market-related expenditure and direct payments' set in Regulation (EU) 1311/2013 are abided by

Comment: by buite049

Financial discipline is necessary to keep the system of Direct Payments working (and better accepted). So the instruments of financial discipline is used to keep the direct payments (the status quo) in control.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:16 The 2014-2020 reform introduced mandatory conditions for claiming dir..... (47:559 [47:1287]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The 2014-2020 reform introduced mandatory conditions for claiming direct payments (leaving the door open for Member States to make them more restrictive if they so wish; Anania and Pupo D'Andrea, 2015). This is done not by defining who is an 'active farmer', but rather by defining who is not. A farmer (whether a natural or legal person) is considered 'non-active' – and, as a result, is not entitled direct payment – whose farm lies in an area naturally kept in a state suitable for grazing or cultivation and who does not carry out in that area the minimum activity defined by the Member State. The Cioloş reform actually goes further and defines a 'black list' of entities that cannot be considered 'active farmers'.

Comment: by buite049

Is in interest of the agricultural sector. To come to a more fairer distribution of direct payments. But also to ensure that the system can continue existing --> slightly enabling robustness --> protection of status quo.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:21 It should be noted, however, that the scope of the 'black list' is sig..... (47:1530 [47:2022]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

It should be noted, however, that the scope of the 'black list' is significantly reduced by the provision that even entities included on the list may receive direct payments if they are able to prove that: the annual amount of the direct payment is at least 5 % of the annual total receipts they obtain from non-agricultural activities; or their agricultural activities are not insignificant; or their principal company objective consists of exercising an agricultural activity.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the protection of the status quo and of the agricultural interest. The 'black list' is significantly reduced by the provision that even entities included on the list can still receive direct payments by proving a set of conditions --> Constraining robustness. --> the previous measure then seems to be of less importance because this 'side note' shows that it is possible to get around it.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:31 The number of payment entitlements allocated in 2015 to each farm is e..... (50:155 [50:985]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The number of payment entitlements allocated in 2015 to each farm is equal to the number of eligible hectares that a farmer declares in 2015. Member States may limit the number of entitlements assigned to a farmer. In particular, Member States may: allocate a number of payment entitlements equal to the number of eligible hectares that a farmer declared in 2013, if this is lower than the number declared in 2015; reduce the number of payment entitlements allocated if the number of eligible hectares totally declared in Member States in 2015 is more than 35 % in respect to the number declared in 2009 (2013 in Croatia); apply a reduction coefficient to the permanent grassland located in areas with natural constraints; exclude the land devoted to vineyard in 2013 or the arable land under permanent greenhouse.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints protecting the status quo as the Member States can decide to reduce the entitlements allocated.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:63 1.2.4.11. Crop-specific payment for cotton Notwithstanding the extens..... (56:1971 [56:2182]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

1.2.4.11. Crop-specific payment for cotton Notwithstanding the extensive decoupling of support induced by the previous reform of the CAP, significant coupled support has remained in place in the cotton sector.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:66 In order to generate a more equitable distribution of direct payments,..... (58:757 [58:946]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In order to generate a more equitable distribution of direct payments, the reform introduced a mandatory reduction, by at least 5 %, of basic payments for the part exceeding EUR 150, 000.

Comment: by buite049

a mandatory instrument that constraints the protection of the status quo, however it can be seen as minimal because it only influences the first 5% and is mandatory. The measure can grow to a bigger treat for the status quo if the member states decides to increase the percentage up to 100%

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

15:74 the payment for areas with natural constraints. (59:1286 [59:1332]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

the payment for areas with natural constraints.

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands will not apply the payment for areas with natural constraints --> constraints the protection of the status quo.

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:97 Implementation of the payment for areas with natural constraints (94:979 [94:1044]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Implementation of the payment for areas with natural constraints

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands have not implemented the payment for areas with natural constraints ---> constraints the protection of the status quo (in those areas which could have applied)

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:100 The voluntary coupled support is a payment that Member States may grant..... (92:903 [92:1520]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The voluntary coupled support is a payment that Member States may grant each year to farmers with the aim of supporting specific sectors and products listed in Article 52 of Regulation (EU) 1307/2013. The payment may only be granted to those sectors, or to those regions, in which specific types of farming or specific agricultural sectors (of particular importance for economic, social or environmental reasons) face certain difficulties. This means that the support may only be granted to the extent necessary to create an incentive to maintain current levels of production in the sectors or regions concerned.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:103 Belgium, the Netherlands, Austria and Sweden have chosen targeted supp..... (93:252 [93:356]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Belgium, the Netherlands, Austria and Sweden have chosen targeted support only for livestock production,

Comment: by buite049

Only for livestock production, not for arable crops (as is the case for the dutch case study veen -Oldambt) --> not enabling protection of status quo

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:105 Degressivity at mandatory level was chosen by 14 Member States (Cyprus..... (88:3107 [88:3334]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Degressivity at mandatory level was chosen by 14 Member States (Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Estonia, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Portugal, Finland, Slovenia Slovakia and Sweden) (Table 1.15).

Comment: by buite049

*Constraints the protection of the status quo a bit.
The Netherlands chose only for 5 % reduction for the part of the amount exceeding 150,000 euro. and they decided to deduct labour costs before applying the degressivity -
-> slightly constraints*

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

15:106 (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States (91:55:453-91:258:468) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Content

Netherlands	Not implemented
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Comment: by buite049

no distribution of financial support from larger farms to smaller farms. Keeping the situation as it is now --> protecting status quo.

1 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

15:108 Full convergence in 2019, at the latest: in the entire Member State, o..... (48:3109 [48:3317]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Full convergence in 2019, at the latest: in the entire Member State, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State, the same value of the payment entitlement is to be applied by 2019, at the latest;

4 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / J. Adaptability_3

15:109 Partial convergence: differences between the values of the per-hectare..... (48:3321 [48:3565]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Partial convergence: differences between the values of the per-hectare basic payment received by farmers in the Member State as a whole, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State, are to be reduced, but will still exist in 2019.

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / E. Robustness_4

15:110 Full convergence in 2015: in 2015, the first year of implementation of..... (48:2809 [48:3105]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Full convergence in 2015: in 2015, the first year of implementation of the new CAP, the same unit value of the payment entitlement (in other words, the same value of per-hectare basic payment) was to be applied in the entire Member State, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State;

Comment: by buite049

Constrains the protection of the status quo as the whole system is changed in one-go. However, the system of direct payments (based on a Ha) is still in place.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

17:40 Between 2014 and 2020 the EU plans to make available to farmers almo..... (12:62 [12:272]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Between 2014 and 2020 the EU plans to make available to farmers almost 4 million places on training courses and 1.4 million advisory sessions with a focus on economic and environmental performance of farms

Comment: by buite049

Is focused on learning, but more on just cognitive learning and not on social learning in which people together will reflect on underlying assumptions

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

17:43 the formation of producer organisations: these allow farmers to form..... (12:1243 [12:1441]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

the formation of producer organisations: these allow farmers to form groups so that they can sell their products collectively, enabling them to exert greater market power within the food chain;

Comment: by buite049

protection of status quo = it focuses on the interest of the agricultural sector - the interest of the farmers. Together they will be stronger and better capable to deal with short fluctuations brought by markets

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

17:44 other forms of cooperation to give farmers more leverage in the mark..... (12:1446 [12:1570]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

other forms of cooperation to give farmers more leverage in the marketplace and raise profit margins and competitiveness;

Comment: by buite049

*protection of status quo = it focuses on the interest of the agricultural sector - the interest of the farmers. Together they will be stronger and better capable to deal with short fluctuations brought by markets. Or to make sure that they can maintain their desired level of outputs
score 2 --> due to the wording "other forms of cooperation" - this is less clear than the previous statement.*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

17:53 It also provides grants to train both new and established farmers in..... (8:917 [8:1032]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

It also provides grants to train both new and established farmers in the latest technical production methods.

Comment: by buite049

cognitive learning, not really a social process. Is meant to make sure that farmers are using the right techniques to continue the current production system

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

17:54 In pursuance of safe and high-quality food, Europe has developed a r..... (13:626 [13:868]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

In pursuance of safe and high-quality food, Europe has developed a range of tools over the years. These include marketing standards, quality systems to identify products with a specific quality, certification systems and hygiene rules.

Comment: by buite049

A range of certification tools to make sure that the products keep a high standard. It is in iagricultural interest to make sure farmers can produce food at a high standard --> robustness protection of status quo -- slightly enables

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

18:1 Een voorbeeld hiervan is de programmatische aanpak stikstof (PAS)..... (6:532 [6:810]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Een voorbeeld hiervan is de programmatische aanpak stikstof (PAS), gericht op de vermindering van stikstof emissie. Een dergelijk programma kan van grote invloed zijn op de uitbreidingsmogelijkheden van landbouwbedrijven in de (verre) omgeving van een natuurgebied.

Comment: by Buite049

Constraining

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

18:12 Door het wegvallen van de melkquotering en de toename van de melkpro..... (8:786 [8:1204]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Door het wegvallen van de melkquotering en de toename van de melkproductie is binnen de melkveehouderij veel discussie ontstaan over de fosfaatoverschotten. Dit heeft geresulteerd in nationale wetgeving over grondgebondenheid van melkveehouderijen en de bemesting met fosfaat. Naar verwachting zal dit in de komende jaren blijvend druk leggen op de ontwikkelingsmogelijkheden van de melkveehouderij.

Comment: by Buite049

Constraining

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments

18:63 4. Graanacademie Groningen (specifiek opgericht voor de provincie Gr..... (14:2757 [14:3036]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

4. Graanacademie Groningen (specifiek opgericht voor de provincie Groningen): een initiatief van graantelers in het Oldambt om de teelt van granen qua opbrengst en duurzaamheid op een hoger plan te brengen. Proefboerderij SPNA is trekker van de Graanacademie Groningen.

Comment: by buite049

goals is to develop the wheat sector in the region in such a way that it can increase the levels of output

2 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3

Robust_buffer_resources_goals

34 Quotations:

2:7 direct payments are the major source of support (4:712 [4:761]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

direct payments are the major source of support

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

3:1 de komende verandering van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouw Beleid (GL..... (3:1104 [3:1324]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

de komende verandering van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouw Beleid (GLB). Die verandering heeft grote impact op de aardappelzetmeelsector en dus ook op de Veenkoloniën.

Boeren zullen er in inkomen op achteruitgaan.

Comment: by buite049

*The change how direct payments are distributed (historical --> per Ha) has big influence on the potato sector in the area, because farmers will loose a large share of their income because of this. The buffer resource is therefore constraint.
But is it really dismantling the status quo when their is still a system based on direct payments?*

| For the region it will result at least in big losses regarding income

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

3:11 Het nieuwe GLB gaat per 2015 van start. Nederland kiest daarbij voor..... (8:25 [8:273]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Het nieuwe GLB gaat per 2015 van start.

Nederland kiest daarbij voor een geleidelijke invoering van inkomstenstoelagen naar een zogenaamde 'flat rate' tot 2020. Voor boeren in de Veenkoloniën betekent dit een forse teruggang in hun inkomen.

Comment: by buite049

| *The decision to change the way direct payments are calculated has a major effect on the income of the farmers. This thus constraints the buffer resources for the farmers in the veenkoloniën.*

| *Geleidelijk - gradually changing the system from 2015 - 2020*

4 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

6:58 M4.1 Support for investments in agricultural holdings (18:289 [18:343]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M4.1 Support for investments in agricultural holdings

Comment: by buite049

| *The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for the current farm holdings in order to make sure that they can keep continuing their farming practices.*

| *The investments could be considered as a short-term solution / market-oriented solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. Investments in that case provide a buffer.*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

6:59 M4.2 Support for investments in processing/marketing and/or development..... (18:455 [18:554]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M4.2 Support for investments in processing/marketing and/or development of agricultural products

Comment: by buite049

The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for the current products that farms deliver in order to make sure that they can keep continuing their farming practices.

The investments could be considered as a short-term solution / market-oriented solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

6:60 Support for investments in infrastructure related to development, mo..... (18:562 [18:686]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Support for investments in infrastructure related to development, modernisation or adaptation of agriculture and forestry

Comment: by buite049

The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for the current products that farms deliver in order to make sure that they can keep continuing their farming practices.

The investments could be considered as a short-term solution / market-oriented solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

6:61 M4.4 Support for non-productive investments linked to the achieveme..... (18:689 [18:798]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M4.4 Support for non-productive investments linked to the achievement of agrienvironment-climate objectives

Comment: by buite049

Investments in other; various functions that a farm can have (Variety goals).

The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.

The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:68 M 6.4 support for investments in creation and development of non-agr..... (18:1906 [18:1995]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.4 support for investments in creation and development of non-agricultural activities

Comment: by buite049

*Investments in other; various functions that a farm can have (Variety goals).
The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.
The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.*

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:2 Een belangrijk onderdeel van de huidige hervorming van het GLB is de..... (2:1 [2:361]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Een belangrijk onderdeel van de huidige hervorming van het GLB is de vergroening van de eerste pijler, waarmee een deel van de directe betalingen wordt verbonden aan maatschappelijke doelen. Ik blijf met de vergroening nadrukkelijk streven naar een ambitieuze invulling, die leidt tot echte winst voor biodiversiteit en inpasbaar is in de bedrijfsvoering.

Comment: by buite049

*Constrains the buffer resources direct payments by making them a bit harder to obtain due to stricter conditions regarding greening.
It is also used to change the homogeneity of the farming systems a bit - changing the production strategies without changing too much of the operational logics of the farms.*

4 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

8:9 External Convergence: The national envelopes for direct payments for e..... (2:6 [2:689]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

External Convergence: The national envelopes for direct payments for each Member State will be progressively adjusted such that there is not such a wide gap between Member States in the average payment per hectare. This will mean that those Member States where the average payment (in € per hectare) is currently below 90% of the EU average will see a gradual increase in their envelope (by 1/3 of the difference between their current rate and 90% of the EU average). Moreover, there is the guarantee that

every Member State will reach a minimum level by 2019. The amounts available for other Member States who receive above average amounts will be adjusted accordingly.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the buffer resources instrument for member states that traditionally received large envelopes. it changes the traditional national envelopes for direct payments. However, the goal is as the traditional goal of direct payments to provide a financial buffer for farmers --> score 3 fairly enabling fairly constraining

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:22 Financial Discipline: notwithstanding the separate decision for the 20..... (4:1062 [4:1468]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Financial Discipline: notwithstanding the separate decision for the 2014 budget year, it was agreed that any future Financial Discipline reduction in annual direct payments (i.e. when payment estimates are higher than the available budget for the 1st Pillar) should apply a threshold of €2 000. In other words, the reduction would NOT apply to the first €2 000 of each farmer's Direct Payments.

Comment: by buite049

There is a financial discipline. But the importance of the buffer resources is kept in mind because it will affect the direct payments above 2000euro. slightly constraining robustness buffer resource score 4

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

8:24 In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled..... (4:2104 [4:2297]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled a limited number of companies to claim Direct Payments, even though their primary business activity is not agricultural,

Comment: by buite049

The term active farmer is introduced to make the direct payments more selective and to reduce 'abuse'. --> dismantling incentives that protect the status quo. But also to make the payments more credible. The goal is to protect the direct payments to make sure it can continue--> to make the current system a bit more robust --> transformability score 2--> robustness score 4

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals

8:50 Forestry: Strengthened / streamlined support through grants and annual..... (7:2103 [7:2184]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Forestry: Strengthened / streamlined support through grants and annual payments;

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

8:51 Young farmers - A combination of measures can include business start-u..... (7:1168 [7:1304]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Young farmers - A combination of measures can include business start-up grants (up to €70 000), general investments in physical assets,

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

8:54 Those Member States that currently maintain allocations based on his..... (2:716 [2:877]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Those Member States that currently maintain allocations based on historical references must move towards more similar levels of the basic payment per hectare.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints protecting the status quo as the old historical references will be removed. --> fairly constraining 3 However, the measure is still focussed on a basic payment and the goal is to provide the farmers with a basic income as a buffer --> robust buffer resource goals --> enables robust buffer resource 4

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

8:59 Cross compliance: All direct payments, certain rural development payme..... (8:656 [8:1093]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Cross compliance: All direct payments, certain rural development payments and certain vine payments will continue to be linked to the respect of a number of statutory requirements relating to environment, climate change, good agricultural condition of land, human, animal & plant health standards and animal welfare. The list has been simplified to exclude rules where there are no clear and controllable obligations for farmers.

Comment: by buite049

The idea of cross-compliance is to have a set of rules / requirements for farmers to receive direct payments.

However it is not really constraining for farmers to receive these direct payments.

Moreover, it is introduced to make sure that the direct payments are a bit more legitimate. --> score 5 robustness

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

9:1 Its aim is to help provide a decent standard of living for European..... (1:319 [1:421]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Its aim is to help provide a decent standard of living for European farmers and agricultural workers

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

9:7 But in order to prevent a corresponding fall in the incomes of farme..... (2:2100 [2:2283]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

But in order to prevent a corresponding fall in the incomes of farmers, direct payments were introduced, based on historical levels of production (by area or livestock numbers).

Comment: by buite049

Should not be scored - as this is about the history of the CAP.

This is changed after the reform of 2013/14

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

9:15 In an uncertain and unpredictable economic environment, direct payme..... (3:2904 [3:3295]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In an uncertain and unpredictable economic environment, direct payments provide a safety net for farmers. They are a stable source of income that is independent of market fluctuations, making a very important contribution to overall farm income for many farm households (up to around half the total income level). They also give farmers more freedom in taking business decisions.

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

10:5 wil ik in het nieuwe GLB inzetten op een eerlijke hectarepremie, (2:1489 [2:1554]) - D 10: (Dijkma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

wil ik in het nieuwe GLB inzetten op een eerlijke hectarepremie,

Comment: by buite049

A fair direct payment - it is important to make sure the direct payments can continue but in a more legitimate way --> enables buffer resources

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:34 If Member States having applied the SAPS decide to introduce the basic..... (50:2461 [50:2664]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

If Member States having applied the SAPS decide to introduce the basic payment scheme, the active farmers entitled to receive direct payments will be the beneficiaries of the basic payment entitlements

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:39 Member States may use the national/regional reserve, inter alia, to al..... (51:1648 [51:2410]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may use the national/regional reserve, inter alia, to allocate payment entitlements: ☑ to avoid abandonment of the land; ☑ to compensate farmers for specific disadvantages; ☑ to farmers that cannot have payment entitlements as result of force majeure or exceptional circumstances; ☑ to address specific situations in SAPS; ☑ to provide a linear increase, on permanent basis, of the value of all entitlements of the basic payment scheme if the national / regional reserve exceeds 0.5 % of the respective annual ceiling for the basic payment; ☑ to cover the annual needs for payments to be granted to young farmers (if to this ceiling is devoted less than 2 % of the national ceiling for direct payments) and to the small farmers scheme.

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

15:65 In order to generate a more equitable distribution of direct payments (58:757 [58:825]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In order to generate a more equitable distribution of direct payments

Comment: by buite049

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

15:80 or to increase direct support to the agricultural sector (65:3067 [65:3122]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

or to increase direct support to the agricultural sector

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

15:87 The Netherlands, finally, seems to have chosen the most stringent con..... (70:3373 [70:3802]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The Netherlands, finally, seems to have chosen the most stringent conditions for being considered active (a threshold of EUR 1 and the registration of the agricultural activity in the official business register, implying a minimum annual turnover of EUR 10 000; it is expected, however, that the number of historical beneficiaries of direct payments that will not be able to enter the business register will be negligible).

Comment: by buite049

More strict rule in the Netherlands before you are able to be seen as an active farmer and thus receiving direct payments --> this is thus an situation in which its should become less eay for farmers to receive direct payments / financial compensation. --> therefore it constraints the buffer resources (at least for a small part, according to the author(s)).

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:88 Spain, Flanders, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and Finland..... (71:326 [71:476]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Spain, Flanders, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and Finland. Austria, all UK regions, Sweden and Denmark have raised the physical threshold;

Comment: by buite049

slightly constraints the distribution of the buffer resource of direct payments --> the physical treshold (amount of land) to recieve direct payment has been hightened

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4

15:91 The main goal of this component of the direct payments is to remunera..... (78:698 [78:852]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The main goal of this component of the direct payments is to remunerate some public goods produced by farmers when they comply with specific requirements

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

15:115 a system for the progressive reduction of direct payments (66:671 [66:727]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

a system for the progressive reduction of direct payments

Comment: by buite049

| *constraints buffer resources*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals

17:2 to ensure that EU farmers can make a reasonable living. (3:351 [3:409]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

to ensure that EU farmers can make a reasonable living.

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:7 Farmers manage the countryside for the benefit of us all. They suppl..... (4:2277 [4:2641]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Farmers manage the countryside for the benefit of us all. They supply public goods — the most important of which is the good care and maintenance of our soils, our landscapes and our biodiversity. The market does not pay for these public goods. To remunerate farmers for this service to society as a whole, the EU provides farmers with income support.

Comment: by buite049

Farmers manage the countryside. The direct payments provide them with financial compensation for this job.

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:8 Farmers can be adversely affected by climate change. The CAP provides..... (4:2642 [4:2840]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Farmers can be adversely affected by climate change.

The CAP provides them with financial assistance to adjust their farming methods and systems to cope with the effects of a changing climate.

Comment: by buite049

financial assistance to deal with the effect of a changing climate - Climate change brings shocks to the agricultural sector. The financial compensation is then meant to make the agricultural sector better capable to withstand these shocks

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:9 Farmers are the first to realise the need to care for our natural re..... (4:2842 [4:3150]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Farmers are the first to realise the need to care for our natural resources — after all farmers rely upon them for their day-to-day living. To avoid negative side effects of some farming practices, the EU provides incentives to farmers to work in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to make sure that the agricultural production has not too much negative effects on the environment. The Cap provides farmers with incentives (financial compensation) for working in an environmental friendly way. However, to work environmental friendly / sustainable als has the goal to make sure that the farmers can still produce products in the (near) future and that they, for instance, did not damage the soil too much for production.

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:21 This is why the CAP helps young people to get started in farming wit..... (8:800 [8:915])
- D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

This is why the CAP helps young people to get started in farming with funds to buy land, machinery and equipment

Comment: by buite049

Provides young farmers with financial compensation to start farming

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

17:25 It is only fair that farmers are rewarded by the CAP for providing..... (9:1875 [9:1982]) -
D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

It is only fair that farmers are rewarded by the CAP for providing us with this valuable public good.

Comment: by buite049

financial compensation for their efforts of protecting public goods

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robustness_5

Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

103 Quotations:

2:3 the amount for pillar 1 was cut by 1.8% (3:1253 [3:1293]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

the amount for pillar 1 was cut by 1.8%

Comment: by buite049

Constraints buffer resources

Less money for Pillar one, means that there is less money available for the direct payments; thus decreasing the available funds for these buffer resources.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:6 By the end of 2013 it dropped to just 5% as market intervention has..... (4:591 [4:707]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

By the end of 2013 it dropped to just 5% as market intervention has become a safety net tool for times of crisis

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:10 Therefore, a new policy instrument of the first pillar (greening)..... (5:596 [5:731]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Therefore, a new policy instrument of the first pillar (greening) is directed to the provision of environmental public goods,

Comment: by buite049

Greening is a financial mean / subsidy. It is a financial compensation for the introduction of new tasks that farms need to undertake.

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:24 Firstly there is a simplified and more targeted cross-compliance, re..... (6:2879 [6:3088]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Firstly there is a simplified and more targeted cross-compliance, representing the compulsory basic layer of environmental requirements and obligations to be met in order to receive full CAP funding.

Comment: by buite049

*Cross-compliance is a mean of the buffer resource - direct payments - it needs to make sure that a minimum of greening is at least reached
it fairly enables robustness buffer resources as it needs to make sure that at least some requirements are met before a farmer can appeal for direct payments*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:27 1, the Green Direct Payment.Agricultural Brief on CAP..... (6:3183 [7:298]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

1, the Green Direct Payment.

Agricultural Brief on CAP 7 This accounts for 30% of the national direct payment envelope and rewards farmers for respecting three obligatory agricultural practices,

Comment: by buite049

*Green direct payment is a compensation payment for respecting three obligatory agricultural practices. It is therefore a buffer resource.
However because it is aimed at greening measures the score will be reduced to score 4*

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:30 Faced with an ageing farming population (only 14% of EU farmers ar..... (7:2517 [7:2825]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Faced with an ageing farming population (only 14% of EU farmers are under 40 years of age), from 2015, all young farmers entering the sector will have the opportunity to get an additional first pillar payment, which can still be complemented by a start-up aid under the second pillar.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

2:31 Basic Payment (7:2343 [7:2357]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Basic Payment

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

2:32 green direct payment (7:2379 [7:2398]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

green direct payment

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:33 support for ANCs (7:2427 [7:2442]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

support for ANCs

Comment: by buite049

protection of areas facing natural constraints. This measure want to support farms in difficult areas to make sure that they can continue to operate. via financial support

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

2:35 A specific and simplified support scheme for small farmers will subs..... (7:3083 [7:3248]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

A specific and simplified support scheme for small farmers will substantially facilitate their access to direct payments and reduce their administrative burden.

Comment: by buite049

The measure itself is robust, because it is nothing more than financial compensation through direct payments; However, the measure is there with in mind that there are differences between member states regarding their capacity to arrange direct payments. It thus provides a different policy option to arrange direct payments.

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

2:36 A redistributive payment can be attributed to the first hectares o..... (7:2930 [7:3081]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

A redistributive payment can be attributed to the first hectares of the farms, to provide more targeted support to small and medium-sized farms.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:44 degressivity (reduction) of payments, (8:2171 [8:2209]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

degressivity (reduction) of payments,

Comment: by buite049

slightly constraining because it is voluntary

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

2:45 voluntary capping (8:2149 [8:2166]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

voluntary capping

Comment: by buite049

slightly constraining because it is voluntary

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

4:5 Daarnaast zal ik maximaal gebruik maken van de mogelijkheid om in de e..... (2:286 [2:442]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-Invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Daarnaast zal ik maximaal gebruik maken van de mogelijkheid om in de eerste pijler van het GLB aan jonge boeren een top-up op de hectarepremie te geven.

Comment: by buite049

Buffer resource because it is about direct payments related to the amount of land a farmer has. However a bit of variety as the measure is adapted to provide young farmers with a bit more financial support.

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

6:9 Budgets (2014 – 2020): Pillar 1 € 4.35 billion (31%) (51:2582 [51:2633]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Budgets (2014 – 2020): Pillar 1 € 4.35 billion (31%)

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:14 Small Farmers Scheme not implemented (51:2751 [51:2786]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Small Farmers Scheme not implemented

Comment: by buite049

constraints flexibility as there are no other options for small farmers available regarding the Direct payments. But this does mean that also small farmers need to commit to greening measures etc as these will not be replaced for them because of the small farmers scheme

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

6:22 the basic payment scheme (BPS); (14:1804 [14:1834]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

the basic payment scheme (BPS);

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:23 payments for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the..... (14:1839 [14:1960]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

payments for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment (the so-called 'greening' measures);

Comment: by buite049

It is a financial compensation, but it is aimed at more environmental green measures --> fairly enabling robustness buffer resource.

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

6:24 the young farmer scheme (YFS) (14:1969 [14:1997]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

the young farmer scheme (YFS)

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:28 Reduce payments by more than 5 % for amounts exceeding € 150 000; (15:1694 [15:1758]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Reduce payments by more than 5 % for amounts exceeding € 150 000;

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the buffer resources

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

6:30 MS having a single payment scheme in place in accordance with Section..... (16:211 [16:767]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

MS having a single payment scheme in place in accordance with Section I of Chapter 5 of Title III or Chapter 6 of Title III of Reg. (EC) No. 1782/2003 or Chapter 3 of Title III of Reg. (EC) No. 73/2009 can decide to keep existing payment entitlements; Decide to apply different values for payment entitlements according to Art. 26(2), yet convergence rules need to be taken into account; Decide to apply the basic payment scheme at regional level; When applying the single area payment scheme, decide to grant transitional national aid.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:32 Art. 50-51 Payment for young farmers commencing their agricultural..... (16:2091 [16:2244]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Art. 50-51 Payment for young farmers commencing their agricultural activity Decide to allocate up to 2 % of the national ceiling to this scheme.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

6:35 Voluntary simplified scheme for small farmers Decide to implement..... (16:2520 [16:2615]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Voluntary simplified scheme for small farmers Decide to implement a small farmers scheme.

Comment: by buite049

a special scheme for small farmers then can be used = flexibility

Still direct payments that are used as financial compensation = buffer resource

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:36 Art. 16-20 Framework within which Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania may..... (16:2616 [16:3013]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Art. 16-20 Framework within which Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania may complement direct payments Bulgaria and Romania are in 2015 still allowed to complement direct payments with national direct payments; Bulgaria is allowed to complement the specific payment for cotton with national direct payments; Croatia is allowed to complement direct payments with national direct payments.

Comment: by buite049

It are measures that just provide financial support (extra), However the goal of these measures is based on that these countries differ in their farming context and are new members of the EU.

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:62 M 6.5 payments for farmers eligible for the small farmers scheme who..... (18:2086 [18:2210]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.5 payments for farmers eligible for the small farmers scheme who permanently transfer their holding to another farmer

Comment: by buite049

financial compensation

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

6:79 M8.6 Support for investments in forestry technologies and in process..... (19:2924 [20:157]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.6 Support for investments in forestry technologies and in processing, mobilising
Determine the size of holdings above which support becomes conditional on the drafting of a

Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP 20 Measure Sub-measures
Specific implementation choices for MS and marketing of forest products

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

6:88 M11.1 Payment to convert to organic farming practices and methods (20:1186 [20:1252]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M11.1 Payment to convert to organic farming practices and methods

Comment: by buite049

It is just a financial compensation / subsidy to convert to organic farming, however it is a subsidy that does not discourage innovation but that promotes changing homogeneity of farms

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / N.
Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

**6:89 M11.2 Payment to maintain organic farming practices and methods (20:1590 [20:1654])
- D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP**

M11.2 Payment to maintain organic farming practices and methods

Comment: by buite049

*financial compensation to keep organic farming in place.
The goal is however also to maintain this newer / environmental friendlier (niche) form
of farming*

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / N.
Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

**7:16 Uitgangspunt bij de GLB-hervorming is dat betalingen op basis van hist..... (8:65 [8:329])
- D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-
landbouwbeleid (1)**

Uitgangspunt bij de GLB-hervorming is dat betalingen op basis van historische referenties maatschappelijk niet langer verdedigbaar zijn. Daarom houd ik vast aan de convergentie naar een gelijke hectarepremie in 2019 en blijvende ontkoppeling (zie TK 28625-168).

Comment: by buite049

*Constraints the protection of the status quo, however is is not a drastic change that it transforms the system. It changes how direct payments (buffer resources) are granted and changes the situation for certain sector. It therefore constraints the buffer resources, however the system is only adapted not removed. I would therefore not argue that it is transforming the system by dismantling the status quo.
Robustness 4 - slightly constraining - Buffer resources
Robustness 3 - fairly constraining - protection status quo - as the argument is that the old situation is not favourable.*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robustness_4 / F.
Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

7:24 Zetmeelaardappeltelers zien hun directe inkomenssteun de komende jaren..... (9:2544 [9:2758]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Zetmeelaardappeltelers zien hun directe inkomenssteun de komende jaren sterk afnemen. Dit heeft niet alleen gevolgen voor de sector, maar ook voor de regio van de Veenkoloniën, waar deze sector zich concentreert.

Comment: by buite049

Reform constrains the buffer resources for the potato sector in the Veenkoloniën. --> it reduces their direct payments by a large sum.

Score 1 - very constraining Robustness

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

7:26 Voor de begrazing op de uitgesloten gronden voer ik een graasdierpremi..... (10:1699 [10:2605]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Voor de begrazing op de uitgesloten gronden voer ik een graasdierpremie in voor vleesvee en schapen. Dit is als volgt uitgewerkt. Het aantal dieren dat in aanmerking komt voor de premie, wordt gecorrigeerd voor het eigen grasland, omdat de dieren daar ook kunnen Brazen. De hoogte van de premie is zo berekend dat de graasdierpremie bij benadering gelijkwaardig is aan de basispremie per hectare landbouwgrond. De premie voor runderen geldt voor meerjarige dieren; in de berekening is meegenomen dat naast meerjarige dieren ook jongvee meegraast. De premie voor schapen is voor dieren ouder dan een jaar, waarbij rekening is gehouden met meegrazende lammeren. Daarmee komt de premie op 160 euro per rund en 24 euro per schaaap. De vergroeningspremie is hierin niet meegenomen omdat graasdierhouders geen vergroeningsinspanning hoeven te verrichten op de van de hectarepremie uitgesloten gronden.

Comment: by buite049

financial support for animals used for grazing.

It is implemented as a way to replace the direct payments. The greening measures do not apply on this sector.

This measure is explicitly made to compensate for the fact that the sector does not qualify for the direct payments.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

7:33 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (18:76:406-18:460:604) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

kalenderjaar begrotingsjaar	2014 2015	2015 2016	2016 2017	2017 2018	2018 2019	2019 2020	2020 2021	totaal
Nationale enveloppe directe betalingen	793	781	768	756	744	732	732	5.307
waarvan:								
basisbetaling	758	506	497	490	481	473	473	3.678
vergroeningsbetaling	-	225	221	217	214	210	210	1.297
jonge boeren	-	15,0	14,7	14,5	14,3	14,0	14,0	87
graasdierpremie	-	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,5	21
artikel 68	35,4	-	-	-	-	-	-	35
internationale doelen	-	20,0	20,0	20,0	20,0	20,0	20,0	120
verduurzaming	-	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	69
knelsectoren:								
- kalverhouderij	-	10,0	10,0	10,0	10,0	10,0	10,0	60
- vleesveehouderij	-	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	3
- zetmeelsector	-	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	6

Comment: by buite049

Financial means for the Direct Payments enables the buffer resources. However not very enabling because the financial means are reduced over the years

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

7:45 De meeste van deze bedrijven worden geholpen door de in te stellen gr..... (9:1393 [9:1477]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

De meeste van deze bedrijven worden geholpen door de in te stellen graasdierpremie,

Comment: by buite049

An extra buffer resource for a sector that otherwise would not receive these buffer resources.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:1 Moreover, the introduction of a "Greening Payment" – where 30% of the..... (1:1744 [1:2057]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Moreover, the introduction of a "Greening Payment" – where 30% of the available national envelope is linked to the provision of certain sustainable farming practices – means that a significant share of the subsidy will in future be linked to rewarding farmers for the provision of environmental public goods.

Comment: by buite049

The greening payments is a subsidy to compensate farmers for their work (losses) due to environmental measures.

It is still a buffer resource / compensation - therefore robust buffer resource enabling. However, because it is focused on environmental measures the score is not 5 (very enabling).

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:5 The Basic Payment Scheme (BPS): Member States will dedicate up to 70%..... (1:2216 [1:2611]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

The Basic Payment Scheme (BPS): Member States will dedicate up to 70% of their Direct Payments national envelope to the new Basic Payment Scheme – minus any amounts committed for additional payments (Young Farmer top-ups, and other options such as Less Favoured Area top-ups, the Redistributive Payment) and "coupled" payments. For the concerned EU-12, the end-date for the simpler,

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

8:6 flat-rate Single Area Payments Scheme (SAPS) system will be extended..... (1:2613 [1:2694]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

flat-rate Single Area Payments Scheme (SAPS) system will be extended until 2020.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

8:9 External Convergence: The national envelopes for direct payments for e..... (2:6 [2:689]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

External Convergence: The national envelopes for direct payments for each Member State will be progressively adjusted such that there is not such a wide gap between Member States in the average payment per hectare. This will mean that those Member States where the average payment (in € per hectare) is currently below 90% of the EU average will see a gradual increase in their envelope (by 1/3 of the difference between their current rate and 90% of the EU average). Moreover, there is the guarantee that every Member State will reach a minimum level by 2019. The amounts available for other Member States who receive above average amounts will be adjusted accordingly.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the buffer resources instrument for member states that traditionally received large envelopes. it changes the traditional national envelopes for direct

payments. However, the goal is as the traditional goal of direct payments to provide a financial buffer for farmers --> score 3 fairly enabling fairly constraining

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:10 Member States also have the right to use a redistributive payment for..... (2:1696 [2:2029]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Member States also have the right to use a redistributive payment for the first hectares whereby they can take up to 30% of the national envelope and redistribute it to farmers on their first 30 hectares (or up to the average farm size in a Member State if higher than 30ha). This will have a significant redistributive effect.

Comment: by buite049

Enables a redistribution of buffer resources.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:13 In order to encourage generational renewal, the Basic Payment awarded..... (2:3077 [2:3297]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to encourage generational renewal, the Basic Payment awarded to new entrant Young Farmers (no more than 40 years of age) should be topped up by an additional payment available for a period of maximum 5 years

Comment: by buite049

*period of maximum of 5 years - adaptability middle to long term - however the tool is mostly to make sure the farm system can continue through introducing benefits for younger farmers --> therefore lower score on adaptability --> score 2
Enables an extra buffer resource for young farmers --> score 5*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

8:14 Small Farmers Scheme: Optional for Member States, any farmer claiming..... (3:6 [3:275]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Small Farmers Scheme: Optional for Member States, any farmer claiming support may decide to participate in the Small Farmers Scheme and thereby receive an annual payment fixed by the Member State of normally between 500 € and 1 250 €, regardless of the farm size.

Comment: by buite049

An extra buffer resource for small farmers --> robustness buffer resources. But the mean is voluntary. It enables (score 4) a buffer resource.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:17 Areas with Natural Constraints (ANCs) /Less Favoured Areas (LFAs): Mem..... (3:1974 [3:2317]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Areas with Natural Constraints (ANCs) /Less Favoured Areas (LFAs): Member States (or regions) may grant an additional payment for areas with natural constraints (as defined under Rural Development rules) of up to 5% of the national envelope. This is optional and does not affect the ANC/LFA options available under Rural Development.

Comment: by buite049

Measure to provide farms with extra buffer payments on top of the already granted direct payments

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

8:18 Greening: In addition to the Basic Payment Scheme/SAPS, each holding w..... (3:2318 [3:3366]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Greening: In addition to the Basic Payment Scheme/SAPS, each holding will receive a payment per hectare declared for the purpose of the basic payment for respecting certain agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment. Member States will use 30% of their national envelope in order to pay for this. This is compulsory and failure to respect the Greening requirements will result in reductions and penalties which might in some cases go beyond the Greening payment. In years 1 & 2 the penalty for greening may not exceed 0%, 20% in the third year and as of the fourth the maximum penalty applied will be 25%. Of course, the green payment will only be granted for those areas that comply with the conditions (i.e. being eligible for BPS or SAPS, respect of greening obligations).

Areas under organic production, which is a production system with recognised environmental benefits, shall be considered as fulfilling the conditions for receiving the greening payment, without any additional requirements.

Comment: by buite049

Greening payments for agricultural practices that benefit the environment. It is however a compensation payment for these activities as it means the farmers lose farming land due to the greening measures. It therefore enables robustness buffer resources. Lower

score - no score of 5 - due to the fact that it is focused on environmental measures. --> enabling robustness

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:25 “Active farmers”: In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes whi..... (4:2086 [4:2813]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

“Active farmers”: In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled a limited number of companies to claim Direct Payments, even though their primary business activity is not agricultural, the reform tightens the rule on active farmers. A new negative list of professional business activities which should be excluded from receiving Direct Payments (covering airports, railway services, water works, real estate services and permanent sports & recreation grounds) will be mandatory for Member States, unless the individual businesses concerned can show that they have genuine farming activity. Member States will be able to extend the negative list to include further business activities.

Comment: by buite049

The term active farmer is introduced to make the direct payments more selective and to reduce 'abuse'. --> dismantling incentives that protect the status quo. But also to make the payments more credible. The goal is to protect the direct payments to make sure it can continue--> to make the current system a bit more robust --> transformability score 2--> robustness score 4

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / O. Transformability_2 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

8:43 Farm restructuring / investment / modernisation: Grants still availabl..... (7:1010 [7:1162]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Farm restructuring / investment / modernisation: Grants still available – sometimes with higher support rates when linked to the EIP or joint projects;

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:45 Mountain areas: For mountain areas and farmland above 62° N, aid amoun..... (7:2190 [7:2312]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Mountain areas: For mountain areas and farmland above 62° N, aid amounts can be up to 450 €/ha (increased from 250 €/ha);

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

8:56 Small farmers: Business start-up aid up to €15 000 per small farm; (7:1343 [7:1408]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Small farmers: Business start-up aid up to €15 000 per small farm;

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:3 income support for farmers (so-called “direct payments”); (1:709 [1:766]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

income support for farmers (so-called “direct payments”);

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:19 This is why all farmers receiving direct payments must respect the e..... (3:4212 [3:4372]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

This is why all farmers receiving direct payments must respect the environmental standards set by the EU (which are part of the so-called ‘cross-compliance’

Comment: by buite049

Cross-compliance is a mean of the buffer resource - direct payments - it needs to make sure that a minimum of greening is at least reached. This therefore slightly constraints for farmers to achieve a direct payment. They have to oblige to multiple requirements -- > slightly constraining

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:20 An additional layer of the direct payments system – known as ‘greeni..... (3:4387 [3:4747]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

An additional layer of the direct payments system – known as ‘greening’ – was first implemented in 2015 and covers more than 70% of farmed land. It conditions the granting of a significant share of direct payments to actions which are beneficial for the environment and for climate, such as protection of soil, biodiversity and carbon sequestration.

Comment: by buite049

Greening is coupling direct payments to greening measures.

It is actually still a buffer resource, but focused on more green measurements. It can be seen a way to legitimise the direct payments and to make them more legitimate for the outerworld. But is also set a set of extra green requirements for farmers to which the need to oblige to receive direct payments --> fairly enabling fairly constraining (score 3)

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:21 Direct payments are granted to farmers in the form of a basic income s..... (4:35 [4:149]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Direct payments are granted to farmers in the form of a basic income support based on the number of hectares farmed

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:22 a 'green' direct payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the..... (4:293 [4:393]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

a 'green' direct payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment,

Comment: by buite049

*Greening is coupling direct payments to greening measures.
It is actually still a buffer resource, but focused on more green measurements. It can be seen a way to legitimise the direct payments and to make them more legitimate for the outerworld. But is also set a set of extra green requirements for farmers to which the need to oblige to receive direct payments --> fairly enabling fairly constraining (score 3)*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:23 a payment to young farmers, (4:399 [4:426]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

a payment to young farmers,

Comment: by buite049

It is an extra buffer resource for young farmers to aid them in their farming practices.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

**9:24 • (where applied) a redistributive payment to provide improved supp..... (4:429 [4:533])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

- (where applied) a redistributive payment to provide improved support to small and middle-size farms,

Comment: by buite049

It is an extra buffer resource for small and middle-size farms to aid them in their farming practices.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

**9:25 (where applied) payments for areas with natural constraints, where f..... (4:539 [4:680]) -
D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

- (where applied) payments for areas with natural constraints, where farming conditions are particularly difficult, such as mountain areas,

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

**9:26 (where applied) a small farmers scheme, a simplified scheme for smal..... (4:685 [4:793])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

- (where applied) a small farmers scheme, a simplified scheme for small farmers replacing the other schemes,

Comment: by buite049

*the small farmers scheme is just a simple replacement for the basic direct payments. It is therefore still a robust buffer resource score 5
It is however is also an instrument that slightly enables flexibility as it is a specialised measure to satisfy / support owners of smaller farms. It also replaces other schemes. But also keeping in mind that the goal is to support these farmers with a basic income, it is then less about how this is done.*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

9:36 • Basic payment (6:587 [6:601]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

- Basic payment

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:37 • Green' payment* (6:604 [6:620]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

- Green' payment*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:38 • Young farmers scheme (6:623 [6:644]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

- Young farmers scheme

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:39 A simplified scheme for small farmers (voluntary for MS) (6:499 [6:554]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

A simplified scheme for small farmers (voluntary for MS)

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:41 Support in natural constraint areas (6:700 [6:734]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Support in natural constraint areas

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:42 Redistributive payment (6:739 [6:760]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Redistributive payment

Comment: by buite049

The possibility to support small farms with extra payments for their first hectares. It benefits small farms mostly --> enabling

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

**9:43 The basic payment ensures basic income support for farmers engaged i..... (7:20 [7:422])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

The basic payment ensures basic income support for farmers engaged in agricultural activities. Depending on the choices made by each national authority, the basic payment accounts for between 12% and 68% of their national budget allocation.

The basic payment is applied either as the basic payment scheme (BPS) or as a transitional simplified scheme, the single area payment scheme (SAPS).

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:46 In some member states that joined the European Union in 2004 and 200..... (7:1719 [7:1947]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In some member states that joined the European Union in 2004 and 2007, the single area payment scheme (SAPS) is used instead. The SAPS is a transitional measure stemming from the Accession Treaties of those member states.

Comment: by buite049

*Measure made for a different context --> it is therefore slightly flexible in that it is a measure made for different member states that joined the EU as last.
Still buffer resource because it replaces the normal direct payment scheme.*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

9:47 In order to redistribute support to smaller farmers, member states may..... (7:2355 [7:2968]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In order to redistribute support to smaller farmers, member states may allocate up to 30% of their national budget to a redistributive payment for the first eligible hectares. The number of hectares for which this payment can be allocated is limited to a threshold set by national authorities (30 hectares or the average farm size in member states if the latter is more than 30 hectares). The amount per hectare is the same for all farmers in the country where it is applied, and cannot exceed 65% of the average payment per hectare.

Ten member states have decided to opt for the redistributive payment (

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands have not implemented redistributive payments --> therefore not enabling (score 0)

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

**9:49 Member states must allocate 30% of their direct payment allocation t..... (8:349 [8:443])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

Member states must allocate 30% of their direct payment allocation to this greening payment.

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

9:59 This is why the young farmer payment (YFP) – a top-up payment added to..... (9:361 [9:490]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

This is why the young farmer payment (YFP) – a top-up payment added to the basic payment - is obligatory in every member state.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

**9:62 Support to young farmers is also provided under the EU's rural devel..... (9:953 [9:1073])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

Support to young farmers is also provided under the EU's rural development programmes, in the form of a start-up aid.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:63 In addition, in countries implementing the basic payment scheme, new..... (9:689 [9:949]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In addition, in countries implementing the basic payment scheme, newly installed young farmers have to be given priority in the allocation of payment entitlements, a necessary procedure for access to the direct payments system in those countries 3 .

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

**9:64 In order to address the specific situation of these farms, member st..... (10:158 [10:379])
- D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020**

In order to address the specific situation of these farms, member states can apply the small farmers scheme (SFS), a simplified direct payment scheme granting a one-off payment to farmers who choose to participate.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:65 Up to 5% of the national allocation for direct payments can be used fo..... (10:1792 [10:1911]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Up to 5% of the national allocation for direct payments can be used for top-up payments to farmers in these ANC areas

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

9:70 In order to receive the full amount of direct payments for which they..... (5:3026 [5:4098]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In order to receive the full amount of direct payments for which they are eligible, farmers have to respect all these other rules.

Failure to do so results in a cut in the level of support. The size of the cut depends on to what extent the farmer is in breach of the rules.

There are two different sets of rules under cross-compliance: • Statutory Management Requirements (SMRs): The co-called SMRs are 13 legislative requirements written into EU law that concern public health, animal and plant health, the identification and registration of animals, environment and animal welfare.

• Good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs): Farmers are obliged to maintain their land in good agricultural and environmental condition. This means, among others things, protecting the soil against erosion, maintaining soil organic matter and soil structure, avoiding the deterioration of habitats, water management and safeguarding landscape features. The exact standards that farmers must meet in these cases are set at the national, not EU, level.

Comment: by buite049

The cross-compliance makes it necessary for farmers to oblige to a set of rules (related to a variety of aims). This slightly constrains it for farmers to 'simply' receive direct payments as the first need to meet these requirements.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

10:8 Voor directe betalingen voor het kalenderjaar 2014 gaat het om €793..... (2:2431 [2:2644]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Voor directe betalingen voor het kalenderjaar 2014 gaat het om €793 miljoen, in 2015 €781 miljoen en verder aflopend tot €732 miljoen voor het kalenderjaar 2019 (EUBudgetjaren 2015, 2016 respectievelijk 2020).

Comment: by buite049

*maar ook constrain, want neemt af
It very enables robust buffer resources, however the funding is decreasing over the time period --> therefore only enabling*

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

10:12 Het nieuwe GLB stapt af van historische betalingen en vergroening is..... (3:1552 [3:1829]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het nieuwe GLB stapt af van historische betalingen en vergroening is een belangrijk element binnen de directe betalingen. Het nieuwe GLB stuurt op de omvorming van op historische referentie gebaseerde directe betalingen naar een gelijke hectarebetaling binnen lidstaten.

Comment: by buite049

It adapts the direct payments so that they are not based on historical references, but is still a systems based on direct payments. --> the robust buffer resources is slightly constrained (therefore not "very enabling") but "enabling"

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

10:32 Het nieuwe wetgevingskader biedt deze gevraagde ruimte voor een verp..... (6:2107 [6:2242]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het nieuwe wetgevingskader biedt deze gevraagde ruimte voor een verplichte extra hectaresteun aan jonge boeren in de eerste pijler.

Comment: by buite049

Robust buffer instrument - it makes use of the direct payment system which is a simple financial mean compensation to support farmers.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

10:38 Vanaf 2019 is er een systeem van een gelijke basispremie van naar ve..... (7:1360 [7:1545]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Vanaf 2019 is er een systeem van een gelijke basispremie van naar verwachting ongeveer €270 per hectare en een vergroeningspremie van ongeveer €120 per hectare voor heel Nederland.

Comment: by buite049

It is a system of basic direct payments --> therefore enabling robustness buffer resources.

It got a score of 4, because it iss an adjusted version of the "historical references' one.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

10:43 Bij het hanteren van de directe betalingen handhaaf ik de huidige onde..... (8:2490 [8:2791]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Bij het hanteren van de directe betalingen handhaaf ik de huidige ondergrens van €500 per ontvanger per jaar. Op deze manier worden kleine en hobbymatige bedrijven uitgesloten, en disproportionele uitvoeringslasten voorkomen. Directe betalingen boven €150.000 per bedrijf worden afgeroomd met 5%.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

10:44 Op de uit te sluiten gronden vinden voor het beheer in bepaalde gevallen..... (9:665 [9:1032]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Op de uit te sluiten gronden vinden voor het beheer in bepaalde gevallen agrarische activiteiten plaats, zoals begrazing door schapen. Voor die activiteiten wil ik via het GLB een graasdierpremie introduceren. Deze graasdierpremie, vormgegeven als een dierpremie, zal gelden voor schapen en (zoog)koeien die op de genoemde niet-subsidiabele gronden grazen.

Comment: by buite049

governmental financial support for grazing livestock in areas that are excluded. It is introduced as a way to compensate for this and to make sure the activity of grazing can continue -- enables robust buffer resource

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

12:66 Met de verlaging van het totale beschikbare GLB-budget voor Nederland..... (14:2082 [14:2326]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Met de verlaging van het totale beschikbare GLB-budget voor Nederland valt een deel van de directe inkomenssteun, onder andere voor zetmeelaardappelen, weg. In het bijzonder voor akkerbouwers in de Veenkoloniën kan dit grote gevolgen hebben.

Comment: by buite049

| *Valt weg = constraint*

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:1 Degressivity and capping: despite the Council attempt to make degressi..... (33:791 [33:1029]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Degressivity and capping: despite the Council attempt to make degressivity a voluntary instrument, the progressive reduction of large direct payments will be mandatory in all Member States, while “capping” remains a voluntary measure.

Comment: by buite049

| *Constraints buffer resources The Direct payments are still present (the buffer resource), however this instruments restricts the growth of large direct payments and thus constraining the continuation of (perverse) direct payments (by a small amount) Capping is voluntary. --> slightly constraints robustness*

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:4 Greening: 30 % of the national envelope for direct payments is to be e..... (33:1032 [33:1185]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Greening: 30 % of the national envelope for direct payments is to be earmarked for payments linked to the production of environmental benefits by farms.

Comment: by buite049

| *a financial compensation for the greening measures. But is is used for other things than the main functionality of the farms --> fairly enabling robustness buffer resource.*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:7 Reserve for crises in the agricultural sector: within Heading 2 of the..... (33:3209 [33:3553]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Reserve for crises in the agricultural sector: within Heading 2 of the MFF, a crisis reserve was created to provide support in the event of crises affecting the agricultural sector. EUR 2 800 million have been allocated to the reserve using resources raised through a reduction of direct payments exceeding EUR 2 000 by means of the financial

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:11 Member States that do not transfer funds from Pillar I to Pillar II ma..... (46:601 [46:771]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States that do not transfer funds from Pillar I to Pillar II may make transfers in the opposite direction, shifting up to 15 % of funds from Pillar II to Pillar I.

Comment: by buite049

*The transfer is also possible in the opposite direction --> slightly enables flexibility (2)
There will then be extra funding available for direct payment scheme --> buffer resource
--> slightly enables robustness (2)*

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:20 Even potential beneficiaries who do not qualify as 'active farmers' (b..... (47:2279 [47:2625]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Even potential beneficiaries who do not qualify as 'active farmers' (because they are on the 'black list' or because agricultural activities form only a marginal part of their overall economic activity and/or are not their principal activity) are nevertheless entitled to receive direct payments if these do not exceed EUR 5 000 Euro per year.

Comment: by buite049

*a smaller financial compensation for non 'active farmers' (black list or agriculture as secondary task).
Also a bit constraining protection status quo, as other people than active farmers can receive funding.*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:23 The basic payment is nothing more than a scaled-down version of what w..... (48:205 [48:409]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The basic payment is nothing more than a scaled-down version of what was the SPS in the pre-2015 CAP. Member States using the SAPS are allowed to continue using it until the end of 2020, at the latest.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:28 In order to reduce the risk of unspent funds, Member States are allowe..... (49:3027 [49:3361]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In order to reduce the risk of unspent funds, Member States are allowed to increase the ceiling for the basic payment by a maximum of 3 % of the national ceiling (after deduction of the ceiling for the 'green payments'), provided that the payments actually paid do not exceed the national ceiling, net of the amount of degressivity.

Comment: by buite049

| *Increasing direct payments to reduce the risk of unspent funds --> enables robustness*

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:37 Croatia will continue to enjoy the special national de-mining reserve..... (51:867 [51:1108]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Croatia will continue to enjoy the special national de-mining reserve established in Regulation (EC) 73/2009, the aim of which is to allocate payment entitlements to farmers with de-mined land back to being used for agricultural activities,

Comment: by buite049

| *not specifically relevant for the Dutch case = not clear (0)*

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:38 In the first year of implementation of the basic payment scheme, Membe..... (51:1233 [51:1647]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In the first year of implementation of the basic payment scheme, Member States shall establish a national or regional reserve with a deduction of the ceiling for the basic payment no higher than 3 %. The reserve shall primarily be used to allocate payment entitlements to young farmers and new farmers. If the reserve is insufficient to address these needs, the percentage of deduction may be higher than 3 %.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:40 A fixed percentage (30 %) of the national ceiling for direct payments..... (52:248 [52:572]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

A fixed percentage (30 %) of the national ceiling for direct payments is allocated to 'green' payments. The 'green payment' takes the form of an annual payment per hectare, calculated by dividing the financial resources allocated to these payments by the number of eligible hectares (referred to below as "flat payment").

Comment: by buite049

financial compensation for green measures.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:48 Direct payments for young farmers are mandatory payments that compleme..... (53:2569 [53:2903]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Direct payments for young farmers are mandatory payments that complement the start-up aid that may be granted to young farmers as part of Pillar II. These payments are financed by up to 2 % of the national ceiling for direct payments and are granted annually to young farmers entitled to receive the basic payment (or under SAPS).

Comment: by buite049

Financial compensation for young farmers. The instrument stays the same: support through payments.

The goals is perhaps long term as it focus is on the new generation --> but does it really transform the situation

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:58 Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints ar..... (55:1068 [55:1363]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints are a voluntary component of the direct payments, justified by the goal of guaranteeing the presence of farmers and farming in these areas by providing support that is additional to that foreseen in rural development policies.

Comment: by buite049

The direct payments for areas with natural constraints is just financial support / compensation for the farmers. The goal is to guarantee the presence of farmers and farming in those areas; thus to keep things as they are --> protecting status quo.

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:62 The payment takes the form of an annual payment per hectare – or per h..... (56:305 [56:607]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The payment takes the form of an annual payment per hectare – or per head, in the case of livestock; because the aim is to maintain the current level of production (i.e. the support provided should not result in increased production), payments are limited to a maximum number of hectares and heads.

3 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:64 Member States may increase this percentage to up to 100 %, thereby in..... (58:947 [58:1106]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may increase this percentage to up to 100 %, thereby introducing a de facto EUR 150,000 threshold for the degressivity ‘cap’ on basic payments.

Comment: by buite049

*may introduce a 150,000 euro treshold for direct payments. This means that big receivers can be constraint in their direct payments. This constraints financial compensations for big farms. constraining buffer resources
However it is voluntary, meaning that a member state can decide themselves it they want to do this or not. = flexibility*

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:67 The small farms scheme is a simplified scheme that aims to reduce the..... (56:2536 [56:2715]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The small farms scheme is a simplified scheme that aims to reduce the bureaucratic burden, both for the beneficiaries and for the public sector, when small payments are involved.

Comment: by buite049

small farmers scheme is a buffer resource for farmers. It is however made with the idea to make it more easier for small farmers to obtain a direct payment - it is therefore focused on the goal of providing small farms with financial support instead of the way how to do it. Flexibility in how grants can be provided

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:72 Twelve countries (Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Ireland, Greece, Cyprus,..... (59:906 [59:1135]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Twelve countries (Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Ireland, Greece, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Austria, England, Wales and Northern Ireland) maintained a high share of the national ceiling on the basic payment/SAPS (above 60 %).

Comment: by buite049

High share of national ceiling is used for direct payments (or in other words: financial compensation).

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:76 Eight out of these twelve countries (Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Cypru..... (59:1608 [59:1920]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Eight out of these twelve countries (Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Cyprus, Netherlands, Austria, England and Wales) will implement a flat-rate payment, which means that a high portion of the national ceiling will be distributed among all the beneficiaries, who will ultimately receive the same unit value payment

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:77 With regards to the support for young farmers (mandatory in Pillar I i..... (65:2111 [65:2290]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

With regards to the support for young farmers (mandatory in Pillar I in addition to the basic payment), 14 Member States chose to allocate the maximum percentage of support (2 %).

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands chose to allocate the maximum percentage of support (2%). Financial compensation for young farmers = buffer resource. However it is meant for young farmers, for a new generation, to help them with farming (long term goal).

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:98 The implementation of the small farmers scheme (94:1614 [94:1659]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The implementation of the small farmers scheme

Comment: by buite049

*The Netherlands did not implement the small farmers scheme --> There is thus not alternative way of providing direct payments to small farmers - a seperate buffer resource. However this means that the regular direct payment scheme is in place as a buffer resource --> not clear
However, this also meant that non of the small farms can opt for this option to support their existing agricultural structure*

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:104 (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States (87:53:514-87:540:578) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Content

Netherlands	2%	No	the farmer has declared, but no more than 90 Applying art. 50.8 The annual payment is calculated as 25% of the national average payment per hectare multiplied by number of payment entitlements that the farmer has activated, but no more than 90
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Comment: by buite049

the Netherlands reserves 2% of the national ceiling (the maximum percentage allowed) for the implementation of the payment for young farmers. They did not set any additional criteria as regards appropriate skill or training requirements for young farmers to apply.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

15:107 The countries to suffer the most pronounced cuts – above 15 % – in th..... (43:853 [43:1047]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The countries to suffer the most pronounced cuts – above 15 % – in their allocations for direct payments are Belgium (-17.8 %), Denmark (-16.1 %), Italy (-15.2 %) and the Netherlands (-18.4 %)

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the direct payments (buffer resources) in the Netherlands

2 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

15:112 Farms located in areas covered by the Habitat, Water and Bird directiv..... (52:1478 [52:1816]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Farms located in areas covered by the Habitat, Water and Bird directives are entitled to receive 'green payments', provided that they comply with green practices compatible with the objectives of the relevant directive. Land devoted to organic agriculture is by default assumed to fulfil the conditions to receive the 'green payment'.

Comment: by buite049

*Flexible instruments as different conditions are in place for different cases / context. There is therefore some flexibility in the measure for farmers that are already participate in green / environmental measures --> enables flexibility
This still regards financial compensation --> buffer resource*

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments / L. Adaptability_5

17:15 Income support . Direct payments provide support to farm income and..... (7:774 [7:975]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Income support . Direct payments provide support to farm income and remunerate farmers for delivering public goods not normally paid for by the markets, such as taking care of the countryside.

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5

18:10 • financiële ondersteuning; (7:1920 [7:1946]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

- financiële ondersteuning;

Comment: by buite049

financial support is an instrument to make sure that goals are reach. However, unclear how and for what this financial support is used.

2 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments

18:59 5) Ondersteunen van projectinitiatieven: binnen het beschikbare budg..... (11:2234 [11:2467]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

5) Ondersteunen van projectinitiatieven: binnen het beschikbare budget wordt ruimte gecreëerd voor financiële ondersteuning van initiatieven en projecten.

Voorwaarde is dat zij bijdragen aan de hierboven genoemde doelstelling.

Comment: by buite049

*Just financial support for the promotion of organic farming. It can thus just be regarded as a buffer resource / financial compensation.
however, the financial support is used for projects that aim for a new (innovative) way of farming, and therefore not discouraging innovation.
Perhaps the instrument is therefore adapts variety*

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

Robust_other_risk_management_goals

13 Quotations:

2:13 Some outdated commodity aid schemes will also be abolished, and ot..... (5:2891 [5:2984]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Some outdated commodity aid schemes will also be abolished, and other schemes modernised.

Comment: by buite049

*abolishment means that risk management / aid schemes will be constrained
modernised means that risk management / aid schemes will be in place*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

2:18 At the same time the new CAP also offers more responsive safety net..... (6:1064 [6:1358]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

At the same time the new CAP also offers more responsive safety net measures and strengthens the EU's capacity for crisis management. This will be achieved by more efficient market measures to deal with potential threats of market disturbances and more flexible exceptional measures.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

2:22 Farmers also have to adapt to challenges stemming from changes to th..... (6:2416 [6:2655]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Farmers also have to adapt to challenges stemming from changes to the climate by pursuing climate change mitigation and adaptation actions (e.g. by developing greater resilience to disasters such as flooding, drought and fire).

Comment: by buite049

*The farming system needs to adapt to these challenges through mitigation and adaptation = adaptation variety.
But it is also a goal for risk management as the adaptation is necessary to deal with shocks and stresses = robustness risk management*

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals / J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:40 supporting farm risk management; (17:370 [17:402]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

supporting farm risk management;

Comment: by buite049

| *supporting risk management - thus not applying it or producing it. --> fairly enabling.*

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

6:52 enhancing accessibility to, use and quality of information and communi..... (17:1630 [17:1742]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

enhancing accessibility to, use and quality of information and communication, technologies (ICT) in rural areas

Comment: by buite049

| *Better accessibility to information for inhabitants of rural areas*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

8:31 to improve the market orientation of EU agriculture in light of incr..... (5:1393 [5:1756]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

to improve the market orientation of EU agriculture in light of increased competition on world markets, while providing an effective safety net for farmers in the context of external uncertainties (together with direct payments and options for risk management under rural development). The existing systems of public intervention and private storage aid

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

8:32 In order to improve farmers' negotiating position in the food chain, t..... (5:3180 [5:3828]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to improve farmers' negotiating position in the food chain, the Commission is looking for a better organisation of the sectors with a few limited derogations to EU competition law. Rules related to the recognition of Producer Organisations (POs) and inter-branch organisations are now covering all sectors – with further options for establishing such organisations now transferred to Rural Development funding (see below).

Furthermore, the possibility for farmers to collectively negotiate contracts for the supply of olive oil, beef, cereals and certain other arable crops is foreseen under certain conditions and safeguards.

Comment: by buite049

improving the position of farmers in negotiations to make sure that they are better able to deal with the economic market related to food production --> no real risk management, but improves the robustness for farmers --> slightly enabling robustness

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

9:12 Farmers also have to cope with the special characteristics of agricu..... (3:389 [3:1008]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Farmers also have to cope with the special characteristics of agricultural commodity markets. Everybody needs food to survive, but demand does not change significantly if prices fall, as might be the case with other products.

This means that farmers cannot rely on simply selling more of their output to compensate for lower prices. In addition, food production processes are long: for example, it takes two years for a dairy cow to reach the stage where it produces milk. These factors can have a significant impact on farmers' incomes, and yet they have virtually no control over them.

Comment: by buite049

*Not really a goal, but more the reason why the CAP is implemented. However, one could argue that the CAP had as goal to reduce these problems.
Need to be able to overcome short disturbances of markets.
It legitimises the EU's influence through safety nets or market intervention. To help manage risks for farmers.*

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

10:68 Weersextremen kunnen zeer ingrijpende inkomensgevolgen hebben voor a..... (12:1260 [12:1855]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Weersextremen kunnen zeer ingrijpende inkomensgevolgen hebben voor agrarische ondernemers. Binnen POP3 ga ik het ondersteunen van een brede weersverzekering continueren, zoals nu vormgegeven binnen artikel 68 in de eerste pijler van het GLB. De agrarische ondernemer neemt zelf verantwoordelijkheid door al dan niet te kiezen voor een brede weersverzekering.

Het betreft een privaat verzekeringsinstrument dat wordt ondersteund door een subsidiepercentage op de verzekeringspremie. Het doel van deze steun is om uiteindelijk te komen tot een instrument dat in de markt functioneert.

Comment: by buite049

To continue the support for extreme weather insurrances for farmers --> very enabling other modes of risk management.

It is focused on coping with (short term) shocks and provides some form of a safety net for farmers.

It is then the decision of the farmer him/herself if they want to have an insurance.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

17:6 In order to ensure that farmers can operate efficiently and that the..... (4:897 [4:1498]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

In order to ensure that farmers can operate efficiently and that these upstream and downstream sectors remain modern and productive, they need ready access to the latest information on agricultural issues, farming methods and market developments. This is why the CAP is improving access to high-speed technologies in rural areas and, by so doing, is contributing to one of the Commission's top 10 priorities — a connected digital single market. During the period 2014-2020 the policy is expected to provide improved internet services and infrastructure to 18 million rural citizens

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to provide the farmers with information with they can use to maintain and increase their levels of output better.

Accessibility of data to individuals.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

17:13 A policy set at the European level ensures common rules in a single..... (6:1570 [6:1918]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

A policy set at the European level ensures common rules in a single market, addresses market volatility where needed, safeguards the progress made in recent reforms towards increased competitiveness of European agriculture and provides for a common trade policy allowing the EU to negotiate as one, vis-à-vis our global trading partners.

Comment: by buite049

needed to produce a single way of dealing with market related problems and to have a shared negotiation position instead of multiple, competing policies and positions; also to make sure that every EU country can maintain the desired levels of output in the agricultural sector --> risk management

2 Codes:

G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals / K. Adaptability_4

17:45 the creation of mutual funds and insurance schemes to allow farmers..... (13:148 [13:284]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

the creation of mutual funds and insurance schemes to allow farmers to respond better to market instability or fast-falling prices.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

17:46 contractual relationships throughout the food chain; (13:91 [13:143]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

contractual relationships throughout the food chain;

Comment: by buite049

contractual relationships between supply chains provides a more secure way of selling food products and a more stable income. --> robustness - slightly enabling

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals

Robust_other risk management_instruments

25 Quotations:

2:16 Measures to facilitate producer cooperation under both pillars of t..... (5:2986 [5:3205]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Measures to facilitate producer cooperation under both pillars of the CAP should also boost the competitiveness of farming by reducing costs, improving access to credit and adding value to the primary sector.

Comment: by buite049

The cooperation can be seen as a way to keep producing the desired levels of output, while the risks/costs that come with this production process can be shared with others (reducing individual risks).

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

2:17 At the same time the new CAP also offers more responsive safety net..... (6:1064 [6:1260]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

At the same time the new CAP also offers more responsive safety net measures and strengthens the EU's capacity for crisis management. This will be achieved by more efficient market measures

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

2:19 A new crisis reserve (of EUR 400 million per year in 2011 prices) is..... (6:1363 [6:1631]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

A new crisis reserve (of EUR 400 million per year in 2011 prices) is established to secure the financial resources needed in case of crisis, through deductions from direct payments, with unused amounts reimbursed to farmers in the consecutive budget years.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

2:20 In addition, the second pillar offers a new risk-management toolkit..... (6:2034 [6:2229]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

In addition, the second pillar offers a new risk-management toolkit including insurance schemes for crops, animals and plants, as well as mutual funds and an income stabilisation tool.

Comment: by buite049

very enables other risk management tools by offering a risk-management toolkit with different options

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

3:54 Collectieve inkoop diensten en producten (18:1088 [18:1129]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Collectieve inkoop diensten en producten

Comment: by buite049

Collective buying of services and products --> a way of sharing the costs and therefore a way of managing the risks.

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

3:56 Aanleg van ICT-infrastructuur voor het kunnen toepassen van innovati..... (18:490 [18:596]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Aanleg van ICT-infrastructuur voor het kunnen toepassen van innovatieve technieken op het boerenbedrijf

Comment: by buite049

*The ICT-infrastructure is a mean to make experimentation possible. It is a resource for the experiments.
Not really sure if this is "transformation"
It actually feels more as robustness. The ITC makes it beter possible to access data and to continue the current practices on the farms*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

4:14 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:68:581-3:480:602) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

• Voorzetting brede weersverzekering	2,2	5,8	8,0
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2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

6:56 M5.1 Support for investments in preventive actions aimed at reducing..... (18:971 [18:1140]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M5.1 Support for investments in preventive actions aimed at reducing the consequences of probable natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events

Comment: by buite049

| *Support for financial investments, but clearly focused on risk management*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

6:57 M5.2 Support for investments for the restoration of agricultural lan..... (18:1143 [18:1322]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M5.2 Support for investments for the restoration of agricultural land and production potential damaged by natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events

Comment: by buite049

| *Support for financial investments, but clearly focused on risk management*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

6:64 M7.3 Support for broadband infrastructure, including its creation,..... (18:2841 [18:3036]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.3 Support for broadband infrastructure, including its creation, improvement and expansion, passive broadband infrastructure and provision of access to broadband and public e-government

Comment: by buite049

| *This measure provides better data access for farmers.*

2 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

6:76 M8.3 Support for prevention of damage to forests from forest fires a..... (19:1908 [19:2023]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.3 Support for prevention of damage to forests from forest fires and natural disasters and catastrophic events

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

6:77 M8.4 Support for restoration of damage to forests from forest fires..... (19:2432 [19:2549]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.4 Support for restoration of damage to forests from forest fires and natural disasters and catastrophic events

2 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

7:34 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:81:406-19:463:419) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

brede weersverzekering			2,1	5,6	-	7,7
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2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

8:26 Moreover, new safeguard clauses are introduced for all sectors to enable..... (5:2252 [5:2673]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Moreover, new safeguard clauses are introduced for all sectors to enable the Commission to take emergency measures to respond to general market disturbances – such as the measures taken during the e-coli crisis in May-July 2011. These measures will be funded from a Crisis Reserve financed by annually reducing direct payments. Funds not used for crisis measures will be returned to farmers in the following year.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

8:30 The existing systems of public intervention and private storage aid are..... (5:1689 [5:1871]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

The existing systems of public intervention and private storage aid are revised to be more responsive and more efficient, for example with technical adjustments for beef and dairy.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

8:33 Crisis reserve : A crisis reserve will be created every year for an amount of €400 million (in 2011 prices) by application of financial discipline. If the amount is not used for a crisis it will be reimbursed to farmers as direct payments in the following year. (8:1386 [8:1654]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Crisis reserve : A crisis reserve will be created every year for an amount of €400 million (in 2011 prices) by application of financial discipline. If the amount is not used for a crisis it will be reimbursed to farmers as direct payments in the following year.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

8:44 Risk management toolkit: Insurance & mutual funds – for crop & weather..... (7:1414 [7:1717]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Risk management toolkit: Insurance & mutual funds – for crop & weather insurance, animal disease [currently available under Article 68 in the 1st Pillar] - extended to include income stabilisation option (which would allow a pay-out (up to 70% of losses) from a mutual fund if income drops by 30%);

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

8:55 In case of severe imbalance in the market, the Commission may also a..... (5:2674 [5:2995]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In case of severe imbalance in the market, the Commission may also authorise producer organisations or inter branch organisations, respecting specific safeguards, to take certain temporary measures collectively (for example market withdrawal or storage by private operators) to stabilise the sector concerned.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

9:4 market measures, for example to combat a sudden drop in prices, (1:767 [1:831]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

market measures, for example to combat a sudden drop in prices,

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

9:66 Market measures are used if normal market forces fail - for example,..... (11:1371 [11:1767]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Market measures are used if normal market forces fail - for example, if there is a sudden drop in demand because of a health scare or a fall in prices because of a temporary oversupply on the market. In such cases, the European Commission can activate market support measures – financing for a particular affected sector that on average accounts for around 5% of overall EU farm spending

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

10:9 De uitgaven in het kader van het markt- en prijsbeleid kennen geen p..... (2:2645 [2:2895]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De uitgaven in het kader van het markt- en prijsbeleid kennen geen plafond, maar afgaande op de betalingen over 2012 en rekening houdend met de afgeslankte interventie maatregelen bedraagt de raming voor 2014 voor Nederland maximaal €150 miljoen.

Comment: by buite049

market- and price policy = risk management (interference when economic market is not beneficial for a product). These are the financial means the netherlands presumably will have for these measures.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

10:69 Ik wil hierbij gebruik maken van ongeveer €2 miljoen aan EU-cofinanc..... (12:1857 [12:1985]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik wil hierbij gebruik maken van ongeveer €2 miljoen aan EU-cofinanciering in POP3 aangevuld met €7 miljoen rijksmiddelen.

Comment: by buite049

money available for an extreme weather insurance

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

17:16 Market measures . The European Commission can take measures to deal..... (7:978 [7:1215]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Market measures . The European Commission can take measures to deal with difficult market situations such as a sudden drop in demand due to a health scare, or a fall in prices as a result of a temporary oversupply on the market.

2 Codes:

F. Robustness_5 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

17:42 other means are also available. These include financial guarantee sc..... (12:523 [12:616]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

other means are also available. These include financial guarantee schemes and insurance.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

17:48 Risk management and marketing tools can improve farmers' position in..... (13:285 [13:455]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

Risk management and marketing tools can improve farmers' position in the food chain. The 2013 reform provides financial support to farmers who wish to use such tools

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / H. Robust_other risk management_instruments

Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals

16 Quotations:

3:11 Het nieuwe GLB gaat per 2015 van start. Nederland kiest daarbij voor..... (8:25 [8:273]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Het nieuwe GLB gaat per 2015 van start.

Nederland kiest daarbij voor een geleidelijke invoering van inkomstenstoeslagen naar een zogenaamde 'flat rate' tot 2020. Voor boeren in de Veenkoloniën betekent dit een forse teruggang in hun inkomen.

Comment: by buite049

The decision to change the way direct payments are calculated has a major effect on the income of the farmers. This thus constraints the buffer resources for the farmers in the veenkoloniën.

Geleidelijk - gradually changing the system from 2015 - 2020

4 Codes:

B. Robustness_1 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

3:26 De in 2013 gestarte projecten hebben alle een looptijd tot uiterli..... (13:609 [13:692]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

De in 2013 gestarte projecten hebben alle een looptijd tot uiterlijk medio 2015.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / J. Adaptability_3

3:96 nvesteren in Duurzame Aardappelrassen en de projectexperimenten op..... (13:934 [13:1581]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

nvesteren in Duurzame Aardappelrassen en de projectexperimenten op het gebied van de Vergroening. Het vervolg van deze projecten is inmiddels ondergebracht bij de (nieuwe) projectinitiatieven die verderop bij de projecten zijn beschreven. Daarnaast is de verwachting dat een aantal veelbelovende initiatieven nog een verlenging nodig heeft om de kansrijkheid en/of draagvlak verder te concretiseren. Inschatting is dat het gaat om een twintigtal projectinitiatieven.

Begin 2015 zal op basis van monitoring worden bepaald of een eventueel vervolg van de startprojecten relevant is voor de verdere innovatieontwikkeling.

Comment: by buite049

...het vervolg van deze projecten is inmiddels ondergebracht bij de (nieuwe) projectinitiatieven die verderop bij de projecten zijn beschreven. ---> some projects have the change to get extended within (new) projectinitiatives. These projects will therefore continue over a longer period of time (middle-to-long). The idea is thus that the projects regarding innovation can continue

1 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals

6:2 Firstly, in the decisions relating to direct payments, the main cons..... (51:207 [51:410]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Firstly, in the decisions relating to direct payments, the main consideration was to make the reduction of payments a smooth transition to the sectors that would undergo significant changes in support

Comment: by buite049

a smooth transition for the sectors that benefit highly from the old direct payment system. The smooth transition meant that the Dutch government had decided to gradually introduce the new direct payment scheme. Not based on historical references but on Ha. Still, the system of direct payments will stay in place.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

7:18 Met een zo geleidelijk mogelijke (lineaire) overgang zorg ik dat de s..... (8:330 [8:463]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Met een zo geleidelijk mogelijke (lineaire) overgang zorg ik dat de sectoren zich tot 2019 kunnen aanpassen aan de nieuwe situatie.

Comment: by buite049

Very enabling middle to long term as it is intentionally introduced to provide farmers a bit more time to cope with changes

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / L. Adaptability_5

7:28 Met de gekozen aanpak om op een zo geleidelijk mogelijke wijze naar e..... (12:1897 [12:2011]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Met de gekozen aanpak om op een zo geleidelijk mogelijke wijze naar een gelijke hectarebetaling per 2019 te gaan,

Comment: by buite049

a gradual change untill 2019. Middle-to-long term goal

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / L. Adaptability_5

9:45 All entitlements allocated to a farmer have the same value, but diff..... (7:801 [7:1540]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

All entitlements allocated to a farmer have the same value, but differences in the value of entitlements may exist between farmers, if a member state opted for such an approach. In that case, the past level of direct payments to individual farmers was taken into account (or the value of the entitlements they possessed under the previous direct payments regime) in order to avoid too abrupt disruptions in their level of support. However, since one of the objectives of the new system is to move away from these historical references, the member states that take this approach have agreed to progressively reduce the differences in the values of entitlements and bring these values to (or closer to) the average by 2019

Comment: by buite049

*protection of the status quo = the disruption of the level of support needs to be done progressively + past level of direct payments were taken into account.
Also a bit constraining the protection of status quo = the direct payments are moving away from historical references.*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:35 k vind het belangrijk dat de overgang naar het systeem van gelijke h..... (7:926 [7:1268]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

k vind het belangrijk dat de overgang naar het systeem van gelijke hectarebetalingen geleidelijk en voorspelbaar verloopt, zodat bedrijven zich kunnen voorbereiden en aanpassen. Bij deze geleidelijke overgang is het startpunt de waarde van de toeslagrechten die een landbouwer in 2014 bezit (inclusief eventueel verhuurde rechten).

Comment: by buite049

geleidelijke overgang --> geeft een signaal dat het over een middel-lange periode gaat plaatsvinden

This statement clearly shows the intention to gradually introduce the new direct payments over a middle-to-long -term period in order for farmers to adjust themselves -->

Very enabling adaptation midle to long term

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / L. Adaptability_5

10:37 Een zo geleidelijk mogelijke (lineaire) overgang naar de gelijke hec..... (7:1549 [7:1748]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Een zo geleidelijk mogelijke (lineaire) overgang naar de gelijke hectarebetaling en gelijke vergroeningspremie per hectare, waarbij de vergroeningspremie in de overgangsfase bedrijfsafhankelijk is

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / L. Adaptability_5

10:40 Omdat ik de overgangperiode maximaal geleidelijk invul, met een ove..... (7:2355 [7:2603]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Omdat ik de overgangperiode maximaal geleidelijk invul, met een overgangperiode tot 2019, heb ik er alle vertrouwen in dat de sectoren die per saldo minder gaan ontvangen robuust genoeg zijn om zich aan de GLB-hervormingen aan te passen.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / L. Adaptability_5

12:23 Wij willen ons in het beleid voor duurzame landbouw concentreren op de..... (8:1433 [8:1701]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen ons in het beleid voor duurzame landbouw concentreren op de vergroening van de landbouw, in relatie tot innovaties die plaats (kunnen) vinden en op de omschakeling van de nu gangbare landbouw naar duurzame(re) vormen van akkerbouw, tuinbouw en veeteelt.

Comment: by buite049

Adaptability as the goal is aiming to change the production strategies of the farms into a more sustainable one.

Middle-to-long-term as it is the goal of this sustainable agriculture programme.

This goal enables adaptability

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

12:44 Wij willen daarom bijvoorbeeld de ontwikkeling van nieuwe, diervrien..... (10:3678 [11:35]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen daarom bijvoorbeeld de ontwikkeling van nieuwe, diervriendelijke stalconcepten en de omschakeling naar minder intensieve veehouderij in de

11 komende jaren verder stimuleren

Comment: by buite049

Komende jaren = middle-to-long-term

*to stimulate the change towards less intensive livestock farming
adapt*

*However it is about livestock --> not relevant for the arable farming of the dutch case
study --> Not clear*

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals

12:52 Belangrijke uitdagingen voor de komende jaren zijn de vermindering v..... (11:3140 [11:3345]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Belangrijke uitdagingen voor de komende jaren zijn de vermindering van de CO₂-uitstoot door bedrijven en waar nodig en mogelijk aanpassing van de bedrijfsvoering aan veranderende klimaatomstandigheden.

Comment: by buite049

Important challenges FOR THE COMING YEARS are to reduce co2 emissions by farmers and where necessary adapting the farming practices to changing climate circumstances.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

12:61 Veel van de relaties kunnen leiden tot nieuwe mogelijkheden op het geb..... (13:827 [13:1378]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Veel van de relaties kunnen leiden tot nieuwe mogelijkheden op het gebied van verduurzaming van de landbouw, vooral als het gaat over het leggen van een nauwere relatie met de directe omgeving van een boerenbedrijf. De kwaliteitssprongen naar duurzaamheid zijn in dit kader minder technisch innovatief van aard en liggen meer op het terrein van netwerkvorming en nieuwe activiteiten (verbreding).

In het kader van de verbrede blik op de landbouw, is het belangrijk om in de komende jaren deze relaties verder te onderzoeken en te versterken

Comment: by buite049

de komende jaren = the coming years.

The goal is to further investigate the coming years the interaction between the agricultural policy field and other policy fields to ensure further sustainability, slightly enabling adaptability --> the investigation can lead to interessting insights, but it is not sure if it would indeed lead to groundbreaking integration and increasing sustainability.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / I. Adaptability_2

18:29 Doel is om in de collegeperiode 2015-2019 het areaal biologische lan..... (10:458 [10:992]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Doel is om in de collegeperiode 2015-2019 het areaal biologische landbouw in de provincie te laten groeien. In 2015 werd in de provincie 4.130 ha biologisch geteeld en was er 87 ha in omschakeling van gangbaar naar biologisch (info: P. Brul, 1 april 2016). Het omschakelen van gangbare landbouw naar biologische landbouw is vaak een langdurig proces waarin een ondernemer veel afwegingen moet maken om tot de

daadwerkelijke keuze te komen. Op basis van de huidige inzichten is een groei van 1.000 ha tot 2020 reëel.

Comment: by buite049

goal of increasing organic farming in 2020 --> to adapt the situation in a time period --> socre 4

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

18:38 Doel voor de periode tot 2020 is boeren in de provincie Groningen te..... (12:1372 [12:1659]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Doel voor de periode tot 2020 is boeren in de provincie Groningen te stimuleren om concrete maatregelen in te zetten om te komen tot Natuurinclusieve Landbouw. Daarbij is van belang dat de maatregelen landbouweconomisch inpasbaar en als zodanig herkenbaar voor de landbouw zijn.

2 Codes:

I. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_goals / K. Adaptability_4

Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

14 Quotations:

3:17 Per twee jaar vindt een evaluatie plaats waarmee het Innovatieprogra..... (9:1724 [9:1854]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Per twee jaar vindt een evaluatie plaats waarmee het Innovatieprogramma zal worden geactualiseerd en indien nodig aangescherpt.

Comment: by buite049

Per two years there is a moment of monitoring to evaluate the programme. The information will be used to update the programme.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

3:30 In 2014 wordt daarom een monitoringssysteem ontwikkeld en wordt ge..... (13:1987 [13:2233]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

In 2014 wordt daarom een monitoringssysteem ontwikkeld en wordt gestart met het monitoren van de lopende projecten. Deze monitoring loopt door tot 2020 waarmee ook inzichtelijk wordt gemaakt of de gestelde doelen per 2020 behaald worden.

Comment: by buite049

The monitoring is used in projects in which different knowledge institutes are brought together. The monitoring must lead to new insights and need to show if objectives are met.

The monitoring will take place over a longer period of time.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

3:66 Verruiming Vruchtwisseling: met dit praktijkexperiment worden de eff..... (24:1510 [24:1721]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Verruiming Vruchtwisseling: met dit praktijkexperiment worden de effecten van een ruimere vruchtwisseling op de bodemgezondheid van veenkoloniale gronden over een periode van 4-5 jaar in kaart gebracht.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

6:15 Full internal convergence by 2019; (51:3038 [51:3071]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Full internal convergence by 2019;

Comment: by buite049

gradually changing the direct payment system to let the farmers prepare themselves for the change that comes in 2019. The goal is thus to make sure that '(knel)sectors' are able to cope with this; that they are still able to maintain their desired levels of outputs while the economic support is changed.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

7:13 Om de effecten te kunnen meten en evalueren heb ik Alterra gevraagd e..... (7:1103 [7:1654]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Om de effecten te kunnen meten en evalueren heb ik Alterra gevraagd een monitoringssystematiek te ontwikkelen en als referentie in 2014 reeds een nulmeting uit te voeren. Hiermee kunnen de veranderingen vanaf introductie van de vergroening in 2015 worden bijgehouden en voor de Nederlandse situatie geëvalueerd. Alterra zal de

monitoringmethodiek opzetten langs de lijnen van het Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF) zoals vastgesteld door de Europese Commissie en daaraan een aantal specifieke indicatoren voor Nederland toevoegen.

Comment: by buite049

A monitoring system used to measure the effects of the greening. the monitoring is done from 2014/15 until 2020. It is not mentioned what the goal is of the monitoring ? --> used to change policies or measures? is it used to adapt? Therefore a lower score is given (score 2).

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

7:44 Omdat equivalente pakketten in de Europese kaders als ANB-pakket zull..... (4:1227 [4:1362]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Omdat equivalente pakketten in de Europese kaders als ANB-pakket zullen worden gezien, worden zij voor vijf tot zeven jaar aangegaan.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / L. Adaptability_5

8:13 In order to encourage generational renewal, the Basic Payment awarde..... (2:3077 [2:3297]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to encourage generational renewal, the Basic Payment awarded to new entrant Young Farmers (no more than 40 years of age) should be topped up by an additional payment available for a period of maximum 5 years

Comment: by buite049

period of maximum of 5 years - adaptability middle to long term - however the tool is mostly to make sure the farm system can continue through introducing benefits for younger farmers --> therefore lower score on adaptability --> score 2 Enables an extra buffer resource for young farmers --> score5

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

8:34 Monitoring & Evaluation of the CAP: The Commission will present a repo..... (8:2081 [8:2392]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Monitoring & Evaluation of the CAP: The Commission will present a report before the end of 2018 – and every 4 years thereafter – on the performance of the CAP with respect to its main objectives – viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources, and balanced territorial development.

Comment: by buite049

The idea of monitoring and evaluating the CAP for a middle term period of 4 years each. It is meant to make the performance of the CAP visible with respect to the main objectives. But it is not clear how the results will be used / which purpose they serve / will it be used to adapt? --> slightly enabling

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

8:49 Basic services and village renewal: Investments in broadband infrastru..... (7:2985 [7:3175]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Basic services and village renewal: Investments in broadband infrastructure and renewable energy can go beyond small-scale, relocation of activities / conversion of buildings now covered;

Comment: by buite049

quite big structural changes that will be around for a longer period to improve the rural area.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / J. Adaptability_3

9:60 £It is granted for a maximum of five years from the moment a young far..... (9:491 [9:606]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

£It is granted for a maximum of five years from the moment a young farmer takes over as the head of a farm holding.

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

10:10 Voor het plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma (POP3) is voor de periode 2..... (3:127 [3:347]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Voor het plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma (POP3) is voor de periode 2014- 2020 voor Nederland €607 miljoen (per jaar circa €85 miljoen) beschikbaar uit het Europees Landbouwfonds voor Plattelandontwikkeling (ELFPO).

Comment: by buite049

The POP3 finances (rural development programme) for the periode of 2014-2020 (6 years).

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

15:27 Under the ‘full convergence in 2019, at the latest’ option, the unifor..... (49:989 [49:1187]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Under the ‘full convergence in 2019, at the latest’ option, the uniform unit value of the basic payment will be introduced progressively in equal steps and will be in place by 2019, at the latest.

Comment: by buite049

progressively adapting the basic payments

1 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments

15:51 The payment is granted for a maximum period of five years (less than t..... (54:617 [54:806]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The payment is granted for a maximum period of five years (less than that if the farmer had become head of the holding before the application to receive the payment for young farmers).

32

2 Codes:

J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / K. Adaptability_4

15:108 Full convergence in 2019, at the latest: in the entire Member State, o..... (48:3109 [48:3317]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Full convergence in 2019, at the latest: in the entire Member State, or in each specified ‘region’ within the Member State, the same value of the payment entitlement is to be applied by 2019, at the latest;

4 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / D. Robustness_3 / J. Adapt_middle-to-long-term_instruments / J. Adaptability_3

Adapt_Flexibility_goals

52 Quotations:

2:5 Furthermore the share of expenditure between pillars may change in 2..... (4:1208 [4:1493]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Furthermore the share of expenditure between pillars may change in 2014-2020, with the possibility to transfer up to 15% of their national envelopes between pillars (as shown in the chart) 4 , enabling Member States to better target spending to their specific priorities

Comment: by buite049

Ability for countries to decide if they want to transfer 15% of their national envelopes between pillars

Score 3 fairly enabling. This goal does enable flexibility in budget per pillar. However it is limited to 15% and limited to two choices -the two pillars- in which the EU has set elements.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

2:8 From 2014 onwards, the allocation of direct payments dedicated to co..... (4:1027 [4:1204]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

From 2014 onwards, the allocation of direct payments dedicated to coupled support, young farmers, small farmers, etc. will depend upon the choices made by Member States.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility for member states to make choices on how to spent their direct payments. This enables flexibility score 4

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

2:12 There is new flexibility for Member States in the budgeting and imp..... (5:1286 [5:1770]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

There is new flexibility for Member States in the budgeting and implementation of first Pillar instruments, acknowledging the wide diversity of agriculture, agronomic

production potential and climatic, environmental as well as socio-economic conditions and needs across the EU.

This flexibility will however be framed by well-defined regulatory and budgetary limits in order to ensure a level-playing field at European level and that common objectives are met.

Comment: by buite049

Allows member states to make decisions on the budgeting and implementation of first pillar instruments --> enables flexibility

At the same time there are limits to this flexibility as regulatory and budgetary limits are in place (of course necessary to prevent big differences)

Score 3 fairly enabling and also fairly constraining

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

2:38 The flexibility offered to Member States to implement the new direct..... (7:3368 [7:3569]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The flexibility offered to Member States to implement the new direct payments means that the share of funding allocated to different schemes can potentially vary significantly throughout the EU.

Comment: by buite049

member states have a certain freedom to determine themselves where money may go to.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

2:43 In addition Member States will have further possibilities to rebalanc..... (8:2010 [8:2090]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

In addition Member States will have further possibilities to rebalance payments

Comment: by buite049

Score 4 enabling - Member states can decide if they want to introduce other measures to rebalance payments. But this is not mandatory

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

2:55 The two pillars will also interact in financial terms, with possible..... (9:1835 [9:1929]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The two pillars will also interact in financial terms, with possible transfers between both

Comment: by buite049

*Financial flexibility between the two pillars
Limited to 15%.
Score 3 fairly enabling flexibility*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

3:73 Mogelijk kunnen (nieuwe) teelten van eiwitgewassen deel uitmaken van..... (25:535 [25:654]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Mogelijk kunnen (nieuwe) teelten van eiwitgewassen deel uitmaken van de vergroeningsagenda in het kader van het GLB.

Comment: by buite049

*A possible alternative way to reach greening objectives. But it is still not sure if this is possible --> it is possible.
When possible it would fairly enable flexibility, but is only partially opens up a alternative to oblige to the greening measures.*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

4:3 Met de provincies is afgesproken dat ze streven naar een zo gelijk mog..... (1:1901 [1:2191]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Met de provincies is afgesproken dat ze streven naar een zo gelijk mogelijke uitvoering van de regeling. Omdat het karakter van de regeling zich richt op innovaties kunnen per provincie wel accentverschillen aangebracht worden zodat beter ingespeeld kan worden op regionale behoeften.

Comment: by buite049

*possibility to accentuate different measures to be better capable to deal with local contexts
However, 'to accentuate' does not feel like that major differences are possible. And the overall goal is to aim for a as much as possible even implementation per province.
Slightly enabling flexibility (score 2)*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

4:5 Daarnaast zal ik maximaal gebruik maken van de mogelijkheid om in de e..... (2:286 [2:442]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Daarnaast zal ik maximaal gebruik maken van de mogelijkheid om in de eerste pijler van het GLB aan jonge boeren een top-up op de hectarepremie te geven.

Comment: by buite049

Buffer resource because it is about direct payments related to the amount of land a farmer has. However a bit of variety as the measure is adapted to provide young farmers with a bit more financial support.

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

4:7 Voor LEADER en voor de regeling samenwerking bij proefprojecten en i..... (2:1559 [2:2001]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Voor LEADER en voor de regeling samenwerking bij proefprojecten en innovatie maken de provincies hierop een uitzondering in POP3 ten behoeve van stadslandbouw.

Dit betekent dat onder de lokale ontwikkelingsstrategieën van LEADER die gericht zijn op de ontwikkeling van het platteland via de versteviging van stadlandrelaties, nu ook projecten kunnen worden uitgevoerd in stedelijk gebied, dus in kernen met meer dan 30.000 inwoners.

Comment: by buite049

The POP3 is adapted to make it possible that projects focused on urban agriculture also have the possibility to receive subsidies.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

5:2 De eerste stap is dat lidstaten keuzes maken uit de generieke lijst en..... (2:140 [2:395]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

De eerste stap is dat lidstaten keuzes maken uit de generieke lijst en besluiten of, en zo ja welke equivalente pakketten beschikbaar zijn. De tweede stap is dat vervolgens boeren hun keuze maken uit de door de lidstaat opengestelde mogelijkheden.

Comment: by buite049

First the member states are allowed to make a choice - local decision can be made. Then within the member states, the farmers can choose from the options presented by the Member state. It is thus more about if the goal can be reached rather than the means Fairly enabling as there are possibilities for both member states and farmers to choose which greening measures they want to apply. However, this decision is reduced to a generic list from which member states can choose - a bit limited. Eventually the farmers can only choose from the limited list that the member states provide them.

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

5:3 Mijn voorstel voor de invulling van de EFA dat tijdens het AO van 1 ju..... (2:396 [2:753]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

Mijn voorstel voor de invulling van de EFA dat tijdens het AO van 1 juli jl. is besproken bestond uit een combinatie van zowel keuzes uit de generieke lijst als een equivalent pakket. De focus lag op een pakket equivalente maatregelen met de nadruk op beheerde akkerranden. Als alternatief konden boeren kiezen voor keuzes uit de generieke lijst.

Comment: by buite049

Providing farms a possibility to choose between different option to oblige to greening

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

6:4 for Pillar 2 a learning process has been set in motion since the la..... (51:426 [51:610]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

for Pillar 2 a learning process has been set in motion since the last programming period which supported a more focused approach in the RDP implying the choice for only 10 measures

Comment: by buite049

Reducing the amount of choices from the previous programme to only 10 measures = constraining the flexibility. However, with the learning process + the idea that "more does not always means better" you can argue that this could be a smart choice to reduce to much fragmentation and diversity.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

6:12 Individual greening payment with four options for EFA compliance and e..... (51:2895 [51:2984]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Individual greening payment with four options for EFA compliance and equivalent practices

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

6:20 There is an opportunity to review the rates for the 2018 year onwards,..... (14:959 [14:1349]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

There is an opportunity to review the rates for the 2018 year onwards, with notifications to be made to the Commission by 1 August 2017. Similar notification requirements are in place for the transfers from Pillar 2 to Pillar 1 – Member States had to notify the Commission by 1 August 2014 for transfers for the years 2016-2020 and can review their decision for the years 2019 and 2020

Comment: by buite049

ability to review and change the transfers from one to the other Pillar.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

7:9 Collectie ve in vulling EFA Ik wil mogelijk maken dat groepen van boe..... (5:894 [5:1303]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Collectie ve in vulling EFA Ik wil mogelijk maken dat groepen van boeren in 2015 kunnen kiezen voor een collectieve invulling van de EFA-verplichting. De Europese voorschriften bepalen dat het gaat om maximaal tien boeren met bijeengelegen bedrijven. Zij moeten zelf afspraken maken. De EFA-gebieden moeten aaneengesloten liggen. Elk bedrijf moet minimaal 2,5% van zijn eigen bouwland als EFA inrichten.

Comment: by buite049

Provides the possibility for farmers to cooperate and achieve their EFA-obligation. They can make their own arrangements. It is a different way of achieving the goal.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

7:32 Daaruit komen luzerne, rode klaver, esparcette, rolklaver, lupine en v..... (16:2361 [16:2931]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Daaruit komen luzerne, rode klaver, esparcette, rolklaver, lupine en veldbonen naar voren als soorten met een relatief hoge biodiversiteitswaarde en een inherent lage behoefte aan gewasbescherming en mest. Hierbij geldt op uitspoelingsgevoelige gronden een verplichte nateelt indien de teelt van het eiwitgewas in de nazomer of herfst wordt beeindigd, om stikstofuitspoeling te voorkomen. Met deze keuze blijft het gebruik van gewasbeschermingsmiddelen en mest in EFA's tot een minimum beperkt en geef ik invulling aan de wens om eiwitgewassen als EFA te erkennen.

Comment: by buite049

Different plant species can also be used for this mean. Increasing possibilities for farmers to find out which they want to use. It is more about that they will use protein rich crops then which ones and how (goals rather than means).

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

8:7 They may choose from different options: to take a national approach, o..... (2:879 [2:1695]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

They may choose from different options: to take a national approach, or a regional approach (based on administrative or agronomic criteria); to achieve a regional/national rate by 2019, or to ensure that those farms getting less than 90% of the regional/national average rate see a gradual increase (by one third of the difference between their current rate and 90% of the national/regional average) – with the additional guarantee that each payment entitlement reaches a minimum value of 60% of the national/regional average by 2019 (unless Member States decide to limit the decrease in the value of entitlements). The amounts available to farmers receiving more than the regional/national average will be adjusted proportionally, with an option for Member States to limit any "losses" to 30%.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to decide how the internal convergence can be achieved. However, the options are limited and internal convergence need to be achieved anyway. It thus slightly enables flexibility in how it is done, but very limited

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

8:20 In order to avoid penalising those that already address environmental..... (4:396 [4:494]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to avoid penalising those that already address environmental and sustainability issues,

Comment: by buite049

"greening equivalency" - it is introduced as a mean to also oblige to the greening measures. It allows member states to introduce a equivalent measure for farmers which can also contribute to the greening.

It provides flexibility in how a outcome is reached over the mean how it is reached.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

8:38 Member states or regions will continue to design their own multi-ann..... (6:338 [6:1168]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Member states or regions will continue to design their own multi-annual programmes on the basis of the menu of measures available at EU level – in response to the needs of their own rural areas. These programmes will be co-funded from the national envelopes – where the amounts and rates of co-funding will be dealt with within the context of the MFF. The new rules for the 2 nd Pillar provide a more flexible approach than at present. Measures will no longer be classified at EU level into "axes" with associated minimum spending requirements per axis. Instead, it will be up to Member States / regions to decide which measures they use (and how) in order to achieve targets set against six broad "priorities" and their more detailed "focus areas" (sub-priorities), on the basis of sound analysis.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

9:6 Each country also has a certain level of flexibility in the way they..... (1:1514 [1:1707]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Each country also has a certain level of flexibility in the way they grant these payments to take account of national farming conditions, which vary greatly throughout the European Union.

Comment: by buite049

A bit flexibility in deciding how payments are granted - a certain level of flexibility. But would not argue that it allows member states to have major differences. They are allowed to change small things within the lines set by the EU score 2

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

9:28 National authorities can decide which of the various direct paymen..... (4:1477 [4:1732]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

National authorities can decide which of the various direct payments schemes to finance from this allocation, subject to certain legislative limits. They may also choose to transfer money to or from their national rural development allocations.

Comment: by buite049

certain freedom to decide how money is granted between the different schemes and between pillars. But within legislative limits .

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

9:35 EU member states (MS) can combine different direct payment schemes to..... (6:800 [6:943]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

EU member states (MS) can combine different direct payment schemes to ensure efficient support to farmers, adapted to their national context.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

9:44 Depending on the choices made by each national authority, the basic..... (7:117 [7:422]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Depending on the choices made by each national authority, the basic payment accounts for between 12% and 68% of their national budget allocation.

The basic payment is applied either as the basic payment scheme (BPS) or as a transitional simplified scheme, the single area payment scheme (SAPS).

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

9:56 In order to accommodate the diversity of agricultural systems and envi..... (8:2931 [8:3513]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In order to accommodate the diversity of agricultural systems and environmental conditions across Europe, the concept of 'equivalence' was introduced. Member states may allow farmers to meet one or more greening requirements through equivalent (alternative) practices. This means that some practices can replace one or several of the three established greening measures. These practices include agri-environmentclimate measures or certification schemes that are similar to greening and which yield an equivalent or higher level of benefit for the climate and the environment.

Comment: by buite049

Possibilities for member states and farmers to oblige to the greening requirements through different means. In this goal the focus is on making sure that benefits for the climate and environment over how this should be reached

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:1 Binnen de kaders is ruimte voor nationale en regionale verschillen e..... (1:2143 [1:2227]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Binnen de kaders is ruimte voor nationale en regionale verschillen en maatwerk.

Comment: by buite049

Flexibility of the CAP guidelines at national level

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:11 Daarbij zal ik mij inzetten om de regeldruk en administratieve lasten..... (3:1161 [3:1345]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Daarbij zal ik mij inzetten om de regeldruk en administratieve lasten terug te dringen, de uitvoeringslast van de overheid te verminderen en het ondernemerschap de ruimte te bieden.

Comment: by buite049

It depends how you look at it (which political perspective you will use):

You can see it as that the government is displacing her responsibilities and places it with the farming sector; the farming sector is self-responsible for change. But why would you change, if the current situation is fine for your farm and economic situation and there are less consequences or a government that is nudging you in the right way?

On the other hand: reducing meddling of the government and providing entrepreneurial freedom may lead to that farmers dare to take initiatives to change or are able to better react to markets or problems

4 Codes:

A. Robustness_0 / C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / G. Adaptability_0 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:18 Binnen de gewasdiversificatie bestaan geen mogelijkheden voor nationale..... (4:1090 [4:1170]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Binnen de gewasdiversificatie bestaan geen mogelijkheden voor nationale keuzen.

Comment: by buite049

Constraining: no room for national decisions for crop diversification and thus no room for different approaches or other crop better suitable for the national context.

2 Codes:

H. Adaptability_1 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:25 Ruimte voor een collectieve benadering, binnen de randvoorwaarden van..... (5:2179 [5:2653]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ruimte voor een collectieve benadering, binnen de randvoorwaarden van het wetgevingskader. Hiermee kunnen groepen boeren gezamenlijk invulling geven aan de ecologisch aandachtsgebieden. Dit behelst dat een deel (maximaal de helft) van de individuele verplichting kan worden uitgevoerd door andere boeren binnen het collectief. Eis daarbij is, zoals geformuleerd in de Brusselse regelgeving, dat een aaneengesloten ecologisch aandachtsgebied wordt gerealiseerd.

Comment: by buite049

possibility for farmers to collectively arrange EFA. This enables flexibility for farmers to find other ways to oblige to the greening requirements score 4

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:26 Sloten die grenzen aan akkerranden en dergelijke kunnen als aangrenzen..... (5:2655 [5:2869]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Sloten die grenzen aan akkerranden en dergelijke kunnen als aangrenzend landschapselement worden meegeteld in de vergroeningsoppervlakte, omdat ze een extra bijdrage aan biodiversiteit of waterkwaliteit leveren.

Comment: by buite049

Flexibility: as the already existing ditches can also be counted as a green surface. Protection of status quo: The ditches are already there and will be counted as green surfaces. The change that occurs is thus minimal, because the ditches are already present without introducing new green surfaces. The increase in green surface will be only on paper, while the real amount of green surfaces stay the same. This may also mean that farmers feel less obliged to introduce new green surfaces.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:27 De vergroening zal aanpassingen vergen in de bedrijfsvoering, maar n..... (6:973 [6:1197]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De vergroening zal aanpassingen vergen in de bedrijfsvoering, maar naar mijn overtuiging hebben boeren hiermee voldoende ruimte om een invulling te kiezen die past bij hun bedrijf, hun ambities en hun mogelijkheden.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to provide the farmers with enough leeway to oblige to the greening measures, but it is not really clear to what extent this enables flexibility as is not a specific goal, but more an overall desire of the Dutch government.

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:30 Met de beschreven aanpak kan een deel van de vergroeningsverplichting..... (6:127 [6:451]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Met de beschreven aanpak kan een deel van de vergroeningsverplichting worden ingevuld met de teelt van bepaalde eiwitgewassen. Hiertoe zullen nader te bepalen eiwitgewassen als onderdeel van de invulling van de aangeduide combinatiepakketten kunnen dienen. Hiermee wordt ook de teelt van veevoergewassen gestimuleerd.

Comment: by buite049

The cultivation of protein crops as a equivalent measure that should lead to the same greening goal.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:50 POP3 wordt landsdelig ingevuld door de provincies en aangevuld door..... (10:619 [10:954]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

POP3 wordt landsdelig ingevuld door de provincies en aangevuld door het Rijk. Met de landsdelige aanpak kunnen gebiedsspecifieke behoeftes in de landbouw worden aangepakt. Aan generieke behoeftes wordt landsdekkend invulling gegeven. Met deze combinatie kan optimaal ingespeeld worden op het bevorderen van een gelijk speelveld.

Comment: by buite049

POP3 has the possibilities to be adapted to certain needs of the regions (provinces). It therefore provide a bit flexibility to have a more regional specific approach. Enables flexibility score 4

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:52 Het nieuwe wetgevingskader voor het GLB maakt het mogelijk om in POP3..... (10:1510 [10:2307]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het nieuwe wetgevingskader voor het GLB maakt het mogelijk om in POP3 een keuze te maken uit verschillende maatregelen ten gunste van de agrarische sector. Met deze maatregelen moet worden bijgedragen aan minimaal vier van de zes vastgestelde Europese plattelandsprioriteiten. Dit zijn: innovatie en kennisoverdracht, versterking van de concurrentiekracht, organisatie van de voedselketen en risicobeheer, beschermen van ecosystemen, duurzaam grondstofgebruik en CO2 reductie en economische ontwikkeling in plattelandsgebieden. Minimaal 5% van de beschikbare middelen moet worden ingezet voor LEADER, de bottom up benadering voor lokale initiatieven, en minimaal 30% moet worden ingezet voor maatregelen gericht op natuur en milieu, zoals bijvoorbeeld agrarisch natuurbeheer.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to make a decision within the POP3. However the member states can only decide within a set of provided means and priorities.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:58 Eventueel benodigde fysieke investeringen voor agrariërs wil ik onde..... (11:1723 [11:2091]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Eventueel benodigde fysieke investeringen voor agrariërs wil ik ondersteunen voor het ontwikkelen van nieuwe prototypes die in de praktijk getest moeten worden en voor de uitrol van innovaties in de land- en tuinbouw zoals precisielandbouw en duurzame stallen. Hierbij kan selectief gekeken worden naar specifieke problemen, gebieden en groepen van agrariërs.

Comment: by buite049

enables a bit flexibility as there is a possibility to focus on specific problems, areas and groups of farmers during the investment in innovations. No general approach, but paying attention to where it is necessary. slightly enables flexibility

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:63 Ze zullen hieraan gebiedsgericht invulling geven. (12:744 [12:794]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ze zullen hieraan gebiedsgericht invulling geven.

Comment: by buite049

The restructuring of farm businesses can be done in a region specific manner --> enables flexibility

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:82 Het GLB-wetgevingspakket laat weinig nationale keuzen voor het markt..... (15:2977 [15:3063]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het GLB-wetgevingspakket laat weinig nationale keuzen voor het markt- en prijsbeleid.

Comment: by buite049

Constraining, because there is almost no room for national autonomy to take decision regarding market- or price policy

2 Codes:

H. Adaptability_1 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

10:85 Hiernaast kunnen lidstaten equivalente maatregelen, na goedkeuring doo..... (4:1294 [4:1496]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Hiernaast kunnen lidstaten equivalente maatregelen, na goedkeuring door de Europese Commissie, toevoegen aan de Europese lijst waarmee bedrijven ook kunnen voldoen aan de vergroeningsverplichting.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

10:87 Samen met de provincies kies ik voor een beperkt aantal maatregelen..... (10:2431 [10:2796]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Samen met de provincies kies ik voor een beperkt aantal maatregelen (minder dan 10) uit de mogelijkheden die het wetgevingkader biedt. Dit is aanzienlijk minder dan in het huidige POP2, dat ruim 20 maatregelen kent. Zo wordt in POP3 een duidelijke focus en samenhang aangebracht om een versnipperde inzet te voorkomen en de uitvoeringskosten te beheersen.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the flexibility (score 2 constraining) as the amount of possible ways to deal with different circumstances / problems will be reduced. The reason for this decision is provided and actually pretty solid in my opinion

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

12:3 eder bedrijf en iedere keten kan meedoen, ieder binnen mogelijkheden d..... (1:1122 [1:1353]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

eder bedrijf en iedere keten kan meedoen, ieder binnen mogelijkheden die passen. De een maakt de stap naar biologische landbouw of zelfs naar biologisch-dynamische, de ander gaat aan de slag met verspilling of energiegebruik.

Comment: by buite049

There is room for farmers to take steps that are within their own capabilities and with their own focus. -- flexibility. The goal can therefore indeed enable flexibility

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

12:12 Om de koploerspositie te bereiken zijn kwaliteitsprongen nodig. Di..... (2:1940 [2:2269]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Om de koploerspositie te bereiken zijn kwaliteitsprongen nodig. Dit kan binnen ieder bedrijf en binnen de gehele keten, op een manier die bij het bedrijf of een keten past. De een maakt stappen richting biologische landbouw, de ander gaat besparen in watergebruik of voorkomt verspilling van productie of meststoffen.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

15:14 it is an interesting tool, because it acts downstream of the distribut..... (46:2351 [46:2691]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

it is an interesting tool, because it acts downstream of the distribution of financial resources between pillars, and among Member States, that had been decided on in the negotiations, allowing each country to shift resources between the two policies in keeping with its own development strategy, programming skills and spending capacity

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:17 (leaving the door open for Member States to make them more restrictiv..... (47:642 [47:728]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

(leaving the door open for Member States to make them more restrictive if they so wish

Comment: by buite049

Possibility for member states to make the rules / conditions for being a active farmer more strict --> provides a bit flexibility in the policy. fairly enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:45 Member States may decide to implement part of EFA (up to 50 % of the..... (52:3401 [52:3570]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may decide to implement part of EFA (up to 50 % of the individual EFA requirement at regional level) at regional level, in order to create adjacent EFAs.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to implement EFA in a different matter to reach the goal of adjacent EFAs. It is in this perspective more about reaching EFAs then how they are reached. It creates an extra option. fairly enabling flexibility

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:46 Member States may choose to identify agricultural practices that, by d..... (53:183 [53:407]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may choose to identify agricultural practices that, by definition, are considered able to generate benefits for the climate and the environment at least equivalent to those generated by these three conditions.

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

15:52 Member States may introduce additional criteria (54:490 [54:538]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may introduce additional criteria

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to introduce additional criteria. Not that enabling for flexibility.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:67 The small farms scheme is a simplified scheme that aims to reduce the..... (56:2536 [56:2715]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The small farms scheme is a simplified scheme that aims to reduce the bureaucratic burden, both for the beneficiaries and for the public sector, when small payments are involved.

Comment: by buite049

*small farmers scheme is a buffer resource for farmers.
It is however made with the idea to make it more easier for small farmers to obtain a direct payment - it is therefore focused on the goal of providing small farms with financial support instead of the way how to do it. Flexibility in how grants can be provided*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:68 The payment disbursed within the simplified scheme replaces the basic..... (57:355 [57:608]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The payment disbursed within the simplified scheme replaces the basic payment, or payment under the SAPS, the 'green payment', payment for young farmers, redistributive payment, coupled support and the crop-specific payment for cotton, where relevant.

Comment: by buite049

Possibility to use this simplified scheme instead of the regular scheme - flexibility in granting payments by replacing other payments

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:90 decided to apply the basic payment at national level, considering the..... (73:2195 [73:2300]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

decided to apply the basic payment at national level, considering the whole territory as a single region.

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands decided to apply the basic payment at national level, considering the whole territory as a single region. Constraints the idea of regional differences (differences in contexts between regions - farming systems) - and thus the idea to adapt measures accordingly. However also no 'discrimination' between regions?

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

15:94 Despite the mandatory nature of the ‘green payments’, the Member State..... (78:1535 [78:2064]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Despite the mandatory nature of the ‘green payments’, the Member States have been given some flexibility, in particular the possibility to consider “equivalent practices” to be included in the agri-environmental programmes. If the Commission recognises the equivalency of the practice, the Member State does not need to comply on that matter with the “green requirement”. Only a few Members States have embraced this possibility: the Czech Republic, France, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Austria and Poland (Table 1.13).

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands have opted for "equivalent practices"

2 Codes:

K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / K. Adaptability_4

17:17 Whilst Member States compose their programmes from the same list of..... (7:1390 [7:1645]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU’s common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Whilst Member States compose their programmes from the same list of measures, they have the flexibility to address the issues of most concern within their respective territory reflecting their specific economic, natural and structural conditions.

Comment: by buite049

Some flexibility as the member states are allowed to adjust compose their own programmes. However this is limited by the list of measures from which they can choose. Limited flexibility --> slightly enabling

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

18:44 Uitbreiding ten behoeve van dierwelzijn of om te voldoen aan milie..... (13:542 [13:664]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Uitbreiding ten behoeve van dierwelzijn of om te voldoen aan milievereisten blijft ook in de nieuwe situatie mogelijk.

Comment: by buite049

*Upscaling of intensive livestock farming will be not allowed. However there is flexibility in that you are allowed to upscale when it benefits animal welfare or if it has environmental benefits. Exceptions are possible -->fairly enabling
Not really relevant for the case study - different farming sector. About live stock farming not arable farming --> not clear*

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals

Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

50 Quotations:

2:35 A specific and simplified support scheme for small farmers will subs..... (7:3083 [7:3248]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

A specific and simplified support scheme for small farmers will substantially facilitate their access to direct payments and reduce their administrative burden.

Comment: by buite049

*The measure itself is robust, because it is nothing more than financial compensation through direct payments;
However, the measure is there with in mind that there are differences between member states regarding their capacity to arrange direct payments. It thus provides a different policy option to arrange direct payments.*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

4:19 Na goedkeuring blijft altijd de mogelijkheid bestaan om het programma..... (5:140 [5:360]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-Invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Na goedkeuring blijft altijd de mogelijkheid bestaan om het programma opnieuw te wijzigen, bijvoorbeeld om in te spelen op nieuwe behoeftes en inzichten. Dit zal uiteraard in overleg met de provincies moeten gebeuren.

Comment: by buite049

*possibility to change the programmes when the situation asks for it - flexibility
But this needs to be done with the help of the provinces.*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

5:10 Het equivalente pakket Het equivalente pakket krijgt als gevolg van..... (3:850 [3:1379]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

Het equivalente pakket Het equivalente pakket krijgt als gevolg van de aangenomen motie Geurts (Kamerstuk 28625, nr. 205) de vorm van een duurzaamheidscertificaat en niet langer van een agrarisch natuurbeheerpakket. Als gevolg daarvan kan de ondernemer jaarlijks kiezen hoe zijn vergroening in te vullen: op basis van de generieke lijst of met het certificaat. Dit certificaat kent als kernelement de beheerde akkerrand of -strook. Daarnaast kan de boer o.a. kiezen voor vanggewassen en/of stikstofbindende gewassen.

Comment: by buite049

*Different ways to fill in the measure, and farmers are allowed to make a choice which they want to use.
The mean is important, but it is more focused on the desired outcome*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

5:11 Met de voornoemde moties zijn de volgende stappen gezet: 1. De keuze..... (2:774 [2:1233]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

Met de voornoemde moties zijn de volgende stappen gezet: 1. De keuze in de generieke lijst is uitgebreid met de mogelijkheid voor een algemene toepassing van vanggewassen als invulling van de EFA (onder enkele voorwaarden); 2. Een plek voor aaltjesbestrijdende gewassen als vergroeningsoptie; 3. De zogenaamde 'vogelakker' moet worden opgenomen in een equivalent pakket; 4. Boeren moeten jaarlijks kunnen kiezen hoe ze de EFA willen invullen.

Comment: by buite049

All these decisions are taken to provide more room for different ways that can contribute to the greening. It is thus introduced as alternative ways to reach desired outcomes

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:10 Pillar 2 € 1.53 billion (69%), before the transfer of 4.3% from Pill..... (51:2635 [51:2722]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Pillar 2 € 1.53 billion (69%), before the transfer of 4.3% from Pillar 1 to Pillar 2;

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:18 Member States have the flexibility to transfer 15 % of their direct pa..... (14:181 [14:358]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Member States have the flexibility to transfer 15 % of their direct payment envelope from Pillar 1 to Pillar 2 as well as in the opposite direction from Pillar 2 to Pillar 1.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:19 In the case of the transfer from Pillar 2 to Pillar 1, 12 Member Sta..... (14:359 [14:569]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

In the case of the transfer from Pillar 2 to Pillar 1, 12 Member States are permitted to transfer an additional 10 %, bringing the maximum transfer permitted up to 25 % (Art. 14 of Reg. (EU) No. 1307/2013).

Comment: by buite049

This instruments takes into account differences between countries' farming systems

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:21 Member States can also choose to introduce some optional measures – e..... (14:2002 [14:2155]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Member States can also choose to introduce some optional measures – e.g. coupled support and payment to farmers in areas of natural constraint (ANC).

Comment: by buite049

*Member states can choose to do it. Member states have some freedom to choose if they want to implement a some extra (predetermined) payments --> fairly enabling
But these extra payments are mostly very robustness-focused - compensation payments and means to protect the status quo --> robustness very enabling score 5*

4 Codes:

D. Robust_protect_status_quo_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:29 Decide to shift up to 15 % of national annual ceiling from Pillar 1 to..... (15:1937 [15:2214]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Decide to shift up to 15 % of national annual ceiling from Pillar 1 to Pillar 2; Or decide to shift up to 15 % (or 25 % for Bulgaria, Estonia, Spain, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Finland, Sweden and the United Kingdom) from Pillar 2 to Pillar 1.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:35 Voluntary simplified scheme for small farmers Decide to implement..... (16:2520 [16:2615]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Voluntary simplified scheme for small farmers Decide to implement a small farmers scheme.

Comment: by buite049

*a special scheme for small farmers then can be used = flexibility
Still direct payments that are used as financial compensation = buffer resource*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

6:36 Art. 16-20 Framework within which Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania may..... (16:2616 [16:3013]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Art. 16-20 Framework within which Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania may complement direct payments Bulgaria and Romania are in 2015 still allowed to complement direct payments with national direct payments; Bulgaria is allowed to complement the specific payment for cotton with national direct payments; Croatia is allowed to complement direct payments with national direct payments.

Comment: by buite049

It are measures that just provide financial support (extra), However the goal of these measures is based on that these countries differ in their farming context and are new members of the EU.

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

7:7 Een 'equivalent pakket'. Bij gebruik van equivalente pakketten moet de..... (4:1068 [4:1226]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Een 'equivalent pakket'. Bij gebruik van equivalente pakketten moet de boer (volgens Europees voorschrift) zijn volledige EFA-verplichting hiermee invullen.

Comment: by buite049

Flexibility to use an equivalent measure. However, if a farmer decides to do this, the farmer needs to oblige to his/her EFA obligations through this equivalent measure.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

7:8 In plaats van bovengenoemd 'equivalent pakket' kunnen boeren ook kiezen..... (4:2086 [4:2253]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

In plaats van bovengenoemd 'equivalent pakket' kunnen boeren ook kiezen voor een of meer van de volgende elementen van de generieke longlist van de GLB-verordening.

Comment: by buite049

Extra possible measure to oblige to the greening. A generic list of options.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

7:12 Duurzaamheidscertifica ten Mede door inzet van Nederland kunnen duur..... (6:2475 [7:215]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Duurzaamheidscertifica ten Mede door inzet van Nederland kunnen duurzaamheidscertificaten onder voorwaarden als alternatieve invulling gelden voor de vergroening. De maatregelen in het certificaat moeten dan een gelijkwaardig of beter effect hebben op de doelen voor biodiversiteit, milieu en klimaat. Deelnemers dienen te voldoen aan alle vergroeningsverplichtingen. Tevens dient het certificeringssysteem aan Europese regels te voldoen op het vlak van ontwerp, toetsing, Directoraat-generaal

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controle en transparantie. De duurzaamheidscertificaten moeten voor 1 augustus 2014 door de lidstaat gemeld worden en dan worden goedgekeurd door de EC. In volgende jaren moet de melding voor 1 juli plaatsvinden.

Comment: by buite049

A different mean is introduced next to the generic greening measures to oblige to the greening. This provides more options to reach the environmental aims of the CAP. flexibility.

The sustainability certificates are then an instruments that allows to be more flexible.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

7:43 Inmiddels heeft de EC weegfactoren vastgesteld voor de verschillende t..... (3:2446 [4:269]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Inmiddels heeft de EC weegfactoren vastgesteld voor de verschillende toegestane EFA-invullingen. Invullingen die veel bijdragen aan biodiversiteit krijgen een weegfactor groter dan een die door de lidstaat mag worden toegepast, zodat met Nederland heeft in totaal circa 1 miljoen ha bouwland. Vrijgesteld van de EFA-verplichting zijn biologische bedrijven, bedrijven met minder dan 15 ha bouwland (inclusief tijdelijk grasland) en bedrijven die meer dan 75% grasland en stikstofbindende gewassen hebben en daarnaast minder dan 30 ha bouwland.

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minder hectares aan de verplichting kan worden voldaan. Invullingen met een geringe bijdrage aan biodiversiteit hebben een weegfactor kleiner dan een die door de lidstaat moet worden toegepast, zodat juist meer hectares nodig zijn om aan de verplichting te voldoen.

Comment: by buite049

The Weight factors of EFA measures - meaning that their are different policy measures and each of these measures is weighted on its effect.

There is a bit flexibility in that there is a difference in how much the measures contribute to the EFA greening. You can therefore contribute to the greening with less measures that have a high score or with a lot of measures with a low score.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

8:21 Greening Equivalency: In order to avoid penalising those that already..... (4:375 [4:685]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Greening Equivalency: In order to avoid penalising those that already address environmental and sustainability issues, the accord foresees a "Greening equivalency" system whereby the application of environmentally beneficial practices already in place are considered to replace these basic requirements.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

8:23 Transferring funds between Pillars: Member States will have the possib..... (4:1572 [4:2085]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Transferring funds between Pillars: Member States will have the possibility of transferring up to 15% of their national envelope for Direct Payments (1st Pillar) to their Rural Development envelope. These amounts will not need to be co-funded. Member States will also have the option of transferring up to 15% of their national envelope for Rural Development to their Direct Payments envelope, or up to 25% for those Member States that get less than 90% of the EU average for direct payments.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

8:36 Controls: Control requirements will be lowered in regions where previ..... (8:34 [8:268]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Controls: Control requirements will be lowered in regions where previous checks have shown good results, i.e. the rules are being properly respected. However, checks will need to be increased in regions where there are problems.

Comment: by buite049

Monitoring may differ per region. The instrument is flexible to adress the different regions in a Different way.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

8:39 Co-funding rates: The maximum EU co-funding rates will be up to 85% in..... (6:2848 [6:3405]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Co-funding rates: The maximum EU co-funding rates will be up to 85% in less developed regions, the outermost regions and the smaller Aegean islands, 75% in transition regions, 63% in other transition regions and 53% in other regions for most payments, but can be higher for the measures supporting knowledge transfer, cooperation, the

establishment of producer groups and organisations and young farmer installation grants, as well as for LEADER projects and for spending related to the environment and climate change under various measures.

Comment: by buite049

Different regions receive a different approach. The approach depends on the difference in national economy --> is is therefore flexible in its support. At the same time, it is also flexible in that different variated measures can receive a higher payment --> slightly enables flexibility

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

8:40 In the new period, Member States / regions will also have the possibi..... (6:3406 [6:3516]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In the new period, Member States / regions will also have the possibility to design thematic sub-programmes

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

9:26 (where applied) a small farmers scheme, a simplified scheme for smal..... (4:685 [4:793]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

(where applied) a small farmers scheme, a simplified scheme for small farmers replacing the other schemes,

Comment: by buite049

*the small farmers scheme is just a simple replacement for the basic direct payments. It is therefore still a robust buffer resource score 5
It is however is is also an instrument that slightly enables flexibility as it is a specialised measure to satisfy / support owners of smaller farms. It also replaces other schemes. But also keeping in mind that the goal is to support these farmers with a basic income, it is then less about how this is done.*

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

9:46 In some member states that joined the European Union in 2004 and 200..... (7:1719 [7:1947]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

In some member states that joined the European Union in 2004 and 2007, the single area payment scheme (SAPS) is used instead. The SAPS is a transitional measure stemming from the Accession Treaties of those member states.

Comment: by buite049

Measure made for a different context --> it is therefore slightly flexible in that it is a measure made for different member states that joined the EU as last. Still buffer resource because it replaces the normal direct payment scheme.

4 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / F. Robustness_5 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

10:21 De lidstaten kunnen voor de ecologische aandachtsgebieden (of ecologic..... (5:156 [5:485]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De lidstaten kunnen voor de ecologische aandachtsgebieden (of ecological focus area, EFA) op bouwland kiezen uit een aantal opties, waaronder landschapselementen, akkerranden, bufferstroken en stikstofbindende gewassen.

De mogelijkheden lopen uiteen in hun bedrijfseconomische consequenties en biodiversiteitsopbrengst.

Comment: by buite049

the possibility to choose from a set of options to come to EFA --> fairly enables

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

10:23 Equivalente (pakketten van) maatregelen, zoals: o akkerranden met da..... (5:904 [5:1435]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Equivalente (pakketten van) maatregelen, zoals: o akkerranden met daaraan grenzende sloten ten behoeve van de stimulering van biodiversiteit, waaronder bijen; o bufferstroken met daaraan grenzende sloten; o natuurvriendelijke oevers met daaraan grenzende sloten; o combinaties van enerzijds percelen (zoals vogelakkers), stroken of akkerranden ten behoeve van de biodiversiteit op een bepaald deel van de EFA en anderzijds de teelt van bepaalde eiwitgewassen op het overige deel van de verplichte EFA-oppervlakte.

Comment: by buite049

equivalent set of measures that should contribute to the outcome of a more greener agriculture --> fairly enables flexibility

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

10:24 Duurzaamheidscertificaten. Ik zal het bedrijfsleven ondersteunen in he..... (5:1437 [5:2017]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Duurzaamheidscertificaten. Ik zal het bedrijfsleven ondersteunen in het ontwikkelen en uitwerken van zogenaamde duurzaamheidscertificaten. Dit principe, waarvoor een aanzet wordt gegeven in bijvoorbeeld de verduurzamingsaanpak van het programma 'Veldleeuwerik', zal de komende tijd verder uitgewerkt moeten worden door het bedrijfsleven. Randvoorwaarde is dat de vergroeningsmaatregelen een zelfde meerwaarde hebben als de door de commissie voorgestelde maatregelen, waarna deze in de toekomst ook invulling kunnen geven aan één of meer vergroeningsverplichtingen.

Comment: by buite049

The instrument of sustainability certificates is introduced as a equivalent measure for greening. The idea is that it contributes in to the desired otucome (goal) but in a different way.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

12:76 Tot 2014 is een (beperkt) sectoraal budget voor landbouw beschikbaar,..... (13:2140 [13:2599]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Tot 2014 is een (beperkt) sectoraal budget voor landbouw beschikbaar, dat kan worden ingezet voor de (co)financiering van projecten die binnen de doelstellingen van het beleid passen, maar die om andere redenen niet in aanmerking komen voor financiering vanuit de aanvullende budgetten. Te denken valt dan aan kleinere projecten, die niet als 'ster'- project kunnen worden aangemerkt, maar die wel een bijdrage kunnen leveren aan de gestelde doelen.

Comment: by buite049

financial support for other innovative projects that are not regarded as a 'star' project, but still can contribute to one of the stated goals. It is more about the outcome then the mean. It is also a more flexible way of dealing with funding and making possible that means are also achieved through smaller projects --> flexiblity farily enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:3 Flexibility between pillars: all Member States have the possibility to..... (33:1545 [33:1919]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Flexibility between pillars: all Member States have the possibility to transfer up to 15 % of financial resources from direct payment (Pillar I) to rural development measures (Pillar II), and vice versa. Member States with an average direct payment per hectare below 90 % of the EU average are allowed to transfer 10 % of their allocation in the EAFRD to direct payments

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:10 Flexibility between pillars As part of the MFF package, Member States..... (46:205 [46:411]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Flexibility between pillars As part of the MFF package, Member States may transfer funds between pillars. Each Member State may transfer up to 15 % of the annual ceiling for direct payment to Pillar II.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:11 Member States that do not transfer funds from Pillar I to Pillar II ma..... (46:601 [46:771]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States that do not transfer funds from Pillar I to Pillar II may make transfers in the opposite direction, shifting up to 15 % of funds from Pillar II to Pillar I.

Comment: by buite049

*The transfer is also possible in the opposite direction --> slightly enables flexibility (2)
There will then be extra funding available for direct payment scheme --> buffer resource
--> slightly enables robustness (2)*

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:12 Bulgaria, Spain, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romani..... (46:773 [46:1089]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Bulgaria, Spain, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Finland, Sweden and the United Kingdom – the 12 Member States with average direct payments per hectare below 90 % of the EU average – are allowed to transfer up to 25% of the support they receive for rural development to Pillar I.

Comment: by buite049

slightly enables extra flexibility for some countries.

It is a measure that is made available for other countries in perspective of their national context.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:18 defined by the Member State. (47:1134 [47:1161]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

defined by the Member State.

Comment: by buite049

National autonomy to decided upon the definition.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:19 Member States may add other criteria to identify 'active farmers' that..... (47:2023 [47:2278]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may add other criteria to identify 'active farmers' that pertain to the importance the farming activity has on their overall economic activity and/or to the fact that their principal business has still to do with an agricultural activity.

Comment: by buite049

can add some extra requirements --> slightly enabling flexibility

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:22 Member States have the option of lowering this threshold (and even of..... (47:2626 [47:2807]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States have the option of lowering this threshold (and even of differentiating it among regions), and thereby make the definition of 'active farmer' even more restrictive.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:24 Convergence is pursued with reference either to the country as a whole..... (48:2391 [48:2729]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Convergence is pursued with reference either to the country as a whole or to individual regions; the latter are to be defined by the Member State and do not have to coincide with existing administrative or institutional units; may also be defined on the basis of agronomic and socio-economic characteristics or agricultural potential.

3 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:26 The reform did foresee three different options for 'internal converge..... (48:2731 [48:3565]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The reform did foresee three different options for 'internal convergence': Full convergence in 2015: in 2015, the first year of implementation of the new CAP, the same unit value of the payment entitlement (in other words, the same value of per-hectare basic payment) was to be applied in the entire Member State, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State; Full convergence in 2019, at the latest: in the entire Member State, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State, the same value of the payment entitlement is to be applied by 2019, at the latest; Partial convergence: differences between the values of the per-hectare basic payment received by farmers in the Member State as a whole, or in each specified 'region' within the Member State, are to be reduced, but will still exist in 2019.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:35 As regards Bulgaria and Romania, countries that joined EU more recentl..... (51:183 [51:1212]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

As regards Bulgaria and Romania, countries that joined EU more recently, they may use national direct payments in order to complement the basic payment ('topping-up') for 2015 only (the last year of the process of phasing in direct payments).

25 Moreover, in 2015, Bulgaria may use national direct payments in order to complement payments granted under the crop-specific payment for cotton.

26 Croatia, which joined the EU in 2013, will progressively phase in the direct payment to reach the full level in 2022. The country may top up any of the relevant support schemes listed in Annex I of Regulation (EU) 1307/2013 27, subject to the authorisation of the Commission. Croatia will continue to enjoy the special national de-mining reserve established in Regulation (EC) 73/2009, the aim of which is to allocate payment entitlements to farmers with de-mined land back to being used for agricultural activities, provided that the land is eligible for direct payments and that the Commission has been notified.

28

Comment: by buite049

not specifically relevant for the Dutch case = not clear (0)

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:50 In fact, if the amount necessary to cover all requests of young farme..... (53:3074 [53:3466]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In fact, if the amount necessary to cover all requests of young farmers applying for payment is not sufficient, Member States should use the national reserve or, if the percentage for the payment for young farmers is below 2%, proceed to a linear reduction of the basic payment. If the percentage share is 2%, Member State shall make a linear reduction of the payment for young farmers.

Comment: by buite049

possibility to use other reserves or use linear reduction to still be able to provide young farmers financial aid --> this fairly enables flexibility in this instrument

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:53 Member States may decide to calculate the actual payment on an individ..... (54:809 [54:1694]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may decide to calculate the actual payment on an individual basis or as a set payment. The yearly payment for each young farmer is calculated multiplying the number of payment entitlements the farmer has activated by : $\frac{1}{3}$ 25 % of the average value of the basic payment entitlements owned or leased by the young farmer, or $\frac{1}{3}$ 25 % of the national average value of the basic payment 33, or $\frac{1}{3}$ 25 % of the average value of total national payments (including the basic payment) 34.

For Member States applying the SAPS, the payment for young farmers is calculated annually by multiplying 25 % of the SAPS by the number of eligible hectares the young farmers have declared.

Alternatively, Member States may introduce an annual lump sum payment calculated by multiplying a fixed number of hectares 35 by 25 % of the national average value of national payment.

Comment: by buite049

The member states have a certain amount of freedom to choose which method they will use to calculate the actual payment for young farmers.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:54 The redistributive payment is a voluntary component of direct payments..... (54:1949 [54:2019]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The redistributive payment is a voluntary component of direct payments.

Comment: by buite049

member states may decide to do it --> room to make own decision. Voluntary component, therefore not obligated to do so.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:56 Member States are free to decide the amount of the per-hectare payment..... (54:2772 [55:309]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States are free to decide the amount of the per-hectare payment. If the 32 In such instances, the period is reduced by the number of years elapsed between the young farmer becoming head of the holding and the submission of the application for the specific payment.

33 The national average value of the basic payment is obtained by dividing the national ceiling for the basic payment in 2019 by the number of all eligible hectares in 2015.

34 The average value of the total national payments is obtained by dividing the total national ceiling (including the basic payment) in 2019 by the number of all eligible hectares in 2015.

35 The fixed number of hectares is calculated by dividing the number of eligible hectares young farmers have declared by the total number of young farmers who applied for the payment in 2015.

36 The national (or regional) average payment per hectare is calculated by dividing the national ceiling for direct payments at the national (or regional) level in 2019 by the number of eligible hectares declared by the Member State (or region) in 2015.

Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014 – 2020 in the EU Member States

51 basic payment is implemented at regional level, then the amount of the redistributive payment can also be set at this level.

Comment: by buite049

| *free decision for member states. And possibility to set this at the regional level.*

2 Codes:

L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments / L. Adaptability_5

15:57 Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints ar..... (55:1067 [55:1182]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Direct payments to farms located in areas with natural constraints are a voluntary component of the direct payment

Comment: by buite049

| *Not voluntary = flexible instrument. MS can choose if they want to implement it or not. Possibility for member states to decide to implement it or not --> enabling flexibility.*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:59 Member States may introduce the payment in all areas with natural con..... (55:2050 [55:2283]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may introduce the payment in all areas with natural constraints (as defined for rural development policy purposes), or limit it, on the basis of objective and non-discriminatory criteria, to only a part of these areas.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:60 Member States may opt for a payment set at the regional level, i.e. to..... (55:2298 [55:2580]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may opt for a payment set at the regional level, i.e. to differentiate the per-hectare payment by region on the basis of differing characteristics of natural constraints and agronomic conditions, and may limit the payment to a maximum number of hectares per farm.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:64 Member States may increase this percentage to up to 100 %, thereby in..... (58:947 [58:1106]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Member States may increase this percentage to up to 100 %, thereby introducing a de facto EUR 150,000 threshold for the degressivity 'cap' on basic payments.

Comment: by buite049

*may introduce a 150,000 euro treshold for direct payments. This means that big receivers can be constraint in their direct payments. This constraints financial compensations for big farms. constraining buffer resources
However it is voluntary, meaning that a member state can decide themselves it they want to do this or not. = flexibility*

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:78 Flexibility between pillars denotes the option for Member States to sh..... (65:2868 [65:2993]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Flexibility between pillars denotes the option for Member States to shift their own financial resources between CAP pillars.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:81 The CAP already had mechanisms to transfer resources from the direct p..... (66:485 [66:668]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The CAP already had mechanisms to transfer resources from the direct payments ceiling to support relating to rural development. The most important of these was the so-called modulation

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:84 As for transfers in the opposite direction, the possibility of shifting..... (66:1495 [66:1807]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

As for transfers in the opposite direction, the possibility of shifting funds from rural development to direct payments, introduced with the flexibility tool, is a new element. Fully in line with the logic of current reform, it increases the range of the strategic choices at the disposal of the Member States.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:96 a collective implementation of the EFA (Article 46.6). This aspect is..... (78:3502 [78:3793]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

a collective implementation of the EFA (Article 46.6). This aspect is quite interesting given the underlying idea of collective contribution to the environmental services offered in a specific area. This article of the regulation has only been applied in Flanders, Netherlands and Poland

Comment: by buite049

In the Netherlands it is possible to collectively implement an EFA. This is thus a flexible way of achieving the goal of implementing EFA's (and reaching greening goals). It is focused on reaching the goal by providing an extra way to reach it.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

15:112 Farms located in areas covered by the Habitat, Water and Bird directiv..... (52:1478 [52:1816]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Farms located in areas covered by the Habitat, Water and Bird directives are entitled to receive 'green payments', provided that they comply with green practices compatible with the objectives of the relevant directive. Land devoted to organic agriculture is by default assumed to fulfil the conditions to receive the 'green payment'.

Comment: by buite049

*Flexible instruments as different conditions are in place for different cases / context.
There is therefore some flexibility in the measure for farmers that are already participate
in green / environmental measures --> enables flexibility
This still regards financial compensation --> buffer resource*

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments / L. Adaptability_5

15:116 The percentage share of transferred funds may vary from year to year..... (46:1265 [46:1571]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The percentage share of transferred funds may vary from year to year. Member States may revise their decisions by 1 August 2017, with effect from calendar year 2018 in the case of transfers from Pillar I to Pillar II, and with effect in 2019 and 2020 in the case of transfers from Pillar II to Pillar I.

Comment: by buite049

*Slightly enabling flexibility as it is possible to revise the transfer of funding from one pillar to the other pillar.
Also a short term instrument as it means that the payment cycle has a period of only one year and can partially be changed the next year.*

4 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / L. Adapt_Flexibility_instruments

Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

96 Quotations:

2:22 Farmers also have to adapt to challenges stemming from changes to th..... (6:2416 [6:2655]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Farmers also have to adapt to challenges stemming from changes to the climate by pursuing climate change mitigation and adaptation actions (e.g. by developing greater resilience to disasters such as flooding, drought and fire).

Comment: by buite049

The farming system needs to adapt to these challenges through mitigation and adaptation = adaptation variety.

But it is also a goal for risk management as the adaptation is necessary to deal with shocks and stresses = robustness risk management

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / G. Robust_other_risk_management_goals / J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:23 Given the pressure on natural resources, agriculture has to improve..... (6:2265 [6:2412]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Given the pressure on natural resources, agriculture has to improve its environmental performance through more sustainable production methods

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to reduce the stress on the environment through more sustainable methods. The goal is thus to adapt the system. However it seems that is mostly to make sure that natural resources are still available in the future for the system to work --> slightly enables variety.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:26 As the green direct payment is compulsory it has the advantage of..... (7:395 [7:589]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

As the green direct payment is compulsory it has the advantage of introducing practices that are beneficial for the environment and climate on most of the utilised agricultural area.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:47 As in the past, it will be implemented through national and/or reg..... (9:323 [9:431]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

As in the past, it will be implemented through national and/or regional rural development programs(RDP's)

Comment: by buite049

national decision making possible (in line with the EU)

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:50 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:20:494-9:290:519) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

4. Restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:51 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:10:522-9:304:558) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

5. Promoting resource efficiency and supporting the shift towards a low carbon and climate resilient economy in agriculture, food and forestry sectors

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:52 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:16:559-9:294:581) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

6. Promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:53 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:18:455-9:289:492) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

3. Promoting food chain organisation, including processing and marketing of agricultural products, animal welfare and risk management in agriculture

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

2:54 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:14:408-9:294:456) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

2. Enhancing farm viability and competitiveness of all types of agriculture in all regions and promoting innovative farm technologies and sustainable management of forests

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:4 In 2020 komt een kwart van het ondernemersinkomen uit de levering..... (6:665 [6:844]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

In 2020 komt een kwart van het ondernemersinkomen uit de levering van groene grondstoffen ten behoeve van nieuwe toepassingen op het gebied van voeding, farma en/of chemie.

Comment: by buite049

A part of the income needs to come from other functions that the farms can have such as the production of energie.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:6 In 2020 wordt een aanzienlijk deel van het totale energieverbruik i..... (7:54 [7:234]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

In 2020 wordt een aanzienlijk deel van het totale energieverbruik in de Veenkoloniën lokaal en groen geproduceerd. De deelnemende partijen streven vooralsnog naar 20 procent.

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:10 Vergroening: In 2020 heeft 5 procent van de oppervlakte die op dit o..... (7:378 [7:635]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Vergroening: In 2020 heeft 5 procent van de oppervlakte die op dit ogenblik door de landbouw wordt beheerd, een (neven) functie op het gebied van vergroening (minimaal 5.000 hectare). Dit vooruitlopend op de besluitvorming over de nieuwe GLB-eisen.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:20 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (10:124:135-10:335:174) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:21 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (11:94:75-11:357:237) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:22 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (11:49:407-11:180:485) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:36 Met dit project brengen we in kaart welke kennis kan bijdragen aan:..... (15:120 [15:373]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Met dit project brengen we in kaart welke kennis kan bijdragen aan: • het verbeteren van de bodem- en waterkwaliteit, • een optimaal ingericht watersysteem op de gewenste (landbouw) ambities, • en welke behoefte er nog is aan nieuwe kennis.

Comment: by buite049

This are the goals this project want to reach. A variety of different goals

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:58 Dit initiatief richt zich op het valoriseren van reststromen die vri..... (22:15 [22:351]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Dit initiatief richt zich op het valoriseren van reststromen die vrijkomen bij de productie van zetmeel uit aardappelen door deze om te zetten in bio-energie. Hiermee wordt het rendement van de verwerking van zetmeelaardappelen structureel verhoogd. Tegelijk wordt het gebruik van niet hernieuwbare energiebronnen teruggedrongen.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:62 Ontwikkeling van een plan waarmee de vergroeningseisen van het nieuw..... (23:15 [23:698]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Ontwikkeling van een plan waarmee de vergroeningseisen van het nieuwe GLB-beleid worden ingevuld op een manier die past bij de landbouwstructuur van de Veenkoloniën (een bouwplan met voornamelijk zetmeelaardappelen, suikerbieten en graan). Het plan moet aansluiten op en /of invulling geven aan belangrijke nevendoelen op het gebied van het regionale watersysteem (door o.a. buffering), biodiversiteit en landschappelijke kwaliteit.

Het resultaat is een (collectief) pakket aan maatregelen dat door een boer in de Veenkoloniën kan worden uitgevoerd om een extra inkomensbron op het bedrijf te genereren en het gebied daarmee een 'gewenste' dienst te leveren.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:64 Natte Natuurbraak: met dit experiment worden de effecten gemeten die..... (24:799 [24:1138]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Natte Natuurbraak: met dit experiment worden de effecten gemeten die Natte Natuurbraak kan hebben op diverse natuurwaarden, waterkwaliteit en de landbouwpraktijk in de Veenkoloniën. Dit experiment is gericht op het vermeerderen van kennis door een concreet project, ter voorbereiding op verdere opschaling en herhaling elders.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:67 Sluiten kringlopen akkerbouw – veehouderij: samenwerking tussen akkerb..... (24:1778 [24:2024]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Sluiten kringlopen akkerbouw – veehouderij: samenwerking tussen akkerbouw- en veehouderijbedrijven biedt kansen als het gaat om het optimaliseren van de groenvoedervervoorziening, uitwisseling van mest/mineralen, verruiming van het bouwplan

Comment: by buite049

Variety --> There are multiple problems and the aim is to come to a connection between cattle breeding and arable farming to solve these problems; multiple possibilities to solve it through this connection are mentioned.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:68 ontwikkelen en implementeren van food en feed lupine-productie en..... (25:1291 [25:1406]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

ontwikkelen en implementeren van food en feed lupine-productie en verwerkingsketen voor hoogwaardige producten

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:70 kansen voor een eigen Europese eiwit voorziening. Dit project heeft..... (26:264 [26:989])
- D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

kansen voor een eigen Europese eiwit voorziening. Dit project heeft tot doel het verhogen van de opbrengst van de huidige soja rassen tot een niveau waarbij het voor akkerbouwers in de regio kan concurreren met andere gewassen (minimale opbrengst 4,5 ton per jaar). Regionale (Noord West Europese) soja is een extra (duurzaam) gewas dat akkerbouwers kunnen gebruiken in de gewasrotatie. De inspanningen in dit project leveren nieuwe soja rassen op die geschikt zijn in het Noord-West Europese zeeklimaat. De non-gm (=niet genetisch gemodificeerde) soja vindt naast afzet voor veevoer, ook afzet in de foodindustrie (tofu, soja melk, ingrediënt bakkerij) indien het eiwitpercentage toereikend is.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:72 De introductie van uien en de arealgroei van cichorei laat zien dat..... (25:14 [25:533]) -
D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

De introductie van uien en de arealgroei van cichorei laat zien dat er mogelijkheden zijn voor nieuwe gewassen in de Veenkoloniën. De teelt van eiwithoudende gewassen op regionale schaal biedt kansen. In enkele projecten wordt gewerkt aan de verbetering van de teelt van soja en lupine. Door opbrengstverbetering worden deze gewassen in bouwplanverband economisch interessant. Door een regionale afzetketen te vormen (bijv. in samenwerking met Agrifirm) wordt een gesloten kringloopgedachte bevorderd.

Comment: by buite049

Introducing new crops (protein rich crops) is seen as a chance to increase yields and income. It is a goal that does not prioritise the current crops - constrains the protection of the status quo.

But the goal is aimed at changing the production strategy without really changing the operational logic of the farms.

It can bring heterogeinity in the area

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:75 Daarnaast biedt de nieuwe teelt van bijvoorbeeld medicinale planten..... (27:340 [27:497]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Daarnaast biedt de nieuwe teelt van bijvoorbeeld medicinale planten een perspectief voor teeltwisseling en dus toegevoegde waarde aan de biodiversiteit.

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

3:76 Het doel van dit platform is het ontwikkelen van duurzame economisch..... (27:1277 [27:1518]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Het doel van dit platform is het ontwikkelen van duurzame economische bedrijvigheid door het realiseren van hoogwaardige en marktgestuurde productieketens voor de verwerkende industrie (o.a.

voeding, farma, fijn chemie en cosmetica).

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

4:1 Ik zal POP3 eind april 2014 ter goedkeuring bij de Europese Commissi..... (1:1267 [1:1480]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Ik zal POP3 eind april 2014 ter goedkeuring bij de Europese Commissie indienen. Anders dan in POP2 zijn de provincies nu verantwoordelijk voor de programmering en uitvoering van het grootste deel van het POP.

Comment: by buite049

Local regional decision making

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

5:2 De eerste stap is dat lidstaten keuzes maken uit de generieke lijst en..... (2:140 [2:395]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

De eerste stap is dat lidstaten keuzes maken uit de generieke lijst en besluiten of, en zo ja welke equivalente pakketten beschikbaar zijn. De tweede stap is dat vervolgens boeren hun keuze maken uit de door de lidstaat opengestelde mogelijkheden.

Comment: by buite049

First the member states are allowed to make a choice - local decision can be made. Then within the member states, the farmers can choose from the options presented by the Member state. It is thus more about if the goal can be reached rather than the means. Fairly enabling as there are possibilities for both member states and farmers to choose which greening measures they want to apply. However, this decision is reduced to a generic list from which member states can choose - a bit limited. Eventually the farmers can only choose from the limited list that the member states provide them.

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / K. Adapt_Flexibility_goals / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:3 The institutional factor with the strengthened role of the provinces..... (51:613 [51:879]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

The institutional factor with the strengthened role of the provinces especially with regard to the RDP also influenced the implementation choices. However, the choice for retaining one national RDP was a deliberate one, in order to prevent too much fragmentation.

Comment: by buite049

The provinces have a strengthened role regarding the Rural Development Programme = Room for more context related or regional decision making. However, the it is one national programme (one fits all) approach, reducing the ability to design specific RDP for regional contexts.

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:7 with attention for environmental sustainability in terms of emission..... (51:1190 [51:1271]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

with attention for environmental sustainability in terms of emissions and water.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:43 restoring and preserving biodiversity, including in Natura 2000 areas..... (17:537 [17:676]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

restoring and preserving biodiversity, including in Natura 2000 areas and high nature value farming, and the state of European landscapes;

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:44 improving water management; (17:681 [17:708]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

improving water management;

Comment: by buite049

improving the water management can be considered as adapting the current way of dealing with water - adaptability

But it is also about making sure that it can still supply water for the agricultural tasks and to continue farming - robustness

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:45 improving soil management; (17:713 [17:739]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

improving soil management;

Comment: by buite049

*Improving the soilmanagement can be considered as adapting the current way of dealing with water - adaptability
But it is also about making sure that it can still supply water for the agricultural tasks and to continue farming - robustness*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:46 increasing efficiency in water use by agriculture; (17:937 [17:986]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

increasing efficiency in water use by agriculture;

Comment: by buite049

increasing the efficiency is a goal that is beneficial for the environment. It is adapting your your own system to respond to changing external drivers. But it is also about continuing the current system in such a way that you can still maintain desired levels of outputs. --> adaptability (2) --> robustness (3)

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:47 increasing efficiency in energy use in agriculture and food processing..... (17:992 [17:1062]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

increasing efficiency in energy use in agriculture and food processing;

Comment: by buite049

increasing the efficiency is a goal that is beneficial for the environment. It is adapting your your own system to respond to changing external drivers. But it is also about

continuing the current system in such a way that you can still maintain desired levels of outputs. --> adaptability (2) --> robustness (3)

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:48 facilitating the supply and use of renewable sources of energy, of by..... (17:1068 [17:1230]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

facilitating the supply and use of renewable sources of energy, of by products, wastes, residues and other non food raw material for purposes of the bio-economy;

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:49 reducing nitrous oxide and methane emissions from agriculture; (17:1236 [17:1297]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

reducing nitrous oxide and methane emissions from agriculture;

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:50 fostering carbon sequestration in agriculture and forestry; (17:1303 [17:1361]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

fostering carbon sequestration in agriculture and forestry;

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:51 facilitating diversification, creation of new small enterprises and job creation; (17:1496 [17:1576]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

facilitating diversification, creation of new small enterprises and job creation;

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:66 M 6.2 business start up aid for nonagricultural activities in rural areas; (18:1548 [18:1621]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.2 business start up aid for nonagricultural activities in rural areas

Comment: by buite049

Start up aid is focused on the beginning of setting up the non-agricultural activities = short term instrument.

But the activities are introduced to create variety on the farms = variety

4 Codes:

B. Robust_short term_instruments / D. Robustness_3 / J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

6:68 M 6.4 support for investments in creation and development of non-agr..... (18:1906 [18:1995]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M 6.4 support for investments in creation and development of non-agricultural activities

Comment: by buite049

Investments in other; various functions that a farm can have (Variety goals).

The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.

The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / D. Robustness_3 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:1 het kabinet in het nieuwe GLB kiest voor verdere verduurzaming en ont..... (1:1171 [1:1324]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

het kabinet in het nieuwe GLB kiest voor verdere verduurzaming en ontwikkeling van de agrarische sector en voor aanpassing aan maatschappelijke wensen.

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:2 Een belangrijk onderdeel van de huidige hervorming van het GLB is de..... (2:1 [2:361]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Een belangrijk onderdeel van de huidige hervorming van het GLB is de vergroening van de eerste pijler, waarmee een deel van de directe betalingen wordt verbonden aan maatschappelijke doelen. Ik blijf met de vergroening nadrukkelijk streven naar een ambitieuze invulling, die leidt tot echte winst voor biodiversiteit en inpasbaar is in de bedrijfsvoering.

Comment: by buite049

Constrains the buffer resources direct payments by making them a bit harder to obtain due to stricter conditions regarding greening.

It is also used to change the homogeneity of the farming systems a bit - changing the production strategies without changing too much of the operational logics of the farms.

4 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:4 de vergroening met ambitie moet worden ingevuld, in een goede balans..... (3:1893 [3:1992]) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

de vergroening met ambitie moet worden ingevuld, in een goede balans tussen ecologie en economie.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:20 Tegelijkertijd heeft de sector een aantal belangrijke maatschappelijke..... (8:2205 [8:2512]) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Tegelijkertijd heeft de sector een aantal belangrijke maatschappelijke opgaven.

Hoewel de Nederlandse intensieve kalverhouderij belangrijke stappen heeft gezet op terreinen als dierenwelzijn, diergezondheid, vermindering antibioticagebruik en kwaliteitscontrole, acht ik verdere verbetering noodzakelijk.

Comment: by buite049

Goal is to improve the animal welfare, animal health, lessen the use of antibiotics and more quality checks in the meat sector. --> to improve other factors that come with producing meat. However it is an adjustment of the system to continue the current trajectory of producing meat.

Is about livestock farming. Thus not relevant for the Dutch case study of crop farming

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

7:31 Een uitzondering hierop is het LEADER-programma. Hierin worden mogelijk..... (13:886 [13:1176]) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Een uitzondering hierop is het LEADER-programma. Hierin worden mogelijkheden gecreeerd bijvoorbeeld voor het verstevigen van de stad-landrelatie (zie TK 28625-190), voor de (agro)toeristische infrastructuur en voor natuur- en milieueducatie in het kader van het programma Duurzaam Door.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

8:57 Organic Farming: New separate measure for greater visibility; (7:2036 [7:2097]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Organic Farming: New separate measure for greater visibility;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

8:58 Agri-environment - climate payments: Joint contracts, link to adequate..... (7:1882 [7:2030]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Agri-environment - climate payments: Joint contracts, link to adequate training/information, greater flexibility when extending initial contracts,;

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:10 while at the same time shifting the emphasis on to stricter environm..... (2:3211 [2:3379]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

while at the same time shifting the emphasis on to stricter environmental and animal welfare rules, which farmers have to follow in order to receive the payments.

Comment: by buite049

There are some extra rules in place for farmers to receive direct payments related to the environment and animal welfare. But these are basic --> slightly enabling variety.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:17 But direct payments do not just provide farmers an element of certain..... (3:3296 [3:3522]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

But direct payments do not just provide farmers an element of certainty in an uncertain world. They also enhance the other roles that farmers play in protecting the environment and helping to development the rural economy

Comment: by buite049

The goal of direct payments (the buffer resource) is a bit expanded to also include a more variety of reasons why the direct payments are usefull.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:18 Direct payments also contribute to the sustainable management of nat..... (3:3848 [3:4036]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Direct payments also contribute to the sustainable management of natural resources and help contribute to the EU's wider efforts to tackle both the causes and effects of climate change.

Comment: by buite049

The goal of direct payments (the buffer resource) is a bit expanded to also include that it would improve sustainable management nad helps contribute to tackling climate change. It seems more that this is used to legitimise the direct payments better.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:48 Over the years, the CAP has played an increasingly important role in..... (8:1 [8:348]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Over the years, the CAP has played an increasingly important role in maintaining and/or supporting the development of sustainable agriculture across the EU by promoting environmentally and climate friendly practices.

The introduction of the new green direct payment under the 2013 reform was a further significant step in this direction.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:53 Growing a greater variety of crops helps make soil and ecosystems more..... (8:883 [8:1067]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Growing a greater variety of crops helps make soil and ecosystems more resilient. It helps to halt degradation of soils and soil erosion and therefore also helps production capacity.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to make the soil and ecosystems more resilient and halt their degradation, but is then stated that this is done to make sure the production capacity of farm (to continue its most important functionality) --? fairly enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:54 Permanent pasture is a very effective means of locking carbon away and..... (8:1593 [8:1802]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Permanent pasture is a very effective means of locking carbon away and thus helps to reduce global warming.

Preserving environmentally sensitive grassland conserves soil carbon and protects grassland habitats

Comment: by buite049

*an environmentally driven goal --> enabling
However the maintenance of permanent grassland also has the effect that arable land cannot be used by farmers to continue their function of producing food --> constraining
--> fairly enabling*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:55 with a view to safeguarding and improving biodiversity on farms (8:2444 [8:2506]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

with a view to safeguarding and improving biodiversity on farms

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:67 but the common agricultural policy is not just about making sure Eur..... (12:115 [12:432]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

but the common agricultural policy is not just about making sure Europe can feed itself. It also contributes to some of the other key objectives of the European Union: boosting jobs and growth in the food and farming sector, tackling sustainability and climate change and delivering wider benefits for society.

Comment: by buite049

*The CAP contributes also to other goals than "no more hunger in Europe". The important functionality of producing food stays at the core, but these goals show that there is also a bit room to also deal with external drivers and internal process --> adaptability Variety -
-> fairly enabling*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

9:68 Through the direct payments and its rural development programmes, it a..... (12:1029 [12:1520]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Through the direct payments and its rural development programmes, it also helps the EU meet its commitments to the UN sustainable development goals through its active role in promoting the approach of “producing more with less”, at the same time as actively working to mitigate the effects of climate change. It is also the least tradedistortive farm policy compared to other big producing countries and has therefore a positive contribution to the UN’s sustainable development goals.

Comment: by buite049

The CAP contributes also to other goals then "no more hunger in Europe". The important functionality of producing food stays at the core, but the CAP also contributes to other international goals and help with promoting environmental / climate friendly agricultural practices + the less trade-distortive farm policy. The goals show that their is also a bit of room to also deal with external drivers and internal process --> adaptability Variety --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:2 Het kabinet richt zich op verdere verduurzaming en ontwikkeling van de..... (1:1884 [1:2019]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het kabinet richt zich op verdere verduurzaming en ontwikkeling van de agrarische sector en op aanpassing aan maatschappelijke wensen.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:3 De richting die ik het nieuwe GLB wil geven met de invulling van de ve..... (2:351 [2:722]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De richting die ik het nieuwe GLB wil geven met de invulling van de vergroening zal bijdragen aan de maatschappelijk inbedding van het Europese gemeenschappelijk landbouwbeleid. Bij de invulling van de vergroening maak ik nadrukkelijk gebruik van de voorliggende mogelijkheden. De vergroening zal ik ambitieus, maar passend bij de Nederlandse situatie invullen.

Comment: by buite049

Green should ambitious, but suitable for the Dutch context --> adaptability 3

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:4 Mijn ambitie is om de Nederlandse land- en tuinbouw bij te laten dra..... (2:879 [2:1073]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Mijn ambitie is om de Nederlandse land- en tuinbouw bij te laten dragen aan (inter)nationale vraagstukken over voedselzekerheid, biodiversiteit, energie, water, klimaat en dierenwelzijn.

Comment: by buite049

| *aiming to reach multiple objectives through agriculture --> variety --> enables*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:6 een ambitieuze maar passende vergroening en een POP3 dat innovatie e..... (2:1556 [2:1768]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

een ambitieuze maar passende vergroening en een POP3 dat innovatie en verduurzaming stimuleert en daarnaast bijdraagt aan het behalen van internationale doelen op het gebied van natuur- en waterkwaliteit.

Comment: by buite049

| *The goal is focused on multiple desired outcomes*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:13 Ik vind het van groot belang de vergroening van directe betalingen met..... (4:166 [4:459]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik vind het van groot belang de vergroening van directe betalingen met ambitie in te vullen. Een goede (agro)biodiversiteit, milieukwaliteit en bescherming van het klimaat zijn van groot belang voor de kwaliteit van onze leefomgeving en daarmee ook voor een duurzame agrarische productie.

Comment: by buite049

| *Multiple goals are mentioned that should be reached and could contribute to the living environment and sustainable agricultural practices.
Van groot belang = very important
met ambitie = ambitious*

| --> this goal is very enabling

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:17 1. Gewasdiversificatie. Bedrijven moeten op bouwland minstens drie gew..... (4:933 [4:1017]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

1. Gewasdiversificatie. Bedrijven moeten op bouwland minstens drie gewassen telen.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:20 Blijvend grasland is land dat vijf jaar of langer grasland is. Kwetsba..... (4:1696 [4:2048]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Blijvend grasland is land dat vijf jaar of langer grasland is. Kwetsbare blijvende graslanden binnen Natura 2000-gebieden mogen volgens de verordening niet worden geploegd of omgezet, maar wel worden doorgezaaid. Dit verbod zal in Nederland gelden voor alle blijvende graslanden binnen Natura 2000-gebieden ter bescherming van de biodiversiteit.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:29 Met de voorgestelde invulling wordt een belangrijke biodiversiteitwinst..... (6:741 [6:900]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Met de voorgestelde invulling wordt een belangrijke biodiversiteitswinst geboekt en wordt de teelt van duurzaam geproduceerde veevoedergewassen gestimuleerd.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:47 De middelen van het nieuwe GLB zullen benut worden om agrariërs te o..... (9:1357 [9:1589]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De middelen van het nieuwe GLB zullen benut worden om agrariërs te ondersteunen bij investeringen en innovaties om te voldoen aan internationale doelen, met name op het gebied van de Nitraatrichtlijn en de Kaderrichtlijn water.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:48 Het kabinet wil met POP3 bijdragen aan internationale doelen op het ge..... (9:2050 [9:2729]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het kabinet wil met POP3 bijdragen aan internationale doelen op het gebied van natuur, milieu en water. De Europese doelstellingen van de Vogel- en Habitatrictlijnen, de Nitraatrichtlijn en de Kaderrichtlijn water zijn hierbij van groot belang. Hierbij stelt het kabinet het boerenerf centraal. Het kabinet wil dat POP3 ook bijdraagt aan een concurrerende, innovatieve, duurzame en toekomstbestendige agrarische sector door in te zetten op thema's zoals klimaat, energie, milieu, dierenwelzijn, voedselkwaliteit- en veiligheid, dier- en plantgezondheid en ruimtelijke ordening. POP3 draagt zo bij aan de EU2020 strategie voor slimme, duurzame en inclusieve groei.

Comment: by buite049

POP3 is the instrument used for the development rural areas

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:51 Veelal is er sprake van een combinatie van opgaven voor een bepaald ge..... (10:1292 [10:1508]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Veelal is er sprake van een combinatie van opgaven voor een bepaald gebied of sector. POP3 zorgt dat combinaties van meerdere maatregelen in samenhang kunnen worden toegespitst op bepaalde gebieden of sectoren.

Comment: by buite049

POP3 offers and aims to integrate multiple means to tackle a combination of problems / issues in the area --> adaptability

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:60 Het aangegeven pakket van maatregelen op het gebied van innovatie en..... (11:2093 [11:2235]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het aangegeven pakket van maatregelen op het gebied van innovatie en concurrentiekrachtversterking zal worden uitgevoerd door de provincies

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:64 Herstructurering van landbouwbedrijven draagt tevens bij aan de real..... (12:371 [12:560]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Herstructurering van landbouwbedrijven draagt tevens bij aan de realisatie van (internationale) doelen rondom water, Programmatische Aanpak Stikstof (PAS), biodiversiteit en Natura-2000.

Comment: by buite049

The restructuring of the farm businesses can also contribute to other (environmental / international) goals - a variety / multiple goals , however these feels as more secondary goals. The primary goal is to increase the efficiency --> therefor fairly enables variety.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:67 Het betreft een combinatie van mogelijkheden ter verbetering van de..... (12:796 [12:1258]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het betreft een combinatie van mogelijkheden ter verbetering van de verkaveling, de toegankelijkheid en de landbouwinfrastructuur enerzijds en verbetering van de ligging van landbouwbedrijven uit het oogpunt van milieu-, water- en natuurdoelen anderzijds. Verder komen er ook mogelijkheden voor de verbetering van de energie-infrastructuur van land- en tuinbouwbedrijven om geproduceerde energie te kunnen delen met andere bedrijven en instellingen.

Comment: by buite049

A set of different combined goals to which the restructuring of farm businesses could contribute --> enabling variety goals (3)

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:74 Het bevorderen van een emissiearme landbouw en het optimaliseren van h..... (14:128 [14:862]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Het bevorderen van een emissiearme landbouw en het optimaliseren van het waterbeheer voor de landbouw staan hierbij centraal. Een bedrag van ongeveer €25 miljoen, waarvan de helft Europese cofinanciering, wil ik inzetten voor een samenhangend pakket van maatregelen, waarbij het accent ligt op effectgerichte maatregelen voor de landbouw. Hierbij is naast het generieke beleid uit het

actieprogramma, gebiedsgericht maatwerk nodig gericht op bestrijding van eutrofiering en de reductie van uit- en afspoeling van nutriënten. Zowel inrichting- en beheermaatregelen van watersystemen als ook investeringen en innovaties in de landbouw kunnen daarbij een rol spelen. Daarnaast kunnen ook blauwe diensten ingericht worden

Comment: by buite049

An ambitious goal in which the emission of agriculture and the water management of agricultural practices should be adjusted. It will be done through a integrated set of measures - with a general policy and a action programm specific for areas. --> enabling variety

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:77 Met de (verplichte) Nederlandse inzet op LEADER wordt bijgedragen aan..... (14:1258 [14:1872]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Met de (verplichte) Nederlandse inzet op LEADER wordt bijgedragen aan de sociaal-economische ontwikkeling en werkgelegenheid op het platteland, de innovaties op agrarische bedrijven, de leefomgeving van de agrarische sector, jonge boeren en hun gezinnen en aan samenwerking in 'krimp'-gebieden waarbij alle actoren zich inspannen voor een sociaal en economisch vitaal platteland. Juist ook voor jonge boeren zijn voldoende voorzieningen essentieel.

Ook heb ik met de provincies afgesproken dat LEADER bijdraagt aan projecten voor duurzaamheidseducatie in het kader van het programma Duurzaam Door.

Comment: by buite049

LEADER seems to be mostly focused on improving rural areas & the agricultural sector for the future. It is aware of that there are multiple problems in the area and that rural areas are more than places where food is produced.

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

10:78 Bij LEADER gaat het per definitie om integrale projecten die meerdere..... (14:2275 [14:2572]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Bij LEADER gaat het per definitie om integrale projecten die meerdere doelen en prioriteiten dienen (zoals innovatie, energie, water, natuur, werkgelegenheid).

Specifiek kan het extra bijdragen aan het creëren van werkgelegenheid in geval van bevolkingsdaling in krimp- en anticipeerregio's.

Comment: by buite049

LEADER is especially focused on projects with multiple and integrated aims related to multiple themes --> variety very enabling

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:26 Wij willen de provincie Groningen in de komende jaren op de kaart zett..... (9:471 [9:872]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen de provincie Groningen in de komende jaren op de kaart zetten als 'Regio van de Smaak', vooral om de productie en de omzet van duurzame (biologische) streekproducten te stimuleren.

Productie voor de lokale markt kan een belangrijke bijdrage leveren aan de verduurzaming, bijvoorbeeld doordat transportlijnen korter worden, maar ook omdat geldstromen binnen de eigen regio blijven.

Comment: by buite049

stimulate and promote the production of organic regional products --> promotion of organic production --> variety goals. However, the goal does not feel that radical. The aim is namely to promote the region as a "region of taste"--> slightly enabling

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:49 Minder energie verbruiken, meer energie produceren: De landbouw is een..... (11:2141 [11:2817]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Minder energie verbruiken, meer energie produceren: De landbouw is een belangrijke verbruiker van energie. Tegelijk is er binnen de sector ook veel potentie voor het produceren van energie, uit biomassa maar ook uit andere hernieuwbare bronnen. Een deel van deze potentie wordt al benut (zie hoofdstuk 3), maar bij de verdere verduurzaming van de sector spelen het verminderen van het energiegebruik en de mogelijkheden om lokaal energie te produceren een belangrijke rol.

Behalve verduurzaming brengt productie van energie ook een verbreding van de inkomensbasis voor gezinsbedrijven, zonder dat een fysieke uitbreiding van het bedrijf direct noodzakelijk is.

Comment: by buite049

*The goal is to reduce the use of energy and to increase the self-sufficiency of farms --> adaptability -->
it is also focused on energy production as an extra / new activity of farms (variety) as a way to produce income.
fairly enables adaptability*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:54 Te denken valt dan aan de productie van energie op het boerenerf of va..... (12:760 [12:962]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Te denken valt dan aan de productie van energie op het boerenerf of van groene grondstoffen, maar ook aan de bijdrage die de agrarische sector kan leveren aan producten voor een gezonde levensstijl.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:68 In de kennisnetwerken moet naast aandacht voor technologische innovati..... (9:2690 [9:3183]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

In de kennisnetwerken moet naast aandacht voor technologische innovaties aandacht zijn voor verbreding van de landbouwpraktijk. In de afgelopen jaren is de verbreding van de landbouw vooral in het agrarisch natuurbeheer tot ontwikkeling gekomen, maar er is ruimte voor meer activiteiten, onder andere op het gebied van zorg en recreatie en toerisme. Deels wordt die ontwikkeling gesteund vanuit de plannen voor het nieuwe Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid (maatschappelijke diensten).

Comment: by buite049

the goal is to increase the variety of practices on a farm through knowledge networks --> to increase the heterogeneity of activities --> enables variety

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:69 Ketengerichte aanpak, onder andere in de agrofood en energiegerelateer..... (10:999 [10:1087]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Ketengerichte aanpak, onder andere in de agrofood en energiegerelateerde activiteiten.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:70 Ontwikkeling richting de Biobased Economy (BBE) (10:790 [10:837]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Ontwikkeling richting de Biobased Economy (BBE)

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:71 Wij willen in de komende tijd kijken hoe wij onze inzet op landbouw zo..... (10:2320 [10:2969]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen in de komende tijd kijken hoe wij onze inzet op landbouw zo vorm kunnen geven, dat optimaal gebruik gemaakt kan worden van andere budgetten binnen GLB, EU-fondsen en de Rijksbegroting en de eigen provinciale middelen, om daarmee de mogelijkheden voor het realiseren van innovatie-, duurzaamheids- en vergroeningsdoelstellingen zoveel mogelijk te behouden. Daarbij kan onder andere ook gekeken worden naar het Regiopark Groningen-Assen, LEADER, de Agenda voor de Veenkoloniën en waddenfonds.

Overigens realiseren wij ons dat de druk op deze budgetten groot is en de mogelijkheden om daar gebruik van te maken beperkt zijn.

Comment: by buite049

*Making use of different sources of funding to support the agricultural sector. But fundings is used for innovative projects / groups. The possibility to use these funds is small.
therefore slightly enabling robustness buffer resources*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

12:72 Verder willen wij kijken of naast subsidies ook andere vormen van fina..... (10:2970 [10:3373]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Verder willen wij kijken of naast subsidies ook andere vormen van financiering mogelijk zijn (fondsvorming, streekrekeningen etc.). Wij hopen daarmee duurzame innovatie een meer structurele plek in de bedrijfsvoering van landbouwbedrijven te kunnen geven. Landbouw is een belangrijke economische sector en als zondanig kunnen relevante projecten in principe ook gebruik maken van EZ-budgetten.

Comment: by buite049

financial support -> could argue that is just a buffer resource, but hte aim is focused on innovation. It therefore does not discourage innovation

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

15:44 Finally, the constraint on the EFA aims at maintaining, and possibly i..... (52:2537 [52:2630]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Finally, the constraint on the EFA aims at maintaining, and possibly increasing, biodiversity;

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

15:70 Farmers entering the scheme are exempted both from ‘green payment’ re..... (57:776 [57:894]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Farmers entering the scheme are exempted both from ‘green payment’ requirements and from cross-compliance conditions.

Comment: by buite049

Constraints the introduction of variety as farmers that enter this scheme are exempted from greening requirements and cross-compliance - measures that ask farmers to vary their activities for different goals, instead of only traditionallly supplying food

2 Codes:

H. Adaptability_1 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

15:79 This tool may be used either to strengthen the rural development poli..... (65:2994 [65:3066]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

This tool may be used either to strengthen the rural development policy

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

15:82 introduced in order to achieve a better balance between policy tools..... (66:730 [66:891]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

introduced in order to achieve a better balance between policy tools designed to promote sustainable agriculture and those designed to promote rural development

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:4 climate change and sustainable management of natural resources; (3:636 [3:700]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

climate change and sustainable management of natural resources;

1 Codes:

M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:29 In addition, the CAP promotes agricultural practices such as safeguarding the scenic value of the landscape — in line with what the public wants. (9:2602 [9:2752]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

In addition, the CAP promotes agricultural practices such as safeguarding the scenic value of the landscape — in line with what the public wants.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:34 farm in a manner that reduces emissions of greenhouse gases; (11:991 [11:1052]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

farm in a manner that reduces emissions of greenhouse gases;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:35 use eco-friendly farming techniques; (11:1057 [11:1092]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

use eco-friendly farming techniques;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:36 meet public health, environmental and animal welfare standards; (11:1097 [11:1161]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

meet public health, environmental and animal welfare standards;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:47 specialised types of production such as organic farming; (13:29 [13:87]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

specialised types of production such as organic farming;

Comment: by buite049

encourage specialised farming / organic farming --> slightly enabling variety --> encouraging is not that drastic.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

17:55 At the global level, food production will have to increase to feed a..... (15:262 [15:553]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countries

At the global level, food production will have to increase to feed a global population that is expected to rise considerably in the future. The EU, through the CAP, plays a significant role in meeting this challenge. This is why it needs to continue investing in its farming sector.

Comment: by buite049

*legitimises the current CAP: it is good that we support our agricultural sector in this way as food production is majorily necessary.
It varies the CAP as it is focused on the developing countries and the world instead of the EU itself. But this is also a way of legitimising the CAP*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / E. Robustness_4 / I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

18:7 Het creëren van meer toegevoegde waarde per hectare door schaalvergr..... (7:570 [7:748]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Het creëren van meer toegevoegde waarde per hectare door schaalvergroting, efficiëntere technieken, producten met een hogere waarde of productie van grondstoffen en energie;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

18:8 De vergroening en landschappelijke inpassing met aandacht voor de du..... (7:754 [7:922]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

De vergroening en landschappelijke inpassing met aandacht voor de duurzaamheidseisen voor bodem, water, landschap, energie, dierenwelzijn en arbeidsomstandigheden;

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

18:27 het streven van de provincie Groningen om de reguliere landbouw verd..... (10:264 [10:455]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

het streven van de provincie Groningen om de reguliere landbouw verder te verduurzamen, met oog voor zaken als dierenwelzijn, natuur en landschap en het vergroten van de biodiversiteit.

Comment: by buite049

| *aim to further increase the sustainability of the agricultural sector --> fairly enables*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

18:57 De landbouw kan daarnaast onder andere een belangrijke rol vervullen..... (9:2851 [9:3284]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

De landbouw kan daarnaast onder andere een belangrijke rol vervullen in het realiseren van energiedoelstellingen, bijvoorbeeld door ruimte te maken voor zonnepanelen op daken, door het neerzetten van (kleine) windturbines en door zelf te besparen op het verbruik van energie.

In dorps(energie)coöperaties kunnen de boeren rondom het dorp een rol spelen als leverancier van de benodigde elektriciteit, gas en warmte.

Comment: by buite049

agriculture can also contribute to other goals/activities as realising energy goals -> they can help by producing energy through wind turbines / solar cells and reducing energy consumption. They can also become energy producers for local communities. --> this is a goal that is aimed at creating variety within the farmers activity --> enables variety.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / M. Adapt_variety_tailored_goals

Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

58 Quotations:

2:4 and for pillar 2 by 7.6% (in 2011 prices). (3:1295 [3:1340]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

and for pillar 2 by 7.6% (in 2011 prices).

Comment: by buite049

Constraints variety instruments

The financial budget for Pillar 2, which is focused on rural development --> various other themes than only agricultural production /. market-related expenditures --> is cut, and therefore the instruments (financial means) to realise variety goals is constrained

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

2:25 three obligatory agricultural practices, namely maintenance of perman..... (7:256 [7:392]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

three obligatory agricultural practices, namely maintenance of permanent grassland, ecological focus areas and crop diversification

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

2:28 The focus of the second pillar on sustainability is clearly visible..... (7:774 [7:1396]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

The focus of the second pillar on sustainability is clearly visible by the fact that at least 30% of the budget of each Rural Development programme must be reserved for voluntary measures that are beneficial for the environment and climate change. These

include agri–environmentalclimate measures, organic farming, Areas of Natural Constraints (ANC), Natura 2000 areas, forestry measures and investments which are beneficial for the environment or climate. All these measures contribute significantly to environmental enhancement and climate change because they are adapted to local needs.

Comment: by buite049

It enables variety because it is focused on the environment and climate, however the measures in the second pillar are voluntary.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

3:65 De Groene Zetmeelaardappel: een experimenteel project waarin FAB-rande..... (24:502 [24:755]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

De Groene Zetmeelaardappel: een experimenteel project waarin FAB-randen, spuitsporen, vrijgespeelde kopakkers en wijken worden gecombineerd en waarin wordt verkend in hoeverre ze een bijdrage kunnen leveren aan de vergroening in de Veenkoloniën

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

3:87 4.000.000 (33:746 [33:754]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

4.000.000

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

3:88 5.000.000 (33:641 [33:649]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

5.000.000

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

3:90 5.500.000 (33:126 [33:134]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

5.500.000

Comment: by buite049

Finances for the innovations related to water and soil. Integrative approaches

1 Codes:

N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

4:17 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:62:632-3:464:754) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

Natuur en landschap	43,2	43,2	86,4
• Agrarisch natuurbeheer inclusief ganzen conform natuurpact	35,0	35,0	70,0
• Hydrologische maatregelen in het kader van Programmatische Aanpak Stikstof (PAS) conform natuurpact	5,0	5,0	10,0
• Aanvullende middelen voor aanleg, beheer en herstel landschapselementen	3,2	3,2	6,4

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

5:1 De vergroening van het GLB bestaat uit drie maatregelen: de gewasdiver..... (1:1858 [1:2053]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

De vergroening van het GLB bestaat uit drie maatregelen: de gewasdiversificatie, het behoud van blijvend grasland en de invulling van ecologische aandachtsgebieden (ecological focus area, EFA).

Comment: by buite049

slightly enabling variety.

The instrument is aiming for more diversity through greening on farms. But the three measures are not major changing measures.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

5:12 Om binnen dit duurzaamheidscertificaat als equivalent pakket te kunnen..... (3:1381 [3:1676]) - D 5: (Dijksma, 2014C) [NL] kamerbrief-wijzigingen-invulling-van-de-vergroening-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid-glb (1)

Om binnen dit duurzaamheidscertificaat als equivalent pakket te kunnen combineren met stikstofbindende gewassen en vanggewassen is het gebruik van gewasbeschermingsmiddelen en/of meststoffen verboden, evenals irrigatie, voortvloeiend uit de EU-Verordening 1307/2013, artikel 43 en Annex IX.

Comment: by buite049

These are conditions that need to be met in order to use a sustainability certificate instead of the other measures.

These conditions are focused on changing the production strategy of the farms but the operational logic of the farms will stay the same.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:61 M4.4 Support for non-productive investments linked to the achievement..... (18:689 [18:798]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M4.4 Support for non-productive investments linked to the achievement of agrienvironment-climate objectives

Comment: by buite049

Investments in other; various functions that a farm can have (Variety goals).

The instrument is that there is support for farmers to invest. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.

The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

4 Codes:

C. Robustness_2 / E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:63 M7.2 Support for investments in the creation, improvement or expansion..... (18:2657 [18:2838]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.2 Support for investments in the creation, improvement or expansion of all types of small scale infrastructure, including investments in renewable energy and energy saving

Comment: by buite049

The investments could be considered as a financial solution to overcome perturbations to make sure the farm can withstand them. The investments are a some sort of buffer resource (financial) to maintain the farm.

Investments in small infrastructure are meant to maintain the area and to allow the farms to continue their practices (protection of status quo).

However investments in renewable energy and energy saving are more adaptation - investing in other functions. The investments are financial inputs for other functions.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:69 Support for drawing up and updating of plans for the development of..... (18:2364 [18:2614]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Support for drawing up and updating of plans for the development of municipalities and villages in rural areas and their basic services and of protection and management plans relating to Natura 2000 sites and other areas of high nature value

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:70 Support for investments in the settingup, improvement or expansion of..... (19:130 [19:314]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Support for investments in the settingup, improvement or expansion of local basic services for the rural population including leisure and culture, and the related infrastructure

Comment: by buite049

*It is an instrument that is focused on a different theme than the regular agricultural activities --> enabling variety instrument
But the goal is to improve the rural area for the inhabitants. To make sure that the areas are livable --> to make sure they can continue on existing and that farmers can continue on with their jobs --> protection of status quo - slightly enabling*

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / C. Robustness_2 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:71 M7.5 Support for investments for public use in recreational infrastr..... (19:317 [19:456]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.5 Support for investments for public use in recreational infrastructure, tourist information and small scale tourism infrastructure

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:73 M7.7 Support for investments targeting the relocation of activities..... (19:748 [19:1025])
- D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M7.7 Support for investments targeting the relocation of activities and conversion of buildings or other facilities located inside or close to rural settlements, with a view to improving the quality of life or increasing the environmental performance of the settlement

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:74 M8.1 Support for afforestation/creation of woodland (19:1136 [19:1188]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.1 Support for afforestation/creation of woodland

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:78 M8.5 Support for investments improving the resilience and environmen..... (19:2686 [19:2787]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M8.5 Support for investments improving the resilience and environmental value of forest ecosystems

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:84 M16.5 Support for joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating..... (21:126 [21:317])
- D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.5 Support for joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating or adapting to climate change and for joint approaches to environmental projects and ongoing environmental practices

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:85 M16.6 Support for cooperation among supply chain actors for sustaina..... (21:320 [21:480]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.6 Support for cooperation among supply chain actors for sustainable provision of biomass for use in food and energy production and industrial processes

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:86 M16.9 Support for diversification of farming activities into activit..... (21:607 [21:806]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.9 Support for diversification of farming activities into activities concerning health care, social integration, community-supported agriculture and education about the environment and food

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:88 M11.1 Payment to convert to organic farming practices and methods (20:1186 [20:1252]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M11.1 Payment to convert to organic farming practices and methods

Comment: by buite049

It is just a financial compensation / subsidy to convert to organic farming, however it is a subsidy that does not discourage innovation but that promotes changing homogeneity of farms

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

6:89 M11.2 Payment to maintain organic farming practices and methods (20:1590 [20:1654]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M11.2 Payment to maintain organic farming practices and methods

Comment: by buite049

*financial compensation to keep organic farming in place.
The goal is however also to maintain this newer / environmental friendlier (niche) form of farming*

4 Codes:

D. Robustness_3 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:3 De vergroening van het GLB bestaat uit drie maatregelen: het behoud va..... (3:1056 [3:1299]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

De vergroening van het GLB bestaat uit drie maatregelen: het behoud van blijvend grasland, de gewasdiversificatie op bouwland en de verplichting 5% van het bouwland in te richten als ecologisch aandachtsgebied (ecological focus area, EFA).

Comment: by buite049

Measures to diversify farms / decrease homogeneity in context of environmental and climate mitigation . However, the measures are not that major --> slightly enabling

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:15 Wanneer het aandeel blijvend grasland meer dan 5% daalt ten opzichte..... (7:2227 [7:2557]) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Wanneer het aandeel blijvend grasland meer dan 5% daalt ten opzichte van 2012, ben ik verplicht om een individuele herinzaaiplicht op te leggen aan aanvragers die blijvend grasland hebben omgezet. De kans hierop is aanwezig, aangezien RVO.nl heeft geconstateerd dat het areaal blijvend grasland de afgelopen jaren is gedaald.

Comment: by buite049

It is a measure that increases the variety on the farms - less homogeneity. However, the measure of permanent grassland was not yet fully implemented and will only be done when the total amount of permanent grassland is lower than 5%. This meant that the situation was kept as it was. But if the measure will be used it will constrain the protection of the status quo.

4 Codes:

C. Robust_protect_status_quo_goals / D. Robustness_3 / I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:23 Zij kunnen het Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma 2014-2020 (POP3) ben..... (9:1913 [9:2125]) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Zij kunnen het Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma 2014-2020 (POP3) benutten voor innovatie en investeringen, en om samenwerking en marktconcepten te ontwikkelen, om daarmee de sector toekomstbestendig te maken.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:38 (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:77:448-19:466:496) - D 7: (Dijkma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

Natuur en landschap	43,2	-	43,2	86,4
agrarisch natuurbeheer (incl. ganzen), conform Natuurpact	35,0	-	35,0	70,0
hydrologische maatregelen PAS, conform Natuurpact	5,0	-	5,0	10,0
aanleg, beheer en herstel van landschapselementen	3,2	-	3,2	6,4

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

7:39 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:78:500-19:466:552) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

Verbetering van de waterkwaliteit	12,4	-	12,4	24,8
beheersvergoedingen waterdiensten	2,1	-	2,1	4,2
niet-productieve investeringen voor waterkwaliteit	9,0	-	9,0	17,9
verbetering waterkwaliteit door innovatie	1,3	-	1,3	2,6

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

8:19 The 3 basic practices foreseen are: • maintaining permanent grassla..... (3:3370 [4:374]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

The 3 basic practices foreseen are: • maintaining permanent grassland; and • crop diversification (a farmer must cultivate at least 2 crops when his arable land exceeds 10 hectares and at least 3 crops when his arable land exceeds 30 hectares. The main crop may cover at most 75% of arable land, and the two main crops at most 95% of the arable area);

4 • ensuring an “ecological focus area” of at least 5% of the arable area of the holding for most farms with an arable area larger than 15 hectares – i.e. field margins, hedges, trees, fallow land, landscape features, biotopes, buffer strips, afforested area. This figure may rise to 7% after a Commission report in 2017 and subject to a legislative proposal.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

8:27 The School Fruit Scheme and the School milk scheme are to be extend..... (5:2996 [5:3179]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

The School Fruit Scheme and the School milk scheme are to be extended, and the annual budget for the school fruit scheme is increased from EUR 90 to EUR 150 million per year.

Comment: by buite049

The instruments have a different goal than the traditional agricultural goals. It is also focused on the diets of young children (probably to make it more healthy). However not really clear how this would fit the scoring. --> not clear

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

8:48 Non-agricultural activities: Grants for start-up and development of mi..... (7:2882 [7:2979]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Non-agricultural activities: Grants for start-up and development of micro- and small businesses;

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

9:5 rural development (1:837 [1:855]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

rural development

Comment: by buite049

Rural development is a variety of different goals. Therefore variety. However this statement is not specific enough to give it a clear score

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

9:50 Crop diversification (8:860 [8:879]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Crop diversification

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

9:51 Maintenance of permanent grassland (8:1555 [8:1589]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Maintenance of permanent grassland

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

9:52 Ecological focus areas (8:2305 [8:2326]) - D 9: (EC, 2017B) [EU] CAP Explained Direct Payments for Farmers 2015-2020

Ecological focus areas

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:19 Ecologisch aandachtsgebied met een omvang van 5% van het bouwlandopp..... (4:1213 [4:1293]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ecologisch aandachtsgebied met een omvang van 5% van het bouwlandoppervlak.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:46 Hiervoor wil ik 20 miljoen benutten, een equivalent van de huidige art..... (9:1591 [9:1759]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Hiervoor wil ik 20 miljoen benutten, een equivalent van de huidige artikel 68 maatregelen. De provincies en waterschappen zijn bereid om dit bedrag te cofinancieren.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:71 De afspraken betekenen dat een bedrag van €40 miljoen per jaar aan E..... (13:800 [13:1126]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De afspraken betekenen dat een bedrag van €40 miljoen per jaar aan EU-cofinanciering uit POP3 tezamen met de extra middelen die het kabinet voor natuur heeft vrijgemaakt (gemiddeld 200 miljoen per jaar tot 2027) daarvoor wordt ingezet. Dit betreft €30 miljoen EUcofinanciering voor het stelsel van agrarisch natuurbeheer.

Comment: by buite049

The financial budget available for the nature-related goals, for instance agricultural nature management --> enables variety goals (4)

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:72 De hydrologische maatregelen in Natura-2000-gebieden in het kader van..... (13:1692 [13:2171]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De hydrologische maatregelen in Natura-2000-gebieden in het kader van de Programmatische Aanpak Stikstof (PAS) uit het Natuurpact zullen voor €5 miljoen uit het POP3-budget worden gefinancierd. De maatregelen die in het kader van POP3 worden gefinancierd zijn hydrologische maatregelen zoals onder andere de aanleg van regenwaterbuffers en stuwen, (waterconserverende) drainagesystemen en natte bufferzones, het omleggen van beken en het verhogen van waterpeilen.

Comment: by buite049

Financial budget for water-related goals These are hydrological means that are partly financed through the CAP --> fairly enabling variety

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:73 Daarnaast gaat voor aanleg- en inrichtingsmaatregelen €6 miljoen, waar..... (13:2434 [13:2706]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Daarnaast gaat voor aanleg- en inrichtingsmaatregelen €6 miljoen, waarvan de helft EU-cofinanciering en de andere helft cofinanciering van de provincies, naar aanleg en herstel van landschapselementen en inrichtingsmaatregelen voor specifieke beschermde soorten.

Comment: by buite049

Financial means for ecological restoration. It can partially be financed through POP 3 --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:76 De provincies hebben met de waterschappen afspraken gemaakt over de..... (14:1075 [14:1248]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De provincies hebben met de waterschappen afspraken gemaakt over de cofinanciering van de helft van de genoemde €25 miljoen voor het verbeteren van de waterkwaliteit.

Comment: by buite049

money available for improving the quality of water related to the agricultural sector.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:81 Samen met de provincies heb ik er voor gekozen om ruim €5 miljoen aan..... (15:128 [15:408]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Samen met de provincies heb ik er voor gekozen om ruim €5 miljoen aan Europese cofinanciering te besteden aan LEADER, inclusief Duurzaam Door projecten. De provincies zullen dit bedrag met eenzelfde bedrag cofinancieren, waarmee het totaal bedrag uitkomt op bijna €11 miljoen

Comment: by buite049

Money available for the (long-term) LEADER approach that is focused on a multitude of different themes related to the development of the rural area.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

10:84 Behoud van blijvend grasland. (4:1177 [4:1205]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Behoud van blijvend grasland.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

12:27 Ook voor de ontwikkeling van Groningen als Regio van de Smaak is tot 2..... (9:882 [9:999]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Ook voor de ontwikkeling van Groningen als Regio van de Smaak is tot 2015 € 250.000,- per jaar beschikbaar gesteld.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

12:58 Biodiversiteit; meer variatie In de verbreding van de landbouw is ee..... (12:4049 [13:432]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Biodiversiteit; meer variatie In de verbreding van de landbouw is een duidelijke trend naar meer agrarisch natuur- en landschapsbeheer (zie ook hoofdstuk 3). In de praktijk betekent dit onder ander weidevogelbeheer,

13 maar ook natuurlijk beheer van akker- en slootranden. Een grotere biodiversiteit in de randen is gunstig voor insecten, zoals bijen, maar ook voor andere dieren die op en rond akkers leven.

Met activiteiten in dat kader, maar ook met andere manieren van bodembewerking, het planten van andere gewassen en andere maaieregimes kunnen boeren een bijdrage leveren aan de (agrarische) biodiversiteit in onze provincie.

Comment: by buite049

*Adapting activities that can lead to increased biodiversity in rural areas --> adaptability
The instruments are not that groundbreaking. It is about slightly adapting the activities of farmers related to their main task producing food.
Slightly enabling variety*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

15:6 Rural development: the allocation of rural development funds among Mem..... (33:2559 [33:2978]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Rural development: the allocation of rural development funds among Member States was decided on the basis of objectives criteria and past performance. 16 countries will also receive ad hoc allocations for the initial three years (until 2016), 13 subject to a cofinancing rate of 100 %. The financial resources involved, in total EUR 5 556 million, are from the overall EU allocation to rural development policies.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

15:47 In the worst-case scenario, a farm not satisfying the requirements for..... (53:1440 [53:1645]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

In the worst-case scenario, a farm not satisfying the requirements for the 'green payment' will not only not receive any, but will also incur an administrative penalty. This will be gradually implemented:

Comment: by buite049

*The penalty is an instrument to make sure that the farms will (keep) satisfying the requirements for the green payment.
The penalty can thus be seen as an instrument to make sure that variety within the farm activities - and to create diverse outcomes - are implemented.*

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

15:85 The flexibility tool, regardless of the destination fund of the resour..... (66:2913 [66:3307]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The flexibility tool, regardless of the destination fund of the resources transferred (EAFRD or EAGF), has been chosen by 16 Member States. As mentioned above, 11 Member States have decided to move financial resources from Pillar I to Pillar II (Flanders, Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Greece, France, Latvia, Netherlands, Romania and United Kingdom excluding Northern Ireland),

Comment: by buite049

The Netherlands chose to move financial resources from Pillar I to Pillar II --> thus to the pillar of Rural Development.

Increases the financial funds for rural development - for a variety of other goals --> fairly enabling variety.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

15:92 The first requirement is the diversification of the arable crops grown..... (78:855 [78:1534]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

The first requirement is the diversification of the arable crops grown on their farms. If the farm has a UAA devoted to arable crops of 10-30 hectares, the farmer must introduce one alternative crop for at least the 25 % of the total UAA area. If the specialised UAA is over 30 hectares, the farmer must introduce two new crops, so that one crop does not exceed 75 % of the total UAA and two crops do not exceed 95 %. A second requirement has to do with the maintenance of pasture, and a third with the selection of 5 % of the farm area to be left un-cropped (Ecological Focus Area – EFA). The EFA can include buffer strips, hedges, specific landscape features and so on.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

15:111 Access to the ‘green payment’ is restricted to farmers entitled to rec..... (52:1023 [52:1477]) - D 15: (Henke et al., 2015) [EU] Implementation of the first pillar of the CAP 2014-2020 in the EU Member States

Access to the ‘green payment’ is restricted to farmers entitled to receive the basic payment (or payments under SAPS). In order to receive the ‘green payment’, a farm must satisfy three requirements in terms of agricultural practices beneficial for the

climate and the environment, specifically in terms of: crop diversification; maintaining existing permanent grassland; devoting part of the land to so-called Ecological Focus Areas (EFAs).

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

17:19 Rural development measures . National (sometimes regional) programme..... (7:1218 [7:1388]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

Rural development measures . National (sometimes regional) programmes of development are established to address the specific needs and challenges facing rural areas.

Comment: by buite049

Enabling (not very enabling as the instrument is not really specific) however is focused on multiple issues.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

17:26 they must maintain permanent grassland areas (9:2182 [9:2228]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

they must maintain permanent grassland areas

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

17:27 they must grow a minimum number of crops (9:2327 [9:2366]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

they must grow a minimum number of crops

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

17:28 must farm 5 % of their arable area in a manner that promotes biodive..... (9:2374 [9:2448]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our countrys

must farm 5 % of their arable area in a manner that promotes biodiversity

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

18:13 Een nieuw thema dat zich aandient en wat wel een mogelijkheid is voo..... (8:1723 [8:2257]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Een nieuw thema dat zich aandient en wat wel een mogelijkheid is voor verdere verduurzaming van de sector is de Natuurinclusieve Landbouw. Dit is een vernieuwende wijze om de relatie tussen landbouwproductie en biodiversiteit te versterken.

Zowel landelijk als in onze provincie bestaat inmiddels de nodige belangstelling om dit thema verder uit te werken. Door middel van een pilot in de akkerbouw wordt momenteel verkend of Natuurinclusieve Landbouw een impuls kan geven aan de verdere verduurzaming van de sector

Comment: by buite049

*Nature inclusive agriculture as a way to further increase the environmental sustainability of the sector --> is is a mean that can be used to adapt the production of food
adaptability variety --> fairly enables. It is a new way so it is not yet sure how it can support further sustainble development of the sector.*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

18:55 b. POP3 (3e Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma) Het POP3 biedt voor d..... (16:832 [16:1259]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

b. POP3 (3e Plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma) Het POP3 biedt voor de landbouw tot in ieder geval 2020 belangrijke mogelijkheden om de gewenste ontwikkeling naar verduurzaming en vernieuwing financieel te ondersteunen. Het gaat om Europese middelen aangevuld met provinciale cofinanciering (50%) bedoeld voor veelal grote, meerjarige samenwerkingsprojecten gericht op verduurzaming en innovatie van de landbouw.

Comment: by buite049

Financial support for innovation and sustainability through POP3. It is the instrument to potentially change the production strategies of farms in the region and create diversity within farming systems

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

18:56 Vanwege de oriëntatie op het verminderen van milieubelasting en he..... (8:2504 [8:2717]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Vanwege de oriëntatie op het verminderen van milieubelasting en het versterken van het ecosysteem kan met name Natuurinclusieve Landbouw van betekenis zijn voor de uitwerking en invulling van deze opgave.

Comment: by buite049

integrating a different mean to contribute to the goal of circulaire economy.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

18:59 5) Ondersteunen van projectinitiatieven: binnen het beschikbare budg..... (11:2234 [11:2467]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

5) Ondersteunen van projectinitiatieven: binnen het beschikbare budget wordt ruimte gecreëerd voor financiële ondersteuning van initiatieven en projecten.

Voorwaarde is dat zij bijdragen aan de hierboven genoemde doelstelling.

Comment: by buite049

Just financial support for the promotion of organic farming. It can thus just be regarded as a buffer resource / financial compensation. however, the financial support is used for projects that aim for a new (innovative) way of farming, and therefore not discouraging innovation. Perhaps the instrument is therefore adapts variety

2 Codes:

F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments

Adapt_social_learning_goals

32 Quotations:

2:21 Furthermore, there is a focus on bridging the gap between science..... (6:689 [6:1063]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Furthermore, there is a focus on bridging the gap between science and practice via the Farm Advisory System, as well as training and innovation 8 programmes. These instruments are aimed at helping the farm sector to adapt to new trends and

technologies, thus becoming more resource efficient, cost effective and capable of adapting to emerging challenges.

Comment: by buite049

Mostly focused on cognitive learning instead reflecting together on underlying assumptions.

Would therefore give it no high score regarding social learning. But see it as adaptation as it wants to make sure that farms can use new innovations.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

2:49 (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5 (9:22:374-9:290:408) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Content

1. Fostering knowledge transfer and innovation in agriculture, forestry, and rural areas

Comment: by buite049

slightly enabling (score 2) because it is about sharing knowledge, but is not specified in the goal how or why

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:8 Kennis & Innovatie: Ingezet wordt op de doorontwikkeling van KANON t..... (7:640 [7:968]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Kennis & Innovatie: Ingezet wordt op de doorontwikkeling van KANON tot een professioneel en innovatief "Kennisnetwerk Veenkoloniën". De Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën draagt hieraan bij. Het vernieuwde Kennisnetwerk richt zich de komende jaren vooral op het versterken van het agrarisch ondernemerschap in het gebied

1 Codes:

O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:19 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (10:92:308-10:364:401) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:28 het is de bedoeling van de diverse lopende innovatieprojecten de kennis en de innovaties zoveel mogelijk tot waarde te brengen voor alle agrarische ondernemers in het gebied. Daarbij willen de onderwijsinstellingen een actieve rol spelen, zowel in de analyse van de resultaten van de praktijknetwerken als in de vertaling naar ondernemers, werknemers en studenten. (13:1607 [13:1985]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

het is de bedoeling van de diverse lopende innovatieprojecten de kennis en de innovaties zoveel mogelijk tot waarde te brengen voor alle agrarische ondernemers in het gebied. Daarbij willen de onderwijsinstellingen een actieve rol spelen, zowel in de analyse van de resultaten van de praktijknetwerken als in de vertaling naar ondernemers, werknemers en studenten.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:32 Communicatie met alle betrokkenen en het ondersteunen van effectieve kennisdeling zijn daarbij belangrijk. (14:496 [14:605]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Communicatie met alle betrokkenen en het ondersteunen van effectieve kennisdeling zijn daarbij belangrijk.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:35 Ondernemersgroepen spelen hierbij een belangrijke rol om de kennis voor de praktijk toepasbaar te maken. Ook zullen tools worden ontwikkeld om de kennis in de praktijk toe te kunnen passen. Samen met het praktijkonderzoek en ketenpartijen zal worden bezien hoe hieraan invulling kan worden gegeven. (15:374 [15:685]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Ondernemersgroepen spelen hierbij een belangrijke rol om de kennis voor de praktijk toepasbaar te maken. Ook zullen tools worden ontwikkeld om de kennis in de praktijk toe te kunnen passen. Samen met het praktijkonderzoek en ketenpartijen zal worden bezien hoe hieraan invulling kan worden gegeven.

Comment: by buite049

The use of pilots to learn more about the use of water within the agricultural sector of the region. It is social learning as the pilots are meant to find ways for the water use to be better able to deal with disturbances, but the underlying paradigm stays the same. The system gets a bit adapted but not radically altered.

2 Codes:

O. Adapt_social_learning_goals / Q. Transformability_4

3:38 Verzamelen van kennis en inzicht over de verbetering van de bodemkwa..... (15:1845 [15:2115]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Verzamelen van kennis en inzicht over de verbetering van de bodemkwaliteit in de Veenkoloniën, op basis van eerder uitgevoerde projecten/praktijkonderzoek en lopende trajecten. Daarbij worden speerpunten en witte vlekken geïdentificeerd met de regionale partijen.

Comment: by buite049

together with regional actors the results of research will be discussed to identify challenges

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:39 kennisdeling door en tussen ondernemers door jaarlijkse kennis- en..... (16:60 [16:494]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

kennisdeling door en tussen ondernemers door jaarlijkse kennis- en praktijkdagen met demonstraties, workshops en lezingen gericht op bewustwording en kennisoverdracht (praktische tips en adviezen, ondernemersgroepen, website, nieuwsbrief, etc.). Ontwikkelen praktisch communicatiemateriaal voor ondernemers (bijvoorbeeld checklists, beslisbomen, instructievideo's, kleine apps, serie tips/korte artikelen voor vakpers).

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:40 Kennisontwikkeling (Janjo de Haan): ontwikkelen van nieuwe kennis op..... (16:497 [16:602]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Kennisontwikkeling (Janjo de Haan): ontwikkelen van nieuwe kennis op basis van de praktijkbehoefte.

Comment: by buite049

increasing the knowledge based on the practical demands -- meaning that there is an interaction between actors to have some sort of clue what the demand is. However this is not clear in this. --> not clear

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:41 waar kennis en ervaringen worden overgedragen op een wijze die leidt..... (16:1050 [16:1203]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

waar kennis en ervaringen worden overgedragen op een wijze die leidt tot toepassing in de praktijk. Dit zowel naar ondernemers als naar onderwijs.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:49 Ontwikkelen van het centrum met en door partijen die zich bezig houd..... (17:19 [17:247]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Ontwikkelen van het centrum met en door partijen die zich bezig houden met precisielandbouw toepassingen, werktuigen of diensten. Het plan uitbouwen zodat er een centrum ontstaat met regionale en landelijke uitstraling.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:57 Allerlei nieuwe scheidingstechnieken zullen getest moeten worden op..... (22:978 [22:1215]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Allerlei nieuwe scheidingstechnieken zullen getest moeten worden op hun toepasbaarheid op grote schaal. Hiervoor wordt samengewerkt met kennisinstellingen waaronder de RU Groningen, TU Delft, Wageningen UR en technologiebedrijven.

2 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:71 Het is een innovatieve opgave om op basis van kennis van genetica en..... (26:991 [26:1372]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Het is een innovatieve opgave om op basis van kennis van genetica en kennis van teelt management betere soja rassen te ontwikkelen. Nieuwe rassen die én geschikt zijn voor het Noord West Europese klimaat én voor akkerbouwers aantrekkelijk zijn te verbouwen. Daarnaast biedt het nieuwe mogelijkheden voor samenwerking tussen de melkveehouderij- en de akkerbouwsector.

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

3:79 We willen de relaties met de kennisinstellingen de komende jaren ver..... (29:406 [29:541]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

We willen de relaties met de kennisinstellingen de komende jaren verder versterken en uitbouwen gericht op InnovatieVeenkoloniën.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

4:8 Eenzelfde mogelijkheid wordt gecreëerd voor de regeling voor samenwe..... (2:2003 [2:2358]) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Eenzelfde mogelijkheid wordt gecreëerd voor de regeling voor samenwerking bij proefprojecten en innovatie.

Daarbij gelden als voorwaarden dat stadslandbouw bijdraagt aan de verduurzaming van de landbouw in het landelijk gebied en dat het een project betreft waarbij partijen worden bijeengebracht om nieuwe vormen van ondernemen te genereren.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to make cooperation within experimental projects and innovation regarding urban agriculture better possible. It is necessary that parties need to be brought together within the projects.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

6:38 strengthening the links between agriculture and forestry and research..... (16:3474 [16:3558]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

strengthening the links between agriculture and forestry and research and innovation;

Comment: by buite049

*slightly enabling social learning - it is about increasing the knowledge sharing between the two sectors / to better integrate knowledge.
However, it is not specifically mentioned that it is about increasing contact between different actors to come to new ideas in an interactive way.*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

8:41 Innovation: This key theme (and more specifically the planned European..... (7:166 [7:773]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Innovation: This key theme (and more specifically the planned European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity & Sustainability – the "EIP") will be served by various rural development measures such as "knowledge transfer", "cooperation" and

"investments in physical assets". The EIP will promote resource efficiency, productivity and the low-emission and climate-friendly/-resilient development of agriculture and forestry. This should be achieved, inter alia, through greater cooperation between agriculture and research in order to accelerate technological transfer to farmers;

Comment: by buite049

EIP is focused on innovation. Innovation needs to be reach to cooperation and knowledge sharing --> however not fully focused on the social interactions (social learning) --> but it is focused on learning to adapt. --> Fairly enabling social learning

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

8:47 Co-operation: Expanded possibilities to support technological, environ..... (7:2664 [7:2876]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

Co-operation: Expanded possibilities to support technological, environmental and commercial cooperation (e.g. pilot projects, joint environmental schemes, development of short supply chains and local markets);

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

10:28 De komende tijd wil ik deze invulling verder uitwerken in overleg met..... (6:1198 [6:1327]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

De komende tijd wil ik deze invulling verder uitwerken in overleg met het bedrijfsleven en andere maatschappelijke organisaties.

Comment: by buite049

*It is about learning during interaction.
But is seems for as a consultation before fully implementing the previous idea as a greening measure --> therefore slightly enabling*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

10:56 Vervolgens kan de kennisoverdracht in de vorm van trainingen, demons..... (11:1598 [11:1721]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Vervolgens kan de kennisoverdracht in de vorm van trainingen, demonstraties, praktijknetwerken verder worden gestimuleerd.

Comment: by buite049

*Knowledge sharing can be done in form of training sessions, demonstrations, networks for practice examples need to be stimulated.
Training sessions and demonstrations are simply only cognitive ways of sharing knowledge --> not enabling social learning.
However, the goals is also to stimulate knowledge networks around practical examples. Those networks are ways of socially exchanging ideas. --> slightly enabling*

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

12:4 Verduurzamen kan alleen in nauwe samenwerking met de sector, vandaar d..... (1:1354 [1:1603]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Verduurzamen kan alleen in nauwe samenwerking met de sector, vandaar dat wij momenteel een dialoog voeren met de sector en diverse maatschappelijke partijen om te kijken: wat we met elkaar willen bereiken en hoe we onze ambities kunnen waarmaken.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

12:22 Wij willen deze voorlopers ondersteunen bij de verspreiding van de ken..... (8:1136 [8:1432]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen deze voorlopers ondersteunen bij de verspreiding van de kennis die zij hebben opgedaan en hen helpen om hun voorsprong verder uit te bouwen en innovatief bezig te blijven. Zij kunnen daarmee een middengroep van ondernemers die nu voor belangrijke bedrijfskeuzes staan inspireren.

Comment: by buite049

Using leaders regarding innovative or sustainable agriculture to promote these ways of farming and to interact with other farmers and possibly convince to do the same --> it uses a social component to possible adapt the system --> adaptibility social learning, but is is not clear if it will uses learning method --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

12:29 Voor de middengroep van ondernemers die in de komende jaren voor belan..... (9:1992 [9:2485]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Voor de middengroep van ondernemers die in de komende jaren voor belangrijke bedrijfskeuzes komt te staan, kunnen de innoverende koplopers een belangrijke bron van inspiratie, kennis en ervaring zijn.

De kennisnetwerken van boeren, productschappen en kennisinstellingen kunnen hen ondersteunen om keuzes afgewogen te maken en de bedrijfsvoering verder te verduurzamen. Wij vragen van de koplopers om ons daarbij te helpen door als ambassadeurs richting de 'middengroep' op te treden.

Comment: by buite049

enabling (4) as the goal is specifically focused on transferring knowledge through social networks and interaction

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

12:38 Kennisuitwisseling met andere landen, waaronder minder ontwikkelde lan..... (10:843 [10:993]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Kennisuitwisseling met andere landen, waaronder minder ontwikkelde landen, op het gebied van duurzaam en klimaatbestendig produceren, agrofood en BBE

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

12:64 Naast geld kunnen initiatiefnemers soms ook een zetje in de goede rich..... (13:2621 [13:3050]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Naast geld kunnen initiatiefnemers soms ook een zetje in de goede richting gebruiken, bijvoorbeeld door ze in contact te brengen met kennisinstututen of met andere organisaties met specifieke kennis.

Wij willen in de komende jaren ons netwerk ook voor dat doel beschikbaar stellen en waar nodig uitbreiden. Daarbij zoeken wij nadrukkelijk de samenwerking met belangenorganisaties, productschappen en kennisinstellingen.

Comment: by buite049

specifically aimed at creating knowledge networks and initiating dialogs / social interation to share ideas that should help with development. --> social learning 4

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

17:18 the 'Leader approach' encourages local people to address local issue..... (7:1702 [7:1774]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

the 'Leader approach' encourages local people to address local issues.

Comment: by buite049

Engaging local people to participate and adress local issues. There is recognition of ideas of others and creating social cohesion in the area

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

17:32 In the future, our farmers will have to produce more with less. This..... (11:1906 [11:2326]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

In the future, our farmers will have to produce more with less. This could be achieved through the development of instruments, such as innovation partnerships, to promote innovation in agriculture by bridging the existing gap between research and farming practice and facilitating communication and cooperation among stakeholders (farmers, advisers, agro-business, scientists, administrations and others).

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

18:3 Het realiseren van cross-overs tussen landbouw en andere sectoren (b..... (7:927 [7:1166]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Het realiseren van cross-overs tussen landbouw en andere sectoren (b.v. medicinale voeding, combinaties van landbouw en toerisme); hiervoor is samenwerking tussen de landbouw en onderzoeks- en onderwijsinstellingen noodzakelijk.

Comment: by buite049

sharing knowledge between sectors --> enables social learning

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

18:18 Vanaf 2016 maken we als provincie mooie eerste stappen met de biolog..... (9:4 [9:316]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Vanaf 2016 maken we als provincie mooie eerste stappen met de biologische landbouw.

In het eerste jaar zijn er meerdere goed bezochte informatiebijeenkomsten geweest voor geïnteresseerde boeren. Hieruit zijn twee omschakelcursussen voortgekomen en gestart, voor zowel melkveehouders als akkerbouwers.

Comment: by buite049

Information days and specialised courses for farmers to learn and interact about sustainable farming / organic farming --> it however still feels more like cognitive learning --> slightly enables social learning as there were social events to talk and discuss organic farming

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

18:46 Onze inzet is dat de ontwikkelde meerjarige samenwerkingsagenda's..... (14:215 [14:466]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Onze inzet is dat de ontwikkelde meerjarige samenwerkingsagenda's (verder) zullen uitgroeien tot krachtige netwerken waarmee stevige projecten kunnen worden ontwikkeld en uitgevoerd met betekenis voor innovatie en verduurzaming van de sector

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

18:48 • Voortzetting en versterking van de ontwikkelde samenwerkingsagenda's (15:20 [15:89]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

• Voortzetting en versterking van de ontwikkelde samenwerkingsagenda's

Comment: by buite049

To continue and strengthen the social learning that takes place within collaborating groups

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / O. Adapt_social_learning_goals

Adapt_social_learning_instruments

47 Quotations:

**3:9 , waarbij het Rijk als startimpuls voor het Innovatieprogramma een b..... (7:1045 [7:1159])
- D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien**

, waarbij het Rijk als startimpuls voor het Innovatieprogramma een bedrag van 5 miljoen euro heeft toegezegd. I

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:18 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (10:141:429-10:325:443) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

A handwritten note in black ink on a light background that reads "2012 Rijk: 5 milj.€ start impuls".

Comment: by buite049

| *financial instrument that is used to realise a knowledge network in the region*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:24 Ambitie In 2013 zijn 65 nieuwe projecten gestart, die uitvoering g..... (12:32 [12:265]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Ambitie In 2013 zijn 65 nieuwe projecten gestart, die uitvoering geven aan de vernieuwing van de landbouw in de Veenkoloniën. Concreet gaat het hierbij om Praktijknetwerken (61) en Samenwerkings- en Innovatieprojecten (4).

Comment: by buite049

| *The projects are used to encourage learning within the sector in the region*

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:25 Momenteel zijn er bij deze projecten 350 ondernemers direct betrokke..... (13:5 [13:401]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Momenteel zijn er bij deze projecten 350 ondernemers direct betrokken. Er worden verschillende bijeenkomsten gehouden om de opgedane kennis en inzichten te delen met andere ondernemers. Alle informatie en tussenresultaten over de verschillende gestarte projecten worden gepresenteerd op de speciaal voor InnovatieVeenkolonien ontwikkelde website: www.InnovatieVeenkolonien.nl.

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:61 samengewerkt met de RU Groningen en eventueel Wetsus in Leeuwarden. (23:1294 [23:1362]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien
samengewerkt met de RU Groningen en eventueel Wetsus in Leeuwarden.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:69 Innovatie lupineketen is een vraaggestuurd open innovatie project, v..... (25:1409 [25:1650]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Innovatie lupineketen is een vraaggestuurd open innovatie project, van en door het bedrijfsleven waar kennisinstellingen uitgenodigd worden hun kennis te benutten en in samenwerking met het bedrijfsleven verder tot waarde te brengen.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:78 Verschillende ondernemers uit de keten hebben samen met kennisinstel..... (27:1049 [27:1772]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Verschillende ondernemers uit de keten hebben samen met kennisinstellingen en adviesorganisaties het Innovatieplatform Biobased & Agribusiness - PlantValue (gebaseerd op de verwaarding van plantinhoudsstoffen) opgericht. Het doel van dit platform is het ontwikkelen van duurzame economische bedrijvigheid door het realiseren van hoogwaardige en marktgestuurde productieketens voor de verwerkende industrie (o.a.

voeding, farma, fijn chemie en cosmetica).

Dit platform geeft vorm aan de onderlinge samenwerking tussen primaire productie, toeleveranciers en verwerkende industrie. Er is een dynamisch vitaal netwerk gebouwd, waarin consortia op basis van businesscases uitvoering geven aan ontwikkeling

1 Codes:

P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:80 De afgelopen jaren is er een sterke betrokkenheid opgebouwd tussen ken..... (29:14 [29:404]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

De afgelopen jaren is er een sterke betrokkenheid opgebouwd tussen kennisinstellingen als Wageningen UR, AOC Terra en Van Hall Larenstein bij regionale vraagstukken in de Veenkoloniën. Zo is, onder de vlag van de Agenda voor de Veenkoloniën, vanaf 2008

een Kenniswerkplaats actief, waar studenten, docenten en onderzoekers meewerken aan oplossingen voor regionale vraagstukken.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:81 Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën: de Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën is..... (29:603 [29:1177]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën: de Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën is een samenwerking tussen kennis- en onderwijsinstellingen (VHL, AOC Terra, Wageningen UR) en de regio Veenkoloniën. Voor de periode 2014-2015 is afgesproken dat de Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën integraal onderdeel wordt van InnovatieVeenkolonien. Dit betekent dat vraagstukken passen bij de projecten zoals beschreven in het innovatieprogramma. Maar ook dat het Innovatiecentrum te Valthermond als uitvalsbasis voor de activiteiten van de Kenniswerkplaats Veenkoloniën wordt benut.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:82 Centre of Expertise (HBO) en Centrum voor Innovatief Vakmanschap (MB..... (29:1183 [29:1475]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Centre of Expertise (HBO) en Centrum voor Innovatief Vakmanschap (MBO): de onderwijsinstellingen hebben van de Rijksoverheid de mogelijkheid gekregen een Centre of Expertise (HBO) en een Centrum voor Innovatief Vakmanschap (MBO) op te zetten voor de akkerbouw in Noord-Nederland.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:83 Om de betekenis van deze ontwikkelingen voor de Veenkoloniale ondern..... (30:519 [30:862]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Om de betekenis van deze ontwikkelingen voor de Veenkoloniale ondernemer in kaart te brengen zal enerzijds een verkennende studie naar de (mogelijke) gevolgen worden uitgevoerd, anderzijds zal met een groep akkerbouwers een pilot gericht op de bedrijfsstrategie worden gestart, in samenwerking met accountantskantoren, PPO en LEI.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:86 1.000.000 (33:937 [33:945]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov]
Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

1.000.000

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:89 1.000.000 (33:73 [33:82]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov]
Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

1.000.000

Comment: by buite049

finances for the continuation of innovative projects in the region which need to provide new information and are in collaboration with (local) stakeholders

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:91 2.000.000 (33:296 [33:304]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov]
Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

2.000.000

4 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Transformability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

3:92 2.250.000 (33:828 [33:837]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov]
Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

2.250.000

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

3:94 1.500.000 (33:611 [33:619]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov]
Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

1.500.000

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

4:10 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:61:408-3:471:432) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kennisoverdracht (trainingen, workshops en demonstratieprojecten) 	1,1	1,1	2,2
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Comment: by buite049

More about cognitive learning and gaining knowledge instead of the social aspect of bringing people together. Therefore slightly enabling (score 2)

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

4:12 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:66:482-3:470:518) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Samenwerking bij proefprojecten en innovatie 	1,9	1,9	3,8
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2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

4:16 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:62:517-3:474:550) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oprichting van operationele groepen Europees Innovatie Partnerschap (FTP) 	1,2	1,2	2,4
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2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

4:18 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (4:67:299-4:464:323) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandsonwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

LEADER¹	5,8	5,8	11,6
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2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:5 Stakeholder involvement Dutch stakeholders were engaged in the deci..... (51:1835 [51:2544]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Stakeholder involvement Dutch stakeholders were engaged in the decision-making process already early on. The main governmental department involved was the Ministry of Economic Affairs (former Ministry of Agriculture). The Ministry organised several conferences and launched a dedicated website (www.toekomstglb.nl) with an online consultation. Furthermore, a broad range of stakeholder organisations provided inputs to the process, e.g.

several farmer organisations, farm businesses, the provinces, Water Boards, nature organisations, etc. During the course of the implementation an important role is granted to the agrarian cooperatives and Water Boards for agrarian nature management schemes.

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:55 Support for short-term farm and forest management exchange as well a..... (18:131 [18:226]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

Support for short-term farm and forest management exchange as well as farm and forest visits

Comment: by buite049

exchange of information between two different subsectors of agriculture also through interaction (visits)

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:80 M16.1 Support for the establishment and operation of operational gro..... (20:2079 [20:2213]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.1 Support for the establishment and operation of operational groups of the EIP for agricultural productivity and sustainability

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:82 M16.3 Cooperation among small operators in organising joint work pro..... (20:2800 [20:2958]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.3 Cooperation among small operators in organising joint work processes and sharing facilities and resources, and for developing and marketing tourism

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:83 M16.4 Support for horizontal and vertical cooperation among supply..... (20:2961 [20:3250]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.4 Support for horizontal and vertical cooperation among supply chain actors for the establishment and development of short supply chains and local markets and for promotion activities in a local context relating to the development of short supply chains and local markets

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:84 M16.5 Support for joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating..... (21:126 [21:317]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.5 Support for joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating or adapting to climate change and for joint approaches to environmental projects and ongoing environmental practices

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

6:85 M16.6 Support for cooperation among supply chain actors for sustaina..... (21:320 [21:480]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.6 Support for cooperation among supply chain actors for sustainable provision of biomass for use in food and energy production and industrial processes

3 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / N. Adapt_variety_tailored_instruments / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

7:36 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:83:373-19:462:383) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

samenwerken bij proefprojecten en innovatie 1,9 - 1,9 3,8

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

7:41 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:80:384-19:461:394) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

oprichting van operationele groepen EIP 1,2 - 1,2 2,4

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

8:60 LEADER: Greater emphasis on awareness-raising and other preparatory s..... (7:3181 [7:3377]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

LEADER: Greater emphasis on awareness-raising and other preparatory support for strategies; promoting flexibility for operating with other funds in local areas, i.e. rural-urban co-operation;

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:20 Keukentafelgesprekken over de landschappelijke inpassing van uitbreidi..... (4:526 [4:693]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonderwerpen_2012-2015 (1)

Keukentafelgesprekken over de landschappelijke inpassing van uitbreidingsplannen spelen wat ons betreft een belangrijke rol bij het bepalen van die passende schaal.

Comment: by buite049

It is aimed to talk with farmers and other stakeholders to give form the landscape plans in rural areas --> enabling social learning

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:25 In het coalitieakkoord is tot en met 2015 jaarlijks € 250.000,- vrije..... (8:2583 [8:2865]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

In het coalitieakkoord is tot en met 2015 jaarlijks € 250.000,- vrijgemaakt voor de innovatieve kwaliteitssprongen. In eerste instantie zal dit geld deels gebruikt worden voor de dialoog met de landbouw en de ontwikkeling van een visie op de toekomst van de landbouw in Groningen

Comment: by buite049

First of all the budget will be used for dialogs / social interaction to develop a vision for the agriculture --> social learning is prioritised in the budget --> enabling

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:28 In Groningen zijn op dit moment onder andere kennisnetwerken actief..... (9:1660 [9:1991]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

In Groningen zijn op dit moment onder andere kennisnetwerken actief op het gebied van de pootaardappelteelt (Pootaardappelacademie), de akkerbouw (KANON), de melkveehouderij (Melkveeacademie) en de biologische sector (BIOWAD). In al deze netwerken komt ook de verduurzaming van de bedrijfsvoering nadrukkelijk aan de orde.

Comment: by buite049

Specific knowledge networks for the agricultural sector of the region --> fairly enabling adaptabilty social learning

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:36 Deze Agrodeal kan dienen als paraplu voor echt innovatieve projecten,..... (9:3762 [10:347]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Deze Agrodeal kan dienen als paraplu voor echt innovatieve projecten, waarin ketens worden gesloten en de samenhang binnen ketens groter wordt. Binnen sterke, samenhangende ketens

10 kunnen innovaties nog beter op gang komen.

Dit doen we via Noordelijk Overleg Landbouw Gedeputeerden en deeloverleg i.k.v. het Noordelijk Landbouwberaad krijgt dat verder vorm en inhoud. Ook het SNN wordt betrokken, we leggen namelijk een duidelijke link met de clustervorming in het kader van topsectoren Agrofood en Biobase economy.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:39 Vanaf medio 2012 organiseren wij een dialoog over de toekomst van de l..... (10:1135 [10:2166]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Vanaf medio 2012 organiseren wij een dialoog over de toekomst van de landbouw in Groningen. In dit dialoogproces worden de landbouw, natuur- en milieuorganisaties en andere stakeholders betrokken.

De dialoog bestaat uit twee fasen: een verkenningsfase en een visievormende fase.

Cruciaal onderdeel van de verkenningsfase zijn de gesprekken tussen stakeholders (landbouwers, vertegenwoordigers uit natuur- en milieuorganisaties, experts, andere betrokkenen) over een zestal thema's. Hoewel de aanpak van de thema's onderling verschilt is het resultaat voor elk thema gelijk: een document dat potentiële bouwstenen bevat voor onze visie met een handelingsperspectief ten behoeve van de duurzame ontwikkeling van de landbouw.

Met het presenteren van de bouwstenendocumenten start de visievormende fase. In deze fase, die naar verwachting in het najaar van 2012 en in het voorjaar van 2013 zal plaatsvinden wordt aan de hand van de bouwstenendocumenten een provinciale visie met handelingsperspectief opgesteld.

Comment: by buite049

Social learning

The conversations are held between different types of stakeholders and the results of the conversations are used to form visions and documents that present building blocks (dialogues about policies with the effect of being used in the policy)

Borderline between in-depth and social learning. --> slightly enabling In-depth learning as the results of the dialogs are used for the future.

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:45 In de afgelopen jaren hebben wij een aantal projecten ondersteund waar..... (11:424 [11:725]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

In de afgelopen jaren hebben wij een aantal projecten ondersteund waarin biologische en gangbare boeren kennis over hun bedrijfsvoering uitwisselden. Deze kennisnetwerken zijn een kans voor de verduurzaming van de gangbare landbouw en wij willen dergelijke kennisuitwisseling verder stimuleren.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

12:65 Met het topsectorenbeleid wil het Rijk de concurrentiekracht van het b..... (14:871 [14:1176]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Met het topsectorenbeleid wil het Rijk de concurrentiekracht van het bedrijfsleven versterken, door innovatie en samenwerking tussen kennisinstellingen, bedrijfsleven en overheid. Versterking van land- en tuinbouw op nationaal, Europees en mondiaal niveau maakt daarvan een belangrijk onderdeel uit.

1 Codes:

P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:9 • het benutten van ons bestuurlijk en ambtelijk netwerk (overleg,..... (7:1823 [7:1916]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

- het benutten van ons bestuurlijk en ambtelijk netwerk (overleg, lobby) • communicatie;

Comment: by buite049

Not clear if this really enhances social learning.

2 Codes:

G. Adaptability_0 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:20 1) Samenwerkingagenda's voor deelsectoren: de aardappelzetmeelsector..... (9:1031 [9:1484]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

1) Samenwerkingagenda's voor deelsectoren: de aardappelzetmeelsector (Innovatie Veenkoloniën, gestart in 2012), de melkveehouderij (Versnellingsagenda melkvee, gestart in 2015), de graansector (Oldambt) en de aardappelpootgoedsector in de noordelijke kleischil (Potato Valley, in november 2016 gestart).

2) Samenwerkingsprojecten voor specifieke thema's: het iconproject Bodem , Green deal Soja en het Project 'Vruchtbare Kringloop'.

Comment: by buite049

the creation of collaborating groups within agricultural sectors and themes to share knowledge and ideas.--> fairly enables social learning.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:26 Als noordelijke provincies juichen wij deze ontwikkeling toe en zijn..... (9:1950 [9:2216]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Als noordelijke provincies juichen wij deze ontwikkeling toe en zijn wij bereid, vanuit onze faciliterende rol, in voorkomende gevallen financiële ondersteuning te bieden, ook waar nodig in de benodigde faciliteiten en organisatie van samenwerkingsagenda's.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:30 In het voorjaar van 2016 zijn we van start gegaan met twee informati..... (10:2314 [11:304]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

In het voorjaar van 2016 zijn we van start gegaan met twee informatiebijeenkomsten voor geïnteresseerde landbouwers. Deze bijeenkomsten zijn door ruim 60 landbouwers bezocht. Hier zijn twee omschakelcursussen uit voortgekomen, een akkerbouw- en melkveehouderijcursus met in totaal 25 personen. Daarnaast zijn er 30 keukentafelgesprekken gevoerd tussen landbouwers en een adviseur. Zowel cursus als keukentafelgesprek zijn door de provincie Groningen ondersteund door een bijdrage te leveren in de kosten. Inmiddels hebben 5 boeren besloten om Wierum

10 (gedeeltelijk) hun bedrijf om te schakelen.

Verder is er een speciale uitgave van Ekoland (tijdschrift voor de biologische landbouwsector) uitgegeven. Eind 2016 zijn er nog twee themabijeenkomsten georganiseerd rondom het thema markt. Er is veel animo voor de georganiseerde activiteiten.

Comment: by buite049

conversations and social interaction to promote and inform organic farming --> fairly enables social learning

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:33 3) Demonstratiebedrijven: uit ervaring elders blijkt dat praktijkvoo..... (11:1406 [11:1895]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

3) Demonstratiebedrijven: uit ervaring elders blijkt dat praktijkvoorbeelden van doorslaggevende betekenis kunnen zijn bij de omschakeling naar biologische landbouw.

Omdat er in de provincie nog relatief weinig biologische landbouwbedrijven zijn, zijn er ook weinig praktische voorbeelden. Vanuit het programma 'Stimuleren Biologische Landbouw' zal worden verkend of er bedrijven zijn die hier een actieve rol in willen spelen en hoe de provincie hierin kan ondersteunen.

Comment: by buite049

It implies the promotion of a new business model and a change in how the goods are being produced.

It is making use of example farms to actively promote organic farming and to provide farmers with knowledge and stories based on experience --> social learning --> enables

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:35 Activiteiten kennis- en informatieoverdracht: binnen dit onderdeel w..... (11:917 [11:1242]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Activiteiten kennis- en informatieoverdracht: binnen dit onderdeel worden activiteiten opgepakt, waarmee beschikbare kennis en informatie wordt gedeeld met de doelgroep. Voorbeelden hiervan zijn keukentafelgesprekken, themabijeenkomsten, omschakelcursussen, studieclubs, excursies en voorlichtingsbijeenkomsten.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:36 4) Verkennen mogelijkheden bij uitgifte gronden: verkend zal worden..... (11:2069 [11:2230]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

4) Verkennen mogelijkheden bij uitgifte gronden: verkend zal worden of bij uitgifte van grond (verkoop of pacht) biologische bedrijven voorrang kunnen krijgen

Comment: by buite049

constrains the protection of the status quo.

The aim is to find out if the usual way of selling farmland can be adapted so that organic farming (non-traditional way of farming) has priority

1 Codes:

P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:62 1. Innovatie Veenkoloniën: gericht op verduurzaming en vernieuwing i..... (14:1573 [14:2089]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

1. Innovatie Veenkoloniën: gericht op verduurzaming en vernieuwing in het Veenkoloniaal gebied.

Uitvoeringskader is het Innovatieprogramma 2014- 2020. In het programma werken de provincies Groningen en Drenthe, een groot aantal bedrijven uit de Agrosector en onderwijsinstellingen samen.

4.4. Samenwerking in de sector 13 Er is een organisatie met een ‘regiegroep’, een Boerenraad en een (uitvoerend) programmabureau met een programmamanager. Innovatie Veenkoloniën is gevestigd in Valthermond.

2 Codes:

K. Adaptability_4 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:64 3. The Potato Valley: Fries-Groningse samenwerking voor de kennisont..... (14:2454 [14:2756]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

3. The Potato Valley: Fries-Groningse samenwerking voor de kennisontwikkeling in de pootgoedsector; begin november 2016 van start gegaan op initiatief van het bedrijf HZPC en LTO-Noord. Er is een stuurgroep met vertegenwoordigingen vanuit de sector en het bedrijfsleven en een projectleider.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

18:66 Verder is er een speciale uitgave van Ekoland (tijdschrift voor de b..... (11:51 [11:305]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Verder is er een speciale uitgave van Ekoland (tijdschrift voor de biologische landbouwsector) uitgegeven. Eind 2016 zijn er nog twee themabijeenkomsten georganiseerd rondom het thema markt. Er is veel animo voor de georganiseerde activiteiten.

Comment: by buite049

publishing an informative journal on organic farming and two more social events --> seem less like social learning events than the previous mentioned meetings --> therefore slightly enabling (2)

2 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments

Transform_long-term_goals

13 Quotations:

2:48 which, for a seven-year period, set out the actions to be undertaken..... (9:434 [9:574]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

which, for a seven-year period, set out the actions to be undertaken and the corresponding allocation of funding for these measures.

Comment: by buite049

| *7 year period = long term planning*

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

3:2 een duurzame en vitale agrosector in de Veenkoloniën, die per 2020..... (6:250 [6:362]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

een duurzame en vitale agrosector in de Veenkoloniën, die per 2020 onafhankelijk is van extra overheidssteun.

2 Codes:

Q. Transform_long-term_goals / Q. Transformability_4

3:7 De landbouw heeft op gebiedsniveau de mineralenkringlopen gesloten. H..... (7:236 [7:374]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

De landbouw heeft op gebiedsniveau de mineralenkringlopen gesloten.

Hiermee wordt een forse reductie van de CO₂-uitstoot behaald.

2 Codes:

Q. Transform_long-term_goals / Q. Transformability_4

3:16 InnovatieVeenkoloniën wil de gestelde ambities per 2020 gerealiseerd h..... (9:1391 [9:1467]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

InnovatieVeenkoloniën wil de gestelde ambities per 2020 gerealiseerd hebben.

Comment: by buite049

| *The ambition is to realise the ambitions (their goals) in 2020. Their ambition is thus a long-term plan*

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

3:31 De ambitie op het gebied van Water is om op korte termijn te beginne..... (14:181 [14:356]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

De ambitie op het gebied van Water is om op korte termijn te beginnen met het anticiperen op mogelijke klimaatsveranderingen en op de vastgelegde landbouwkundige ambitie.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is to participate on the long -term changes of climate change and on the agricultural ambitions.

The mindset with this part is that they will prepare for upcoming changes in the future.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

3:60 Dit onderdeel van het Potato Power project behelst onderzoek naar en..... (22:597 [22:959]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Dit onderdeel van het Potato Power project behelst onderzoek naar en implementatie van de isolatie en terugwinning van mineralen die afgezet kunnen worden naar de regionale tuin- en akkerbouw. De ambitie is om de mineralenkringloop in belangrijke mate te sluiten zonder dat dit gepaard gaat met de toevoeging van veel (extra) chemicaliën of energie.

Comment: by buite049

a closed loop is the aim - a fundamental change of the current system but still to provide important functionalities --> transformability score 4

2 Codes:

Q. Transform_long-term_goals / Q. Transformability_4

3:98 (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien (10:124:171-10:341:207) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Content

2 Codes:

Q. Transform_long-term_goals / Q. Transformability_4

10:49 Ik heb met de provincies een akkoord bereikt over de invulling van de..... (10:491 [10:617]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Ik heb met de provincies een akkoord bereikt over de invulling van de genoemde thema's binnen POP3 voor de periode 2014-2020.

Comment: by buite049

A policy plan that is longer than 5 years and focused on a variety of themes. It therefore enables slightly a transformation as the necessary means are in place for a longer period and the vision will also be more focus on the long-term

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

12:1 Onze ambitie is om sprongen te maken in verduurzaming: de Groningse la..... (1:686 [1:818]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

Onze ambitie is om sprongen te maken in verduurzaming: de Groningse landbouw als koploper in de duurzame ontwikkeling in Nederland.

Comment: by buite049

The goal is aimed at the long-term. It is an ambitious statement. It is therefore enabling. But it is not really clear / explicit and I think these ambitious statements can be a bit 'hollow' in policy document - are more used as an opener. --> slightly enabling

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

12:10 het moet anders met de landbouw, het moet duurzamer (2:1701 [2:1751]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonde_2012-2015 (1)

het moet anders met de landbouw, het moet duurzamer

Comment: by buite049

Agriculture needs to be done differently, it needs to be done in a sustainable manner --> A statement aimed at transformation --> long-term. --> But just as with the previous ambitious statement, it feels a bit hollow, but it does state that things need to change --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

12:11 Wij willen dat onze provincie koploper wordt in het verder duurzaam on..... (2:1756 [2:1854]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Wij willen dat onze provincie koploper wordt in het verder duurzaam ontwikkelen van de landbouw.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

12:35 een forse bijdrage te kunnen leveren aan het behalen van de EU2020-doe..... (9:3610 [9:3761]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

een forse bijdrage te kunnen leveren aan het behalen van de EU2020-doelen en tegelijk koploper blijven in de duurzame ontwikkeling van de sector.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / Q. Transform_long-term_goals

12:51 Op lange termijn is het doel om de landbouw CO₂-neutraal te laten werk..... (11:3922 [11:3997]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagonenda_2012-2015 (1)

Op lange termijn is het doel om de landbouw CO₂-neutraal te laten werken.

Comment: by buite049

On the long term the goal is to make the agricultural sector CO₂ Neutral

2 Codes:

Q. Transform_long-term_goals / Q. Transformability_4

Transform_long-term_instruments

0 Quotations

Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals

6 Quotations:

2:15 Competitiveness is addressed directly by changes to market mechanisms..... (5:2596 [5:2888]) - D 2: (EC, 2013B) [EU] Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief no 5

Competitiveness is addressed directly by changes to market mechanisms, particularly the removal of production constraints. All of the existing restrictions on production volumes for sugar, dairy and the wine sector will end, allowing farmers to respond to growing world demand.

5

Comment: by buite049

The removal of production constraints, so that farmers can respond to market developments focuses on short-term fluctuations. It removes an incentive which constrained the production of sugar dairy and wine. And the ability of farmers to respond to markets was constraint. It was an incentive that blocked farmers from producing more. By abolishing it the status quo gets dismantled --> transforming dismantling status quo - score 4

2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals

7:19 Eventuele maatregelen moeten zich richten op verduurzaming en toekoms..... (8:1269 [8:1456]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Eventuele maatregelen moeten zich richten op verduurzaming en toekomstbestendigheid van de betreffende sectoren, zodat zij vanaf 2019 geen uitzonderingspositie meer hoeven in te nemen.

Comment: by buite049

the Goal is to change these 'knelsectoren' in such a way that they are less dependent on major direct payments (as before the reform - based on historical references). These sectors need to become sustainable and future-proof. The old system of the direct payments is changed (economic structure) and make the existing situation untenable, so the stated goal is to help transform these sectors in such a way that they can still provide their functionalities.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals

7:46 Vleesstierbedrijven kennen nu zeer hoge toeslagen, oplopend tot vele..... (9:1616 [9:1801]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Vleesstierbedrijven kennen nu zeer hoge toeslagen, oplopend tot vele honderden euro's per afgeleverd dier. Deze situatie is niet meer te rechtvaardigen en past niet in het nieuwe GLB.

Comment: by buite049

explicitly stated that the old system is not the right one anymore.

2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_ goals

8:24 In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled..... (4:2104 [4:2297]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled a limited number of companies to claim Direct Payments, even though their primary business activity is not agricultural,

Comment: by buite049

The term active farmer is introduced to make the direct payments more selective and to reduce 'abuse'. --> dismantling incentives that protect the status quo. But also to make the payments more credible. The goal is to protect the direct payments to make sure it can continue--> to make the current system a bit more robust --> transformability score 2--> robustness score 4

2 Codes:

E. Robust_buffer_resources_goals / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_ goals

8:29 the end to the sugar quota regime on September 30, 2017, confirming..... (5:97 [5:650]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

the end to the sugar quota regime on September 30, 2017, confirming the indication of the 2005 sugar reform to put an end date for the quota regime while allowing for additional time for the sector to adjust. This will ensure improved competitiveness for EU producers on the domestic and world market alike (as EU exports are limited by WTO rules under quotas). This will also provide the sector with a long-term perspective. Ample supply on EU domestic markets at reasonable prices will also benefit the intermediate and final users of sugar

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_ goals

18:15 Ook circulaire economie wordt momenteel als provinciale opgave uitge..... (8:2366 [8:2503]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Ook circulaire economie wordt momenteel als provinciale opgave uitgewerkt met prioriteit voor de groene verbinding agro-chemie-afval.

Comment: by buite049

ciculaire economy is a change of the system --> dismantling status quo. However, it is still in its infancy --> the aim is ambitious --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / S. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_goals

Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

5 Quotations:

8:25 “Active farmers”: In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes whi..... (4:2086 [4:2813]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

“Active farmers”:

In order to iron out a number of legal loopholes which have enabled a limited number of companies to claim Direct Payments, even though their primary business activity is not agricultural, the reform tightens the rule on active farmers. A new negative list of professional business activities which should be excluded from receiving Direct Payments (covering airports, railway services, water works, real estate services and permanent sports & recreation grounds) will be mandatory for Member States, unless the individual businesses concerned can show that they have genuine farming activity. Member States will be able to extend the negative list to include further business activities.

Comment: by buite049

The term active farmer is introduced to make the direct payments more selective and to reduce 'abuse'. --> dismantling incentives that protect the status quo. But also to make the payments more credible. The goals is to protect the direct payments to make sure it can continue--> to make the current system a bit more robust --> transformability score 2--> robustness score 4

4 Codes:

E. Robustness_4 / F. Robust_buffer_resources_instruments / O. Transformability_2 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

8:28 end to the sugar quota regime on September 30, 2017, confirming the..... (5:100 [5:310]) - D 8: (EC, 2013A) [EU] CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements

end to the sugar quota regime on September 30, 2017, confirming the indication of the 2005 sugar reform to put an end date for the quota regime while allowing for additional time for the sector to adjust.

2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

18:2 de programmatische aanpak stikstof (PAS), gericht op de verminderin..... (6:560 [6:655]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

de programmatische aanpak stikstof (PAS), gericht op de vermindering van stikstof emissie.

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

18:17 Per 1 januari 2019 treedt in de Omgevingsvisie een verbod op uitbrei..... (8:2718 [8:2854]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Per 1 januari 2019 treedt in de Omgevingsvisie een verbod op uitbreiding voor alle bedrijven in de intensieve veehouderij in werking.

Comment: by Buite049

*Veehouderij (geen akkerbouw zoals in case)
Livestock farming is not allowed to expand. This is dismantling the current situation.
However is is about livestock farming, the Dutch case is mostly focused on potato and wheat farming --> not clear*

2 Codes:

M. Transformability_0 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

18:42 In de Omgevingsvisie en -verordening 2016- 2020 is aangegeven, dat er..... (13:174 [13:386]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

In de Omgevingsvisie en -verordening 2016- 2020 is aangegeven, dat er na 1 januari 2019 geen mogelijkheden meer zijn tot uitbreiding van intensieve veehouderijbedrijven (nieuwvestiging was al uitgesloten).

Comment: by buite049

about live stock farming not arable farming --> not clear

2 Codes:

M. Transformability_0 / T. Transform_dismantle_status quo incentives_instruments

Transform_In-depth_learning_goals

2 Quotations:

3:97 Door concreet in gebieden aan de slag te gaan met een maatregel of..... (14:607 [14:1017]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Door concreet in gebieden aan de slag te gaan met een maatregel of combinaties van maatregelen, wordt ervaring opgedaan die input geeft voor beleidsveranderingen en adequate en onderbouwde bestuurlijke besluiten. Op deze wijze wordt per pakket van maatregelen duidelijk gemaakt welke partijen meer of minder verantwoordelijk zijn, en of de geschetste maatregelen effectief zijn in de Veenkoloniën.

Comment: by buite049

"ervaringen opgedaan die input geeft voor beleidsveranderingen en adequate en onderbouwde bestuurlijke besluiten"--> the projects that are implemented for real lead to inputs for policies and decision making.

The things that are learned are used to discuss the future of (new) policies. --> therefore in-depth learning. However, I do not have the idea that there will be intensive reconsideration of paradigms

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / U. Transform_In-depth_learning_goals

17:33 EU research funds are devoted to developing new farming systems so t..... (11:1685 [11:1905]) - D 17: (EC, 2017A) [EU] Agriculture A partnership between Europe and Farmers. The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP) for our food, for our country

EU research funds are devoted to developing new farming systems so that farmers can respond to the many challenges that lie ahead — not least those of a changing climate and growing pressure on natural resources.

Comment: by buite049

Support to develop new farming systems that are better able to respond to challenges. This statement shows some sort of awareness of that the current system is not fully suitable and that their needs to be a change.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / U. Transform_In-depth_learning_goals

Transform_In-depth_learning_instruments

0 Quotations

Transform_niche_innovations_goals

6 Quotations:

3:43 Ambitie Het positioneren van de Veenkoloniën als experimenteergebied..... (16:603 [16:1047]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Ambitie Het positioneren van de Veenkoloniën als experimenteergebied voor precisielandbouw door het uitvoeren van initiatieven en projecten in de Veenkoloniën en het delen van kennis. Het realiseren van een centrum voor precisielandbouw: • waar praktijkrijpe toepassingen worden gebruikt, zodat de praktische meerwaarde (in euro's) kan worden aangetoond.

- waar nieuwe toepassingen worden ontwikkeld, onderzocht en gevalideerd.

Comment: by buite049

A goal that is specifically focused on accelerating innovations and experimentations in the area of the veenkoloniën. It also wants to bring the innovations in practice

2 Codes:

- Q. Transformability_4 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

3:45 Ontwikkeling van nieuwe toepassingen (meerjarig testen) van een stik..... (17:900 [17:1180]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Ontwikkeling van nieuwe toepassingen (meerjarig testen) van een stikstof bijbemestingssysteem in zetmeelaardappelen (uitbouwen/testen van bestaande toepassing), rijenbemesting met nieuwe precisietechnieken, opbrengstmeettechnieken en ziektedetectie met vision-technologie.

2 Codes:

- Q. Transformability_4 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

3:99 Studie naar technologieën voor de terugwinning van mineralen waaronder..... (23:978 [23:1281]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkolonien

Studie naar technologieën voor de terugwinning van mineralen waaronder, maar niet uitsluitend, membraantechnologie, electrolyse en fysische scheidingstechnieken. Het

project omvat inventarisatie van mogelijke technologieën, het vaststellen van een 'proof of principle' door laboratorium studies.

2 Codes:

J. Adaptability_3 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

10:57 Eventueel benodigde fysieke investeringen voor agrariërs wil ik onde..... (11:1723 [11:1990]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Eventueel benodigde fysieke investeringen voor agrariërs wil ik ondersteunen voor het ontwikkelen van nieuwe prototypes die in de praktijk getest moeten worden en voor de uitrol van innovaties in de land- en tuinbouw zoals precisielandbouw en duurzame stallen.

Comment: by buite049

It is focused on prototypes (niche innovations), but these innovations mentioned are focused on improving the production

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

18:41 Inmiddels ligt er een Plan van Aanpak en is er een netwerk gevormd m..... (12:1940 [12:2286]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Inmiddels ligt er een Plan van Aanpak en is er een netwerk gevormd met partijen als Louis Bolk Instituut, GrAJK, Werkgroep Grauwe Kiekendief, BoerenNatuur, RuG, LTO Noord en Natuur en Milieufederatie. Gezamenlijk willen wij in 2017 een pilotprogramma ontwikkelen met natuurinclusieve experimenten, die aansluiten bij de boerenpraktijk.

Comment: by buite049

There is a network that is exclusively organised to develop pilot programmes and experiments regarding nature inclusive agriculture --> to work on new agricultural forms (niche) --> very enabling

2 Codes:

L. Adaptability_5 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

18:51 De provincie wil projecten die daadwerkelijk bijdragen aan innovat..... (16:170 [16:330]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

De provincie wil projecten die daadwerkelijk bijdragen aan innovaties in de landbouw ondersteunen en begeleiden en stelt daar middelen voor beschikbaar.

Comment: by buite049

instruments and financial means are available to support innovation

2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / W. Transform_niche_innovations_goals

Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

13 Quotations:

3:47 Het ontwerpen van een demobedrijf op proeflocatie 't Kompas waar zov..... (17:365 [17:894]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

Het ontwerpen van een demobedrijf op proeflocatie 't Kompas waar zoveel mogelijk technieken in de bedrijfsvoering worden ingezet. Hiertoe wordt geïnvesteerd in nieuwe technieken, deels in samenwerking met partijen beschikbaar gesteld op locatie. Precisielandbouw wordt in de managementcyclus geïntegreerd door gebruik te maken van geo-data, genereren van plaats specifieke adviezen, monitoring van tijdsinzet, besparingen op inputs en opbrengsteffecten, etc. en landbouwkundige en bedrijfseconomische evaluatie.

2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

3:91 2.000.000 (33:296 [33:304]) - D 3: (InnovatieVeenkoloniën, 2014) [Prov] Innovatieprogramma Veenkoloniën

2.000.000

4 Codes:

I. Adaptability_2 / O. Transformability_2 / P. Adapt_social_learning_instruments / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

4:13 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:65:552-3:491:578) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Garantstelling voor marktintroductie van risicovolle innovaties (GMI) 	1,0	2,5	3,5
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2 Codes:

Q. Transformability_4 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

4:20 (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3) (3:68:433-3:468:455) - D 4: (Dijksma, 2014B) [NL] kamerbrief-over-invulling-plattelandontwikkelingsprogramma-2014-2020 (3)

Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investerings voor ontwikkeling en uitrol van innovaties 	4,8	4,8	9,6
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Comment: by buite049

*resources for experimenting and to innovate.
However it is broadly described and not really sure which innovations are meant.
Perhaps it can be considered as a buffer resource, however it is focused on innovations.*

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

6:81 M16.2 Support for pilot projects and for the development of new prod..... (20:2683 [20:2797]) - D 6: (EC, 2016) [EU] Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP

M16.2 Support for pilot projects and for the development of new products, practices, processes and technologies

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

7:25 Om de sector en de regio te steunen in de overgang naar 2019, wil ik..... (10:184 [10:562]) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Om de sector en de regio te steunen in de overgang naar 2019, wil ik de steun van mijn departement aan het Innovatieprogramma continueren. Ik oormerk daarvoor in overleg met de provincies 1 min euro per jaar aan POP3-middelen, die Groningen en Drenthe met een gelijk bedrag zullen cofinancieren. Daarnaast reserveer ik hiervoor nog 1 min euro per jaar uit de eerste pijler.

Comment: by buite049

Financial resources reserved for a programme specifically focused on innovation in the region and the potato sector

2 Codes:

R. Transformability_5 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

7:35 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:80:352-19:458:363) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

investerings voor ontwikkeling en uitrol van innovaties 4,7 - 4,7 9,4

Comment: by buite049

investments for innovations, however not clear if its about niche innovations. In the previous text it seemed that innovations are mostly used to continue the current trajectory instead of transforming it. --> slightly enabling.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

7:37 (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1) (19:83:393-19:462:406) - D 7: (Dijksma, 2014A) [NL] kamerbrief-uitwerking-directe-betalingen-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (1)

Content

garantstelling marktintroductie risicovolle innovaties 1,0 2,5 - 3,5

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

10:83 Aanvullend aan dit pakket voer ik een landsdekkende garantstellingsr..... (11:2238 [11:3253]) - D 10: (Dijksma, 2013) [NL] kamerbrief-over-implementatie-gemeenschappelijk-landbouwbeleid (2)

Aanvullend aan dit pakket voer ik een landsdekkende garantstellingsregeling voor de marktintroductie voor risicovolle innovaties (GMI) in, zoals ik heb aangekondigd in de Beleidsbrief Tuinbouw (Kamerstuk 32627, nr.14), voor de tuinbouw en andere sectoren, uitgevoerd door het Rijk. Het op de markt brengen van nieuwe producten en productiesystemen gaat gepaard met aanzienlijke risico's voor de betreffende ondernemer en wordt belemmerd door extra voorwaarden aan de financiering vanwege het risicovolle karakter (afzetmarkt en hoge kostprijs). Met de GMI wordt de drempel van de eerste toepassingen van risicovolle innovaties, die maatschappelijk gewenst zijn, verlaagd.

Het bedrag dat voor dit pakket van innovatie- en concurrentiekrachtmaatregelen in POP3 wordt gereserveerd is ongeveer €20 miljoen. Het betreft ruim €10 miljoen aan Europese cofinanciering. De provincies cofinancieren dit met €8 miljoen en het Rijk zal de cofinanciering dragen voor de GMI voor ongeveer €2 miljoen per

Comment: by buite049

A specific instrument that should help new (niche) innovations to be introduced to the market.

It is noticed that new innovations can sometimes not be able to reach their potential on the market. They will therefore be financially supported + the budget is clearly described --> highly enables enhancing and accelerating niche innovations.

2 Codes:

R. Transformability_5 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

12:24 Daarnaast is het de bedoeling om hieruit jaarlijks een klein aantal..... (8:2867 [8:3193]) - D 12: (Provincie Groningen, 2012) [Prov] Groningen Landbouwagenda_2012-2015 (1)

Daarnaast is het de bedoeling om hieruit jaarlijks een klein aantal projecten te financieren, die een rol (kunnen) krijgen als boegbeeld voor de verduurzaming, de zogenaamde 'ster'-projecten.

Focus daarbij ligt op projecten die bijdragen aan vergroening van de landbouw en aan de echte kwaliteitssprongen in de landbouw

Comment: by buite049

slightly enabling --> it is a instrument that is supportive to the introduction of innovation / projects that improve the quality of the agriculture. however, it is not specifically focused on niche innovations, but on interesting projects .

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

18:21 Ondersteuning van innovatieve projecten: voor projectinitiatieven fu..... (9:2389 [9:2715]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Ondersteuning van innovatieve projecten: voor projectinitiatieven fungeert de provincie als loket voor zowel inhoudelijke als financiële ondersteuning.

Hiervoor zijn provinciale middelen (IKS) en EUmiddelen beschikbaar (POP3), waarmee kleinere (IKS) en grotere (POP3) innovaties financieel kunnen worden ondersteund.

Comment: by buite049

Instrument to support the acceleration of innovative projects, however it is not really specific if this is about niche innovations --> fairly enabling

2 Codes:

P. Transformability_3 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

18:47 Daarnaast willen wij ter uitvoering van de AgroAgenda initiatieven v..... (14:548 [14:1079]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

Daarnaast willen wij ter uitvoering van de AgroAgenda initiatieven voor specifieke thema's als b.v. nieuwe teelten of precisielandbouw, die zich kunnen ontwikkelen tot (icoon)projecten van noordelijke betekenis, blijven ondersteunen.

Uitgangspunt is dat voor financiering van projecten in beginsel een beroep moet worden gedaan op beschikbare fondsen als POP3. Onze faciliterende rol heeft vooral betrekking op ondersteuning in gevallen waarin niet of nog niet gebruik van deze mogelijkheden kan worden gemaakt.

2 Codes:

O. Transformability_2 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments

18:49 • Waar nodig ondersteunen van noordelijke icoonprojecten voor specifieke..... (15:92 [15:171]) - D 18: (Provincie Groningen, 2017) [Prov] Groningen Programma-Duurzame-Landbouw-2017-2020 (1)

- Waar nodig ondersteunen van noordelijke icoonprojecten voor specifieke thema's

Comment: by buite049

| *Vague what is really meant with this and how it will work out etc.*

2 Codes:

M. Transformability_0 / X. Transform_niche_innovations_instruments